

Impact of IoT, Visibility and Dynamic Data Information Processing Capabilities on Firm Performance

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To My Parents and My Family

Declaration

This dissertation is the result of my own work and includes nothing, which is the outcome of work done in collaboration except where specifically indicated in the text. It has not been previously submitted, in part or whole, to any university of institution for any degree, diploma, or other qualification.

Tahera Kalsoom

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Abstract

Despite extensive research in Internet of Things (IoT) domain, it has been discovered that study into the links and impacts of IoT, visibility, and DDIPCs is limited. Furthermore, the interdependence of financial and operational flows is rarely acknowledged, and decisions are frequently taken on the basis of other criteria. Current methods do not explicitly address the trade-off between operational and financial decisions, as organisations are not always able to forecast the effect of a decision from both an operational and financial standpoint.

This study provides measurements for IoT impact on company performance based on the resource-based view (RBV) theory and investigates the effects of DDIPCs and visibility on financial and operational performance, with DDIPCs serving as moderator and visibility as mediator. The primary drivers of IoT adoption were determined to be connectivity, flexibility, and agility of IoT devices through an extensive literature review. The findings based on the structural equation modelling (SEM) analysis of data from a survey of 375 UK manufacturing enterprises imply that connectivity has a positive link with IoT use, whereas flexibility and agility have no direct relationship with IoT use. Flexibility and agility were found to have a stronger favourable relationship with firm performance when paired with visibility and DDIPCs. The adoption of IoT has a statistically significant influence on firm performance only when moderated by DDIPCs. This also explains why some manufacturing companies have struggled to obtain expected results after implementing IoT. Hence, an organisation can achieve efficient performance only after utilising a combined force of these five key parameters of connectivity, flexibility, agility, visibility and DDIPCs. Furthermore, the degree to which IoT is used has also an impact on company performance and is dependent on the utilisation of information visibility. It necessitates the businesses to prioritise the adoption of both DDIPCs and visibility instead of focusing solely on IoT implementation.

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List of Research Questions & Hypotheses

Research Questions

RQ1	What is the impact of connectivity, flexibility and agility of IoT devices on the use of IoT in firms in manufacturing industries?
RQ2	How is the use of IoT related to data processing of the firms and how does visibility affect this relationship?
RQ3	What is the impact of use of IoT and visibility gained through interlinked DDIPCs on operational and financial performance?

Hypotheses

H1a	Connectivity of IoT devices is positively related to the use of IoT.
H1b	Flexibility of IoT devices is positively related to the use of IoT.
H1c	Agility of IoT devices is positively related to the use of IoT.
H2a	Use of IoT has a direct and positive impact on financial performance.
H2b	Use of IoT has a direct and positive impact on operational performance.
H3a	Visibility mediates the relationship between use of IoT and financial performance.
H3b	Visibility mediates the relationship between use of IoT and operational performance.
H4a	DDIPCs moderate the relationship between use of IoT and financial performance.
H4b	DDIPCs moderate the relationship between use of IoT and operational performance.
H5a	DDIPCs moderate the relationship between visibility and financial performance.
H5b	DDIPCs moderate the relationship between visibility and operational performance.

Nomenclature

IoT	Internet of Things
I4.0	Industry 4.0
DDIPCs	Dynamic Data Information Processing Capabilities
RBV	Resource based view
IT	Information Technology
SEM	Structural Equation Modelling
EFA	Exploratory Factor Analysis
CFA	Confirmatory Factor Analysis
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
CPS	Cyber-Physical Systems
CIM	Computer-Integrated Manufacturing
CNC	Computer Numerical Control
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
CAPP	Computer-Aided Processing Planning
BDA	Big Data Analytics
AI	Artificial Intelligence
VR	Virtual Reality
WSNs	Wireless Sensor Networks
M2M	Machine-to-Machine
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification

SLR	Systematic Literature Review
PMM	Performance Measurement and Management
SCM	Supply Chain Management
SC	Supply Chain
MAS	Multi-Agent System
CIoT	Connectivity of IoT
FIoT	Flexibility of IoT
AIoT	Agility of IoT
UIoT	Use of IoT
FPerf	Financial Performance
OPerf	Operational Performance
RQ	Research Question
EBITDA	Earnings Before Interest, Tax, Depreciation and Amortisation
EVA	Economic Value Added
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
VIF	Variance Inflation Factor
KMO	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin
AVE	Average Variance Extracted
CR	Composite Reliability
GFI	Goodness of Fit
AGFI	Adjusted Goodness of Fit
SRMR	Standardised Root Mean Square Residual
RMR	Room Mean square Residual
RMSEA	Root Mean Square Error of Approximation
IFI	Incremental Fir Index
CFI	Comparative Fit Index

χ^2	Chi-square
df	Difference
MI	Modification Indices
λ	Factor Loadings
δ_i	Error variance
CMB	Common Method Bias
β	Standardised Coefficients
CLF	Common Latent Factor

Chapter 1 Introduction

This chapter presents a brief research background, discussing the important concepts related to the study. Brief details of the implementation and benefits of Internet of Things (IoT) in manufacturing industry are provided based on secondary data. It is followed by the problem identification, research objectives, contribution and structure of the thesis.

1.1 Research Background

IoT is the next technological marvel, allowing communication and information exchange between items via network-connected ubiquitous gadgets, while eliminating human engagement. IoT, which is rapidly gaining traction, has the potential to usher in a new era of technological innovation. It not only connects everyday useable devices, but it also opens up a number of new commercial prospects (Ling *et al.*, 2017; Rao *et al.*, 2019). Currently, there are about 10 million M2M devices connected, which is merely the beginning of IoT growth, with over 24 billion to 50 billion total connected devices predicted in the next five years (Birkel *et al.*, 2020). At present, many firms have adopted IoT while upgrading or replacing their Information Technology (IT) systems, projecting the benefits of IoT ranging from reductions in cost to enhanced safety; and increased responsiveness to completely new revenue streams. The adoption of dynamic data and information processing capabilities of organisations (DDIPCs) has made business operations more agile (Wamba *et al.*, 2017; Akhtar *et al.*, 2018), resulting in firms achieving better productivity and efficiency (Nagy *et al.*, 2018; Mastos *et al.*, 2020), thus enhancing their firm performance (Kalsoom *et al.*, 2021).

Microsoft and other major IT businesses have emphasised the importance of IoT technology and its link to operational efficiency, data, and informed decision-making. Big IT enablers such as Cisco, Ericsson, and International Data Corporation (IDC) estimate that by 2025, there will

be more than 50 billion connected devices with a \$7 trillion market share (Tang *et al.*, 2018). For companies who accept this technology, it opens up a world of possibilities. Firms are seeking for ways to capitalise on commercial opportunities created by the application of new technologies to new markets (Tsiatsis *et al.*, 2018). According to the Vodafone IoTs barometer, 76 percent of businesses consider IoT to be critical to their future success, and 90 percent have already integrated IoT into their IT systems; 63 percent of these early adopters expect a 20 percent rise in earnings (Weking *et al.*, 2019; Ahmed *et al.*, 2021), with projections of improved accurate data collection, enhanced employee productivity, better asset utilisation and customer loyalty. Majority of these adopters are firms in the manufacturing sector. With demands on the rise for customisation, output quality and quantity in addition to increasing operational complexity, manufacturers are looking for innovative solutions to respond to emerging challenges. This rise has led to the emergence of Industry 4.0 (I4.0), with enhanced usage of technologies such as IoT, big data, artificial intelligence (AI) and block-chain. This research focuses on the use of IoT by manufacturing firms in broader terms.

Leminen *et al.*, (2018) claimed that IoT and the corresponding resources of a firm affected the effectiveness of business operations, resulting in improved firm performance. Studies have shown that factors which govern the use of IoT, and DDIP capabilities are the key domains that characterise IoT-performance link (Zanella *et al.*, 2017; Lu *et al.*, 2018; Mehami *et al.*, 2018). Performance measurement is considered to be the most basic activity for assessing a firm's competitive success (Torres *et al.*, 2018). Scholars have defined firm performance as the ability of a business to efficiently use available resources to achieve targets as visualised in the plans and goals of the company, keeping in mind their relevance to their target market (Rao *et al.*, 2019; Kumar *et al.*, 2020; Alhawari *et al.*, 2021). A measure of performance of a company not only depends on its own efficiency but also on the market in which it operates. In other words, it implies the organizational performance including product and service manufacture, function of different units, employee performance and their productivity. Firm performance, therefore, refers to an organization's efficacy, which includes both financial and operational performance (Thong *et al.*, 1996; Fadhilah *et al.*, 2019). Firm performance in operational terms means the company advantage in the context of its business development, introduction to

innovations, use of management strategies, organization of production and other processes conducted by the company (Côte-Real *et al.*, 2019). Whereas, in financial terms, firm performance implies the company advantage in the context of value of company assets, costs including fixed and variable costs, and gains in product quantity and revenues. Therefore, in order to get a complete picture of the performance of a firm, both operational and financial aspects of firm performance need to be considered.

In today's technologically advanced world of IoT, a company's ability to use IoT and DDIP linked to its capabilities demonstrates not only its agility and decision-making process (Ortiz *et al.*, 2014; Oztemel *et al.*, 2020; Tariq *et al.*, 2020), but also its operational and financial performance (Fan *et al.*, 2016; Fadhilah *et al.*, 2019). Current study into how IoT will affect firm performance is minimal (Akhtar *et al.*, 2018; Boyes *et al.*, 2018; Tang *et al.*, 2018; Côte-Real *et al.*, 2020; Chiarini, 2021). The fundamental reason for this is that IoT research is restricted to certain domains such as IoT infrastructure and IoT management; and explanations of the influence of IoT on business performance are thin on the ground (Ortiz *et al.*, 2014; Ng *et al.*, 2017; Al-Surmi *et al.*, 2019). With the rise in academic interest in IoT, there is currently a lack of understanding of the influence of IoT on firm performance (Mikalef *et al.*, 2017; Chae *et al.*, 2018; Wagner *et al.*, 2018; Afzal *et al.*, 2019). The majority of recent study has focused on determining the influence of IoT on a company's operational agility and competitive performance (Tse *et al.*, 2016; Akhtar *et al.*, 2018). Academic research on how IoT affects a company's operational agility is still in its early stages, according to Akhtar *et al.* (2018). In addition, current studies on firm performance either consider operational aspects or financial aspects separately, overlooking the interdependence of operational and financial flows in a firm. Above all, there are no clear theoretical bases for the influence of IoT and DDIPs on a company's operational and financial performance (Figay *et al.*, 2012; Xu *et al.*, 2016; Birkel *et al.*, 2020; Côte-Real *et al.*, 2020).

As per the author's research on this domain, manufacturing industry in the present day is undergoing a shift in perspective to enhance flexibility and agility within their operations in order to react swiftly and effectively (Kalsoom *et al.*, 2021) to constantly changing customer requirements, evolving technologies, and increasing product variations (Côte-Real *et al.*,

2020). In order to comprehend the effective use of IoT in the manufacturing business, it is necessary to recognise the various variables that may be used to assess the effectiveness of IoT. Research has identified three key determinants that make adoption of IoT an attraction for manufacturers – connectivity, flexibility and agility of IoT devices.

- **Connectivity** – Scholars have defined connectivity of IoT as the degree to which things are networked together (Andreev, 2014; Galinina *et al.*, 2017). Stable network connections are needed to sense, gather, process and facilitate data. As IoT system connects uniquely identifiable, embedded devices and sensors that have the ability to gather and transmit data, certain system requirements should be met that guarantee seamless end-to-end connections. For example, data can be quickly and easily collected to arrange maintenance for a machine failure and jobs can be scheduled on more accurate cycle times as a result of steady connection between IoT devices.
- **Flexibility** – Sharing data and connecting devices over the IoT can be accomplished using a variety of software/hardware layers and standard protocols. The utilisation of software/hardware and standard protocols will become more sophisticated as the amount of shared data and connected devices grows. As a result, flexible design aids in the handling of various wireless protocols, the reduction of power consumption, and the addition of new sensor outputs (Secchi *et al.*, 2019). For instance, system designers and operations managers can encounter numerous obstacles when putting large-scale IoT cloud systems into practise, due to different requirements of these systems in terms of IoT infrastructure flexibility. This imposes on the need to have a flexible IoT architecture to enable smooth working of different devices that adapt to user experience.
- **Agility** – One of the main attractions of IoT is its ability to respond quickly to changes, also known as smart response. The ability of IoT to manage faults and modifications in a timely manner has been described as one of the drivers for firms adopting IoT (Warner *et al.*, 2018). For example, firms can now change their productions from blue shirts to red shirts in response to the change in customer preferences for a particular season. This is achievable with the integration of data collected from IoT devices that lets the firms know about what customers demand for a new season.

With the increased connection of its devices and the flexibility of deploying IoT on many platforms, IoT technology has the ability to give businesses and communities with nearly endless opportunities. Cloud-based IoT platforms can connect the physical and virtual worlds, allowing businesses to manage IoT device connection and flexibility (Mehami *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, IoT design must be adaptable enough to support many wireless protocols as well as the inclusion of new sensor inputs (e.g. USB) (Giri *et al.*, 2017; Aydiner *et al.*, 2019). This is also true in terms of physical flexibility, which can include wearable gadgets, carry devices, and battery usages, among other things (Ortiz *et al.*, 2014). Because the majority of IoT devices are unique, connecting them can rapidly become hard. As a result, IoT's connectivity and flexibility can be used to assess the situation and efficient use of IoT in a firm. Aside from the connectivity and flexibility of IoT technology, another term associated with IoT is device agility. A responsive design of IoT architecture, according to Um (2017), allows for consistent presentation of information that adapts to the viewers' preferences. Aside from achieving flexibility, agility, and resilience, IoT has provided businesses with substantial insight of the entire business process, a critical momentum for quick responses to changes, and excellent integration between suppliers and customers.

IoT has gained relevance in modern business since it allows supplier integration and prioritises stakeholder interaction as the cornerstone for driving firm performance improvement. IoT applications enable autonomous coordination between things, and communication between humans and things in manufacturing processes is elevated to new heights (Ben-Daya *et al.*, 2019; Weking *et al.*, 2019). The acquisition, exchange, and elaboration of operational knowledge on time, according to Ardito *et al.* (2019), is the key to success for business processes. The data generated by smart objects can provide unprecedented visibility into all phases of corporate processes by effectively collecting, analysing and turning that data into useful information (Ellis *et al.*, 2018), delivering early warnings of internal and external issues that need to be addressed. Visibility, as defined by scholars, is the transparency of information exchanged, as well as the ability of firms to act on such information. To achieve the objectives of delivering exceptional results in product manufacturing and distribution, manufacturers must have access to information about all parts of the production process. With connected

machines, the manufacturing leaders, plant managers and operators can have insight into all their machines tracking performance as per the production goals. A common example of benefits of visibility is the supply chain (SC), where the amount and time of inventory shipped from the port to the truck to the warehouse is visible to the entire SC, making tracking of products easier for the manufacturers.

However, it has been argued that firms tend to employ dynamic capabilities to reveal the nature of information visibility in today's extremely volatile markets, which can help them to control external turbulences (Brusset *et al.*, 2017). DDIPCs can be defined as organizational and analytical skills of the firms that enable a firm to achieve competitive advantage. These are skills that allow firms to recognise opportunities, grasp them and act upon them to stay relevant in the digital economy (Akhtar *et al.*, 2018). Product development routines, strategic decision making routines, knowledge generation routines and alliance routines are all examples of DDIPCs. DDIPCs are one of the most important capabilities for processing and generating knowledge from the huge amounts of data generated from IoT devices, therefore, for instance, making tracking of products from ship containers to the truck and to the warehouse easier by using analytical skills to make useful information visible to the SC network.

Though a recent term, referring to the convergence of IoT, visibility, and DDIPCs, there was a business underpinning, with the primary focus on the traceability of the entities involved in the activities (Brandon-Jones *et al.*, 2014; Ahmed *et al.*, 2021). However, a thorough examination reveals that a clear specification on transparency is missing. While IoT-based part of visibility focuses on the organization's ability to gather and assess data in order to achieve a fit between strategy and goals, the inventory and operations interpretations show how a lack of visibility across both upstream and downstream processes has an impact the efficacy of the progression of the manufacturing processes (Yen *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, much of the literature on IoT visibility has focused solely on the benefits to an organization's financial and operational performance, such as inventory, quality, lead time, sales, and costs (Kharlamov *et al.*, 2018; Somapa *et al.*, 2018).

A number of academic research has been carried out to investigate the impact of IoT on several aspects of the manufacturing business, including sustainability, organisational structure, lean manufacturing, product development, and strategic management. Within industry 4.0, the majority of these studies focus on the contributions and risks of IoT in terms of flexibility, transparency, information exchange, connectivity, traceability, and tracking. Despite extensive research in these domains, it has been discovered that research into the links and impacts of IoT, visibility, and DDIPCs is limited. Furthermore, the majority of study into the influence of IoT, visibility, and DDIPCs in the manufacturing industry is still theoretical, and the leading technologies that promote visibility have yet to be discovered.

1.2 Problem Identification

Among all of the technological aspects, the introduction of IoT has had a significant impact on enterprises' production approaches and has significantly transformed operational and financial structures. However, the significance of IoT in manufacturing has yet to be fully explored in terms of firm performance. The relevant literature on the subject is generally fragmented, with most of it focusing on in-depth analyses of specific examples, with an emphasis on engineering factors. Following the debate above, three holes in the present literature have been discovered. The first gap is that studies on the impact of IoT and real-time data visibility are lacking. Furthermore, the visibility of real-time data and its impact on business performance following the implementation of IoT technology has received little attention. The second flaw is that the elements that define IoT device use (connectivity, flexibility, and agility), as well as their impact on firm performance, have been overlooked. The final gap is that past research has focused on the influence of IoT with interconnected DDIPCs on operational agility and competitive advantage, two distinct dimensions of firm performance, leaving little room for comparison.

1.3 Research Objectives and Questions

The main aim of this research is to examine the impact of the use of IoT and visibility with interlinked DDIPCs on operational and financial performance of manufacturing firms in the UK. This research aims to contribute to the domain of IoT adoption and use of DDIPCs within manufacturing firms. Furthermore, it is hoped that this study will help the practitioners to gain better understanding of using a combination of IoT, visibility and DDIPCs to improve firm performance. In this context, this research intends to answer the following questions:

1. What is the impact of connectivity, flexibility and agility of IoT devices on the use of IoT in firms in manufacturing industries?
2. How is the use of IoT related to data processing of the firms and how does visibility affect this relationship?
3. What is the impact of use of IoT and visibility gained through interlinked DDIPCs on operational and financial firm performance?

The following aims will aid in meeting the overall goal of this study and answering the research questions listed above:

1. Understand the background and current situation
 - i) To investigate how connectivity, flexibility and agility of IoT devices affects the use of IoT in manufacturing firms.
 - ii) To review the extant literature related to the diffusion of IoT technology in Industry 4.0 and its impact on firm performance.
2. Develop and assess a conceptual framework that grabs the significant factors influencing IoT usage and its impact on firm performance including:
 - i) Connectivity, flexibility and agility of IoT devices
 - ii) Visibility of information
 - iii) DDIP capabilities
3. Examine the effect on the model by using visibility as a mediator in the model.
4. Examine the effect of using DDIPC as moderator in the model.

5. To empirically validate the model in terms of data gathered from UK manufacturing firms.
6. Provide recommendations that emerge from the research that will help practitioners to improve firm performance using IoT technologies.

1.4 Contribution of the Research

The goal of this research is to better understand the interaction between IoT, visibility, DDIPCs, and firm performance, with DDIPCs serving as a moderator and visibility serving as a mediator. Understanding the relationship between these variables can aid policymakers, industry leaders, and specialists in determining the influence of IoT on business performance. This can assist management in achieving the most effective IoT implementation as well as improving their strategic technological decision-making in the future. Before introducing any new technology, they can choose the best strategy that meets their vision. The outcomes of this study will aid system developers in understanding how they might improve their management systems in the context of firm performance. Similarly, management can determine what reasons and variables drive IoT implementation and what influence technology has on their performance.

This research built a paradigm that employs resource-based view at the macro level to understand the influence of IoT on business performance using visibility and DDIPCs from an academic standpoint. To the best of our knowledge, no other study has measured these characteristics in the context of the manufacturing industry in the United Kingdom. As a result, future researchers can utilise this study as a roadmap to better understand the influence of IoT on firm performance using indirect effects of visibility (mediator) and DDIPCs (moderator).

The importance of this research is provided below:

1. This research provides knowledge about the features of IoT, which contribute as the main drivers behind increasing implementation of IoT technologies in manufacturing

firms. The exploratory factor analysis provides factors that make IoT adaptable in these firms – connectivity, flexibility and agility of IoT technologies.

2. The goal of this research is to provide a theoretical framework that will help us better comprehend the influence of IoT and real-time data visibility with interconnected DDIPCs on firm performance. This will be achieved by building an inter-relationship between the use of IoT, visibility, DDIPCs; and operational and financial performance of a firm. As academic research on using dynamic data from IoT to improve operational agility and competitive advantage is emerging, answering the question of how they impact firm performance from both operational and financial perspectives will considerably contribute in closing the gap in the operational and IT domains. This paper will be an enhancement of the work done by (Mikalef *et al.*, 2017; Akhtar *et al.*, 2018), who focused on the impact of IoT on operational agility and competitive advantage of a firm respectively.
3. The multi-variate analysis conducted by using SEM will provide results that will either support or reject the theoretical framework, helping to develop a framework that will help practitioners to enhance both operational and financial firm performance using IoT in manufacturing processes.

1.5 Research Publications

The author's main contributions to research include the investigation and analysis of the impact of IoT and I4.0 on firm performance. Main focus has been on the drivers and challenges of adopting IoT in manufacturing industry, impact of IoT on information visibility within supply chains and use of smart sensors in manufacturing industry.

Journal and conference papers published by the author during this work include:

1.5.1 Journal Papers

1. **Kalsoom, T.**, Ahmed, S., Rafi-Ul-Shan, M. P., Azmat, M., Pervez, Z., Pervez, Z., Imran, M. A. and Ur Rehman, M. (2021) 'Impact of IoT on manufacturing industry 4.0: A new triangular systematic review', *Sustainability* 13 (22): 12506.
2. **Kalsoom, T.**, Ahmed, S., Ramzan, N. and Ur Rehman, M. (2020) 'Advances in sensor technologies in the era of smart factory and industry 4.0', *Sensors* 20 (23), 6783.

1.5.2 Conference Papers

1. **Kalsoom, T.**, Ahmed, S. and Ramzan, N. (2021) 'Impact of use of IoT, visibility and dynamic data information processing capabilities on firm performance', The 25th International Symposium on Logistics (ISL), 10-13 July 2021, Nottingham, UK.
2. **Kalsoom, T.**, Ahmed, S. and Ramzan, N. (2020) 'Societal impact of IoT-lead smart factory in the context of Industry 4.0', 5th International Conference on UK-China Emerging Technologies (UCET), 20-21 August 2020, Glasgow, UK.

1.6 Thesis Structure

The structure of the thesis is as follows (Figure 1.1):

Chapter 2 provides an in-depth literature review of the use and importance of IoT in manufacturing industry. The use of IoT is discussed from the user perspective, using connectivity, flexibility and agility of IoT to define adaptability of this technology in manufacturing firms. This helps to gain insight into the chronological development of theories and evidence of studies related to the impact of IoT and visibility with DDIPCs on firm performance (both operational and financial). This chapter also delivers information about the framework chosen for this research followed by the strategies and literature reviewed in this research.

The research's conceptual framework and assumptions are developed in *Chapter 3*. The key factors of IoT that will have an impact on performance are identified, conceptualised, and measured in this chapter. The following constructs are identified, developed, and measured based on a thorough literature review: connectivity, flexibility, and agility of IoT, use of IoT, visibility and DDIPCs. Next, financial performance is measured with indicators: sales, return on investment, market value added and return on assets; whereas operational performance is measured using: cost, flexibility, innovation, quality and delivery. Finally, the theoretical framework is established. Subsequently research hypotheses are proposed which explain such effects.

Chapter 4 outlines the methodology adopted in this research. The chapter highlights the research philosophy adopted for this study, followed by justifications of the choice. Moreover, research strategy is presented, followed by research design, to show how the research has been conducted and why the choices have been made. The research objectives are achieved by providing answers to the research questions by using surveys as method of data collection. In addition, this chapter provides information about the data analysis techniques used before and after testing the survey data and hypotheses.

Chapter 5 gives the preliminary data analysis done to show how the data has been prepared for structural equation modelling (SEM). Detailed results of exploratory factor analysis (EFA) have been provided using SPSS 26. Results of the survey data are provided such as factor analysis, construct validity and reliability, and correlations.

Chapter 6 presents results of model testing using SEM in AMOS 26. Measurement model and structural model are tested to show the results of hypotheses. The set of hypotheses are examined by using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) followed by structural model testing. A revised version of the conceptual framework is presented that shows the relationships between constructs as confirmed by SEM. The findings in this chapter provide answers to research questions RQ1 through RQ3.

Chapter 7 gives a comprehensive discussion on the findings based on data analysis and hypothesis testing. The impact of the key determinants of IoT on use of IoT is discussed in this

chapter and how the direct and indirect effects impact firm performance. Theory and literature are used to support these discussions. This chapter summarises the findings, as well as their contribution to theory and practise, as well as their limitations and future research. It summarises the key concerns, such as IoT adoption by manufacturing companies and the extent to which it affects firm performance when moderated by DDIPCs and mediated by visibility (direct and indirect effects). This chapter discusses the contribution and implications for theory building and empirical evidence for practitioners based on the discussion of the outcomes. The proposed managerial implications assist businesses in developing competencies to adopt, combine, and manage IoT technologies in order to improve and enhance their financial performance.

Figure 1.1: Thesis structure

1.7 Summary

This chapter provided the background of the research by providing an overview of the topic under study. In addition, research aims and objectives, contributions and significance of this research were covered, followed by an outline and brief description of the structure of the thesis. The following chapter will provide an in-depth literature review highlighting the importance of IoT in I4.0 and its impact on firm performances.

Chapter 2 Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter commences with a detailed explanation of IoT and a detailed examination of the uses of IoT in manufacturing industry. It provides knowledge about different IoT enabled technologies used in manufacturing firms, followed by the importance of IoT in Industry 4.0 according to the theories of studies in IoT. The review of the literature covers the conceptualization of the impact of connectivity, flexibility and agility of IoT devices, along with the visibility gained due to IoT technology using DDIPCs and its impact on firm performance.

2.2 What is IoT?

IoT refers to the use of embedded software and sensors to link items to the internet in order to send, gather, and exchange data with one another, eliminating human contact (Abdel-Basset *et al.*, 2018; Leminen *et al.*, 2018). As a result of IoT technologies connecting internet with sensors, devices, and people, a free pattern of conversation is developed between humans and machines (Souri *et al.*, 2019) (Figure 2.1). The digital world appears to have collided with the physical world as advanced nanotechnology continues to evolve, as well as the concept of linking new and old technologies in the form of innovation and economic progress (Mostafa *et al.*, 2019; Rao *et al.*, 2019). Although IoT is all about synchronising Things (Objects) across the Internet (Castelo-Branco *et al.*, 2019). Figure 2.1 depicts the tri-sectional relationship between the three aspects of IoT.

Figure 2.1: Tri-sectional relationship between the three aspects of IoT

As computer technology becomes more miniaturised in the future, typical PC input/output devices such as keyboards and mice will become obsolete as CPUs and sensors become integrated into ordinary objects (Jeon *et al.*, 2020). Our everyday objects, including watches, kettles, and pens, will, on the other hand, interact with those of other people, resulting in a software-human interaction. This allows the items to react to human presence, movement, voice commands, eyeball tracking, face recognition, and even bodily functions like pulse and sleep patterns. There is access available to the people consuming IoT technology, which enables them to sync personal devices with their daily lives. Instead of carrying out these chores manually, some smartphone applications automatically lock doors and arm the security system when the owner leaves the vicinity of the property. Another improvement would be to replace alphanumeric passwords, which are easy to crack, with sensors that can scan personal recognition traits like fingerprints. One of the most recent examples of IoT integration into daily physical products is the use of face recognition and fingertip touch to unlock iPhones. The introduction of bank vehicles in Poland, which travel to business customers so they can deposit their money with convenience, is an emerging example of innovative banking services (Masum *et al.*, 2016). Bluestore Financial, based in Canada, has devised a plan for how self-driving car drivers will pass the time (Azmat *et al.*, 2019). Customers can check their wealth portfolios while driving thanks to innovative interfaces developed for car windscreens (Chiarini, 2021). These are just a few of the many possibilities that IoT technology could bring to the industry.

According to Souri *et al.*, (2019), IoT is a network of things that are wirelessly connected via smart sensors and interact without the need for human involvement. In the healthcare, transportation, home appliances, and automotive industries, several experimental IoT applications have already been developed (Tang *et al.*, 2018; Ben-Daya *et al.*, 2019). The terms "Internet" and "things" refer to a global network that is interconnected and built on sensory, communication, networking, and information processing technologies, and might represent the next generation of information and communications technology (ICT) (Eliza *et al.*, 2013; Lu, 2018; Calatayud *et al.*, 2019). IoT is a new technology paradigm that envisions a global network of machines and gadgets that can communicate with one another, according to Leminen *et al.* (2018). Many new advancements in the integration of items with sensors in the cloud-based Internet have occurred recently (Guha *et al.*, 2018; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2020; Oztemel *et al.*, 2020).

IoT is becoming a reality thanks to rapid improvements in information and communication technology. IoT is the next technological miracle, allowing communication and information exchange between items via network-connected ubiquitous gadgets, eliminating human engagement (Manavalan *et al.*, 2019; Lee *et al.*, 2020). IoT has enormous potential to alter the global economy. Cisco, Ericsson, and IDC estimate that by 2025, there will be more than 50 billion connected devices with a \$7 trillion market share (Tang *et al.*, 2019; Birkel *et al.*, 2020). IoT has applications in practically every aspect of our lives, including utilities, transportation, security, retail, healthcare, government, financial services, agriculture, industry, and information technology (Gardner *et al.*, 2017; Yacchirema *et al.*, 2018). Smart-homes are made up of internet-connected appliances, home automation components, and energy management equipment (Ling *et al.*, 2017). By enabling tele-health systems, personal fitness and health monitors, as well as network-enabled medical services, are revolutionising the healthcare sector (Zanella *et al.*, 2017). It relieves hospital pressure, provides continuous monitoring and convenience to disabled and elderly individuals, increases independence, and decreases costs (Metsis *et al.*, 2016). Improved safety, fuel efficiency, and service are all advantages of connected vehicles and roadways that facilitate intelligent transportation (Oteafy *et al.*, 2018; Nikitas *et al.*, 2020). Smart cities are on the future, and more automation and observation are

expected to boost agricultural, industrial, and energy production by several folds (Minoli *et al.*, 2017; Tortonesi *et al.*, 2019). Commercial drones and robots are expected to transform the construction and logistics industries. Cost-effectiveness, technological innovation, and market competitiveness have all been cited as important driving forces behind current and future mainstream adoption of IoT, notably in the automotive industry (Hendriks, 2016).

Through behavioural monitoring and improved communications, it is also claimed that IoT can improve analytical abilities, software development, infrastructure management, and workforce performance (Nagy *et al.*, 2018; Weking *et al.*, 2019; Ingemarsdotter *et al.*, 2020). It's essentially a paradigm change in how we approach computing. IoT is regarded as an extension of the internet, despite the fact that, unlike the internet, it lacks global coherence and lacks a well-documented design, architecture, and infrastructure (Leminen *et al.*, 2018; Garay-Rondero *et al.*, 2019; Shah *et al.*, 2020). This raises concerns about data security and privacy, as well as the underlying expectation that data will be shared across devices, applications, and perhaps industries. The benefits of IoT, according to some researchers (Hsu *et al.*, 2016; Rymaszewska *et al.*, 2017; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2020; Ahmed *et al.*, 2021), include increased productivity, increased energy and transportation efficiency, and greater control and auditing in manufacturing and supply processes, with the potential to increase industry and global economy value by billions. Increased availability of ubiquitous, low-cost devices (such as sensors, wearables, and smartphones); ubiquitous internet connectivity; and cloud computing services reflect IoT's recent rise, pressuring companies to achieve increased and rapid innovation to maintain competitive advantage (Akter *et al.*, 2016; Celestine *et al.*, 2020).

Globalisation, changing client needs, and advances in information and communication technology (ICT) have all been identified as major drivers (de Vass *et al.*, 2018), resulting in service industry and manufacturing operating strategies reforms (Dallasega *et al.*, 2018; Manavalan *et al.*, 2019; Scharl *et al.*, 2019; Weking *et al.*, 2019). As a result, numerous industries can become more efficient and flexible, resulting in increased production and yield (Nagy *et al.*, 2018). To remain competitive in a globalised context, manufacturing organisations must constantly update their production methods and adapt to changing market demands, customer needs, and supply conditions (Mikalef *et al.*, 2017; Al-Surmi *et al.*, 2020).

As a result, it has a substantial impact on the market and manufacturing industry, as well as the product's entire life cycle (Zekhnini *et al.*, 2020).

Rapidly evolving digital technologies are pushing the globe toward increasingly connected activities in both breadth and size, influencing business management techniques (Rao *et al.*, 2019). Advanced real-time ICT skills enable information to be freely available across a wide range of businesses, reducing lead times and improving responsiveness (Um, 2017). Factory processes, maintenance schedules, and surrounding environments can all be communicated via IoT (Giri *et al.*, 2017). The adoption of IoT makes manufacturing processes more intelligent and dynamic, allowing automation and self-optimization to assist machines and equipment in improving production processes. IoT, which is powered by connection and sensors, enables factories to create actionable, real-time data insights about physical objects in the production and supply chain (Liao *et al.*, 2017; Sarstedt *et al.*, 2018). When these data are integrated with data analytics, new technology, and quicker networks, manufacturers may better maintain their assets and increase production efficiency (Barton *et al.*, 2012; De Mendonca *et al.*, 2018; Jeon *et al.*, 2020). 5G and IoT are considered to be the key drivers to enhance and enable manufacturing processes such as robotic automation, warehouse transportation etc. 5G networks enable manufacturers and IT operators to convert traditional factories into smart factories and take advantage of digital technologies such as automation, AI and augmented reality (AR). 5G provides manufactures with low latency, high reliability, high bandwidth and connection density that allows secure and ubiquitous connectivity to IoT devices. In addition, 5G-IoT ecosystems enable availability of different carrier frequencies for different networked devices. IoT enables firms to improve efficiency and production while also producing massive amounts of data to aid procedural and strategic decision-making, resulting in smart factories (Mostafa *et al.*, 2019). The fundamental aspects of IoT are listed in Table 2.1 for a better conceptual grasp.

Table 2.1. Key elements of IoT

References	Agility	Visibility	Tracking and Information Sharing	Control and Coordination of Processes	Use of Intelligent Interfaces	Sensing and Actuating Abilities	Self-Configuring	Interoperable Communication Protocols	Seamless Integration
(Ben-Daya <i>et al.</i> , 2019)			×		×			×	
(Oztemel <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	×				×				×
(Bassi, 2017)			×				×		
(Gottge <i>et al.</i> , 2019)		×	×						
(Brozzi <i>et al.</i> , 2020)			×	×		×			
(Jardim-goncalves <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	×				×	×		×	
(Rao <i>et al.</i> , 2019)		×	×		×				×
(Boyes <i>et al.</i> , 2018)				×			×		×
(Haddud <i>et al.</i> , 2017)			×		×		×		
(Hofmann <i>et al.</i> , 2017)								×	×
(Garrido-Hidalgo <i>et al.</i> , 2019)			×				×		×
(Kazancoglu <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	×				×				
(Naeem <i>et al.</i> , 2021)				×					×
(Ricci <i>et al.</i> , 2021)					×		×		
(Calış Duman <i>et al.</i> , 2021)		×	×						×
(Chae <i>et al.</i> , 2021)				×					

2.3 Key IoT Determinants in Manufacturing

Scholars have identified certain key determinants that make IoT adoption in manufacturing firms an attraction. However, these studies are highly fragmented and there is a lack of knowledge on the combined effects of these determinants on IoT adoption. The following determinants have been identified that make IoT adaptable in manufacturing firms.

2.3.1 Connectivity

IoT has advanced rapidly in recent years, allowing every device and object to connect to the Internet. IoT refers to the widespread presence and interconnection of billions of intelligent communication objects that let autonomous networks share information more effectively (Lu *et al.*, 2018). Sensors and network platforms are linked together to establish an IoT infrastructure (Jeon *et al.*, 2020; Sharma *et al.*, 2020). The degree to which things are networked might be defined as IoT connectivity (Andreev, 2014; Galinina *et al.*, 2017). Wireless communication technology has successfully integrated into our daily lives. Broadband connectivity now allows consumers to access a wide range of new and advanced consumer services, from entertainment to professional and industrial applications. With the launch of 5G networks, more than 70 billion devices will be connected by 2025, according to Garcia-Murillo *et al.*, (2018) and Mekki *et al.* (2019). With the tremendous rise of M2M communications during the last decade, omnipresent connectivity between devices has been enabled, allowing autonomous connectivity without human involvement (Kim *et al.*, 2015; Galinina *et al.*, 2017; Jeon *et al.*, 2020). Over time, M2M communications have seen a prompt growth and are now acknowledged as the enabling technology for practical implementation of IoT (Farahani *et al.*, 2018; Kimani *et al.*, 2019).

IoT operating system connects uniquely identifiable, embedded computing devices and sensors that may receive and integrate data via a network with minimal/no human-to-human or human-to-computer contact (Kimani *et al.*, 2019; Mekki *et al.*, 2019; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2021). Any IoT device must meet specific essential system criteria in order to perform effectively, such as ensuring steady network connections and efficiently managing system resources (Jeon *et al.*,

2020). Other unique requirements for IoT applications include limited range, low data rate, low energy consumption, and cost effectiveness, all of which must be met for effective performance (Pradhan *et al.*, 2018). With the evolution of IoT roles from simple sensing and transmitting equipment to sensing, gathering, processing, and service roles, periodic requests between IoT devices are on the rise (Sharma *et al.*, 2020). If IoT devices do not receive requests in a timely manner, responses to such requests may be delayed. These transmission delays can negatively affect all IoT devices, causing the entire information exchange chain to be substantially slowed (Pradhan *et al.*, 2018). Firms must overcome enormous hurdles such as connecting massive volumes of different devices in order to conduct such a move effectively without losing crucial data (Galinina *et al.*, 2017).

Creating higher levels of network and service availability in remote and difficult regions, which may be a requirement of a globally running company, can be a significant difficulty in this scenario (Galinina *et al.*, 2017; Dalenogare *et al.*, 2018; Celestine *et al.*, 2020). Firms have a variety of options when it comes to networking. Traditional options include short-range wireless communications such as wireless LAN, Bluetooth Smart (Low Energy Profile), or ZigBee from edge devices to gateways, which are commonly connected to the cloud through Ethernet (Boyes *et al.*, 2018; Garay-Rondero *et al.*, 2019). These are, however, short-range radio technologies that cannot be used for long-distance communications (Mekki *et al.*, 2019). Another option is to use cellular connectivity from IoT devices to transfer data directly to the cloud, which is excellent for long-range transmissions but has the disadvantage of significant power consumption, which makes it unsuitable for transmitting little data within businesses (Farahani *et al.*, 2018; Lass *et al.*, 2020). Different carrier frequencies will be available for various networked devices to operate as the 5G-IoT ecosystem quickly emerges within businesses (Andreev, 2014; Galinina *et al.*, 2017; S. K. Pradhan *et al.*, 2018). However, today's internet infrastructure necessitates a stable connection as well as the requirement for low-latency data exchanges (Farahani *et al.*, 2018; Jeon *et al.*, 2020; Kimani *et al.*, 2019). According to Galinina *et al.*, (2017;) and Kimani *et al.*, (2019), many industry players have identified the need of a further evolution of IoT enabling technologies to facilitate flexible, convergent and seamless connectivity.

2.3.2 Flexibility

From human-interactive wearables to completely automated machine-to-machine (M2M) applications utilised in smart factories, smart homes, and smart cities, IoT market has a wide range of applications. Sensors, such as WSNs and RFIDs, power the majority of IoT applications. These sensors must all meet the same requirement: they must be constantly active in order to collect data from the environment and transfer it to the cloud without interruption (Secchi *et al.*, 2019). These devices should not only run continuously to collect data, but they should also consume less power while performing wireless communication and sensor processing duties (Mehami *et al.*, 2018). These sensors can therefore be classified as important components of operating systems in organizations, which have incorporated IoT products within their operations.

Today's operating systems aren't restricted to a single piece of hardware or a specific piece of software (Brozzi *et al.*, 2020; Sharma *et al.*, 2020). They can be everywhere, cloud-based, and interact with gadgets according on the situation (Nastic *et al.*, 2014; Ly *et al.*, 2018). In a smart home that has embraced an IoT operating system, for example, we can find a fusion of energy management, security, and convenience. The expenditures of lighting and locking the doors to keep the house secure are carefully managed as a result of this inclusion. In addition, in the smart house, there is an element of efficiently giving convenience to the people. As a result of the merging of these three elements into one sensor, the user receives a more personalised and personalised experience. In other words, the user is given flexibility (Williams *et al.*, 2013; Fatorachian *et al.*, 2018). The degree to which IoT goods are adopted, and, more crucially, how convenient they are for the user, is primarily determined by their flexibility (Kazancoglu *et al.*, 2021; Mehami *et al.*, 2018).

IoT can have an impact on business models by opening up new avenues for the development of innovative new models that are long-term viable (Yang *et al.*, 2013; Patel *et al.*, 2016; Lass *et al.*, 2020). These new innovative models facilitate service and operation improvements by not only increasing value for a company by improving brand competence and brand attachment as perceived by customers (Mukherjee *et al.*, 2018), but also improving performance by

reducing human errors (Nascimento *et al.*, 2019; Rao *et al.*, 2019; Birkel *et al.*, 2020; Maisiri *et al.*, 2021). The process of adopting things based on criteria that can improve firm performance can be defined as the flexibility of IoT devices in a firm (Patel *et al.*, 2016; Wagner *et al.*, 2018; Afzal *et al.*, 2019; Punithavathi *et al.*, 2019) and is assessed as a general capability of a firm (Mukherjee *et al.*, 2018). Satisfying their customers in the process of product delivery, which is in turn determined by the firms' architectural flexibility, enhances the competitiveness of a firm (Tang *et al.*, 2019).

Within businesses, cloud computing technologies have been widely used to manage massive amounts of data generated by IoT devices. The cloud, in theory, provides limitless storage, computing, and network capabilities for integrating various types of IoT devices in businesses, as well as an elastic runtime for IoT systems (Oztemel *et al.*, 2020). Scholars believe that most businesses are using cloud-computing approaches to virtualize data generated by physical sensors and actuators (Fatorachian *et al.*, 2018; Mehami *et al.*, 2018; Mukherjee *et al.*, 2018; Sawyerr *et al.*, 2019). Although approaches exist to assist businesses in managing IoT infrastructures (Punithavathi *et al.*, 2019; Matarazzo *et al.*, 2021), the combining of IoT and cloud computing is still in its infancy (Büyüközkan *et al.*, 2018; Oztemel *et al.*, 2020; Wan *et al.*, 2020). System designers and operations managers encounter numerous obstacles when putting large-scale IoT cloud systems into practise, owing to the different requirements of these systems in terms of IoT infrastructure flexibility (Mukherjee *et al.*, 2018; Afzal *et al.*, 2019; Matarazzo *et al.*, 2021). Large-scale IoT cloud systems, for example, rely extensively on cloud and virtualized IoT resources and capabilities (for example, to support complex, computationally expensive analytics), therefore these resources must be accessible, configured, and managed in a unified manner with a single point of management (Mehami *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, while IoT systems are expected to run continuously, they can be scaled down during off-peak periods, such as when demand for a particular data source drops. Because the needs of the various stakeholders in a business are diverse, IoT solutions must provide a variety of customised usage experiences (Beigne *et al.*, 2015; Zhong *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, to utilize the benefits of cloud computing, a flexible IoT infrastructure should be designed and adopted by firms.

Flexible platforms not only promote cross-device communication, but they also collect, validate, and enrich data using analytics before combining it with other resources (Szydło *et al.*, 2017; Secchi *et al.*, 2019). They then allow IoT devices to expose the generated intelligence to apps that produce commercial outcomes such as optimising energy production for a utility or decreasing manufacturing process mistakes. As a result, the architecture of IoT systems must be flexible in terms of handling alternative wireless protocols, minimising power consumption, and adding additional sensor inputs.

2.3.3 Agility

IoT devices are frequently referred to as "smart objects," which are physical things with computing, connectivity, sensing/actuation, and storage capabilities (Birkel *et al.*, 2020). The value of these smart things lies in their ability to make the physical environment smart so that people can receive cyber-physical services (Wan *et al.*, 2020). IoT linked devices are vast and complicated, but even small, mobile, and miniature devices like wearables and sensors consume a lot of power and have different data storage capacity. When many types of IoT devices are used within a single department, data presentation may need to be seen on a variety of devices, including small portable communication terminals like smartphones and displays on other devices. The information can be displayed in a consistent manner that adapts to the viewer's device thanks to a responsive and adaptable design (Gunasekaran *et al.*, 2017; Sawyerr *et al.*, 2019). Scholars predict that as technology advances, future IoT systems will include smart cities, intelligent grids, agile networks, and flexible infrastructures (Tarafdar *et al.*, 2017; Queiroz *et al.*, 2018; Sawyerr *et al.*, 2019). In a dynamic and ever-evolving autonomic system, these systems will be globally interconnected. One of the properties of IoT devices that has attracted enterprises all around the world is smart response (Birkel *et al.*, 2020; Wan *et al.*, 2020). The capacity of IoT to manage faults and modifications in a timely manner has been described as one of the drivers for organisations embracing IoT.

Agility is a tool that helps companies respond more quickly to client needs (Akhtar *et al.*, 2018; Farahani *et al.*, 2018). In other terms, agility is described as an organization's capacity to respond quickly to changes and uncertainty (Hasegan *et al.*, 2018). Braojos *et al.*, (2019)

defined agility as a company's capacity to adapt to or respond to market developments. In addition to these features, agility aids in reacting to internal operational changes and gives more flexibility in day-to-day operations (Akhtar *et al.*, 2018), allowing the firm to take advantage of market opportunities in the external business environment. (Burke *et al.*, 2014).

Managing hundreds of interactions between IoTs can be difficult, and good data organisation is critical for businesses (Rao *et al.*, 2019; Oztemel *et al.*, 2020). A Service Oriented Architecture (SOA) is a traditional approach to data processing used by businesses, in which devices expose their functionality to cloud computing as services (Tao *et al.*, 2018). However, given the massive amounts of data created every second, this strategy may be insufficient. Another issue with this strategy is its lack of responsiveness to events linked with the requirement to transfer data to the cloud and wait for a response. As a result, communication is delayed (Tortonesi *et al.*, 2019). Fog computing is another strategy utilised by modern businesses, with the goal of making logic transfer data-driven rather than service-driven (Yacchirema *et al.*, 2018). Data is shared using this manner by sending messages between the devices. The order in which the procedures are performed determines how long they take to complete. As a result, fog computing aids IoT devices in reducing overall reaction time and improving communication, as response time has a significant impact on overall message exchange. (Zhong *et al.*, 2015; Patel *et al.*, 2016; Szydlo *et al.*, 2017). According to Tarafdar *et al.*, (2017), as the waiting time between devices increases, so does the reaction time of the network environment, slowing down the entire process. One way to improve IoT device responsiveness is to boost the device's processing capability on the server side.

As more computational capabilities in IoT clusters become accessible, demand in delivering flexible and smart response will continue to develop fast (Wan *et al.*, 2020). It is critical to recognise critical data and events, as well as reply fast when something noteworthy occurs, in order to achieve speed and accuracy. A responsive design also enhances the user experience (Szydlo *et al.*, 2017; Oteafy *et al.*, 2018; Oztemel *et al.*, 2020). Users of IoT include not just customers, but also technicians, engineers, families, and others. IoT's flexibility and ability to communicate with small devices is a big selling point.

The emergence of a data-rich business environment has been aided by ubiquitous connectivity of IoT devices within businesses. In today's digitally enhanced corporate worlds, access to information at any time, from any location, and in any format is anticipated. Businesses have recognised the growing necessity to build strategies that reflect their reliance on their digital ecosystems as their customers become increasingly connected to their suppliers via the internet (Oztemel *et al.*, 2020). Customer-facing decision support and dynamic analytic models are examples of best practises in scenario-based planning that anticipates change (Szydlo *et al.*, 2017). The fundamental enablers of agility for digital business success can be identified through the progress of digital relationship between the management and the customers.

Smart devices (e.g., wearables, smartphones), their functions (e.g., Bluetooth, ZigBee, Wi-fi), and cloud computing technologies can efficiently enable device-to-device connections and communications supplied by IoT devices and sensors (Siddiqi *et al.*, 2018; Son *et al.*, 2019). These gadgets transmit data and information in real time, allowing you to track and trace operational resources and workers (Akhtar *et al.*, 2018; Khan *et al.*, 2018). As a result, visibility improves, allowing connected corporate networks to establish more agile processes (Nastic *et al.*, 2014; Akhtar *et al.*, 2018; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2021). In today's business world, agility is critical for firm innovation and competitive success (Akhtar *et al.*, 2018). Firms are progressively using IoT into their daily operations in order to improve their agility. Gunasekaran *et al.*, (2017) and Fosso Wamba *et al.*, (2019) found that the usage of IoT improves response operations in terms of specialised actions, situational assessment, resource allocations, and multi-organizational coordination. Fine-grained knowledge obtained from internet-connected devices and the ability of organisations to successfully receive and send information in a timely manner can help firms become more agile. In fact, IoT enables all business network operations and the adoption of such advanced technologies (Gu *et al.*, 2014; Nastic *et al.*, 2014).

2.4 Industry 4.0

Industrial revolutions have been sparked by massive technology advancements throughout history. The mechanisation of processes defined the first industrial revolution, the second by the introduction of electrically-powered mass production based on the division of labour, and the third by the automation of processes via the use of electronics and computers (Jardim-goncalves *et al.*, 2017; Boyes *et al.*, 2018; Ramirez-Peña *et al.*, 2020) (Figure 2.2). These innovations have enabled the shift of water and steam driven machinery to completely automated production, making manufacturing processes more complicated, automatic, and sustainable (Vaidya *et al.*, 2018; Rao *et al.*, 2019; Lass *et al.*, 2020). The image of industrial production has been transformed by technology-oriented manufacturing practises, computer-integrated manufacturing, lean management, and cellular manufacturing (Dallasega *et al.*, 2018; Brozzi *et al.*, 2020). The term 'Industry 4.0' was coined in Germany in 2011 to describe a strategic German economic programme that emphasised manufacturing computerization (Maisiri *et al.*, 2021). Industry 4.0 became the attention of the German government almost immediately, and it is now being used globally to denote self-sufficient manufacturing processes through the employment of machines and devices that communicate with one another via digital interconnectivity (Afzal *et al.*, 2019; Castelo-Branco *et al.*, 2019). Industry 4.0 is the future of manufacturing (Scharl *et al.*, 2019) and an active study subject for practically an age, despite the fact that most of the design philosophies and technology (such as IoT) are currently in use. Industry 4.0 is an imminent hit rather than a hype, much as uncertainty was the biggest hurdle to the internet in the 1990s, which later emerged as a leading and essential phenomenon (Xu, 2011; Dalenogare *et al.*, 2018; Benitez *et al.*, 2020).

Figure 2.2: Four Industrial Revolutions (Vaidya *et al.*, 2018)

Traditional manufacturing applications are isolated and stand-alone (Chaniyas *et al.*, 2019), with limited automated monitoring and control capabilities (Tibaut *et al.*, 2016). Marketing, product development, manufacturing, and consumer distribution are only a few of the different and independent phases of traditional manufacturing (Holmström *et al.*, 2016; Abdel-Basset *et al.*, 2018; Mostafa *et al.*, 2019; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2020). As a result, traditional manufacturing's system reuse and integration of physical and digital systems is weak (Scharl *et al.*, 2019). Intelligent manufacturing, flexible manufacturing, and agile manufacturing are some innovative manufacturing strategies that have the potential to address the disadvantages of traditional production (Galinina *et al.*, 2017; Xie *et al.*, 2020).

One of the basic foundations of Industry 4.0 is the widespread usage of the internet, serving as a conduit for connecting machines, devices, sensors, and people (Tuptuk *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, the ability to use the internet as a source of real-time data benefits in the development of new product information and features (Tuttokmaği *et al.*, 2019). As a result, massive amounts of sensor data in the form of diagnostics and predictive maintenance collected from multiple locations and plants will help to reduce maintenance costs (Bassi, 2017; Boyes *et al.*, 2018), increase asset availability, and develop new usage-based business models (Nagy *et al.*, 2018; Côte-Real *et al.*, 2019). Business model changes and technological improvements have an impact on corporate performance and long-term viability (Yen *et al.*, 2014; Esposito De Falco *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, in order to remain competitive in a hyper-competitive market, it is essential for manufacturers to adopt this industrial revolution (Gokalp *et al.*, 2017; Tuttokmaği *et al.*, 2019; Benitez *et al.*, 2020; Lass *et al.*, 2020).

The main goal of the Industry 4.0 concept is to distinguish highly digital industrial processes in which the flow of information between devices is regulated in an environment with very little human participation (Castelo-Branco *et al.*, 2019; Benitez *et al.*, 2020; Lass *et al.*, 2020). Industry 4.0 refers to the integration of Cyber-Physical Methods (CPS) with manufacturing processes, resulting in new business models and production systems (Jardim-goncalves *et al.*, 2017; Nascimento *et al.*, 2019). The main difference between Industry 4.0 and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing (CIM) is that Industry 4.0 connects people, machines, and machines to accomplish a quality leap in industrial output (Dalenogare *et al.*, 2018; Dallasega *et al.*,

2018). As a result, there has been a spike in new production systems with faster and more targeted information sharing (Frank *et al.*, 2019; Rauch *et al.*, 2019).

Industry 4.0 is defined by four digital disruptions, according to Aryal *et al.*, (2018): increased big data; computational power and connectivity, especially new low-power wide-area networks; evolution of analytics and business-intelligence capabilities; new patterns of human-machine interaction, such as touch interfaces and augmented reality systems; and advances in transferring digital information to the physical world, such as advanced robotics and 3D printing. According to Park *et al.*, (2014), Sung, (2018) and Lass *et al.*, (2020), Industry 4.0 has pushed automation to a new level by introducing adaptable mass production technology. As a result, machines will have independent functionalities that will constantly try to maintain themselves in order to provide customer-oriented manufacturing with the least amount of human interaction possible (Farhangi, 2017; Dallasega *et al.*, 2018; Raut *et al.*, 2019). As a result, machines become entities that collect, analyse, and provide advice on data. This is likely to happen if the sector adopts self-optimization, self-cognition, and self-customization, where manufacturers will be able to connect with computers rather than just control machinery (Ng *et al.*, 2017; Sung, 2018; Lass *et al.*, 2020).

The manufacturing industry has played a critical part in modern society's development. Industry 4.0, the first smart factory, has access to a wide range of modern technologies, including big data analytics, artificial intelligence, advanced robotics, 3D printing, and cloud computing (Rojko, 2017; Alcácer *et al.*, 2019; Oztemel *et al.*, 2020). Production systems have become more flexible as a result of widespread use of computer numerical control (CNC) and industrial robotics (Ivanov *et al.*, 2020), while computer-aided design (CAD) and computer-aided processing planning (CAPP) have made computer integrated manufacturing possible (Abdel-Basset *et al.*, 2018). Manufacturers have been able to adopt digital changes from a variety of perspectives thanks to IoT's genuine applications such as efficient productivity, automation, customer focus, competitive advantages, and enhancing the value chain and rapid returns (Zanella *et al.*, 2014; Ghasemaghahi *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 2.3: Industry 4.0 technologies (Frank *et al.*, 2019)

IoT, cloud computing, big data & analytics, and robotics are the four key drivers of Industry 4.0. (Rao *et al.*, 2019; Raut *et al.*, 2019). Frank *et al.*, (2019) proposed a conceptual framework for explaining and simplifying various Industry 4.0 technologies (Figure 2.3). The front-end technologies of Industry 4.0, according to him, are smart manufacturing (the transformation of manufacturing activities based on novel technologies) and smart goods (the way products are delivered). As front-end technologies, the framework considers the smart supply chain (how raw materials are distributed) and smart working (new ways in which labour conducts their duties with the help of growing technologies) (Frank *et al.*, 2019). These front-end technologies are so named because they are concerned with an industry's operational processes. The front-end layer of technologies is dependent on a layer known as base technologies. For front-end technology, this layer provides connectivity and intelligence. IoT, cloud computing, big data and analytics, and robotics have all contributed to the development of the industry, therefore creating cyber-physical systems in Industry 4.0 (Sung, 2018; Kerin *et al.*, 2020).

In order to comprehend the effective use of IoT in the manufacturing industry, it is necessary to grasp the various technologies, particularly sensors, that enable manufacturing firms to operate efficiently under Industry 4.0 (Souri *et al.*, 2019; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2020). It is possible

to acquire information, analyse it, and produce an action that learns from processes by merging common things with linked devices via IoT (Kalsoom *et al.*, 2020). The basic goal of the Industry 4.0 idea is to define highly digital industrial processes in which the flow of data in an environment with relatively little human involvement to regulate communication between different devices (Castelo-Branco *et al.*, 2019; Benitez *et al.*, 2020; Lass *et al.*, 2020). Cloud-based IoT technologies connect the physical and virtual worlds, allowing businesses to manage IoT device connectivity and flexibility (Oztemel *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, IoT architecture must be adaptable enough to support a variety of wireless protocols as well as the inclusion of new sensor inputs (such as USB) (Huang *et al.*, 2012). This can also be seen in terms of physical flexibility, such as wearable devices, carry devices, battery usage, and so on (Kharlamov *et al.*, 2018). This is possible because to the usage of sensors.

People can connect and share market information thanks to I4.0 technology. By connecting people, these technologies can help strengthen the economy (Gottge *et al.*, 2019; Tortorella *et al.*, 2019). Procurement is a critical component in determining and agreeing on mutual terms for the transmission or transfer of product ownership (De Angelis *et al.*, 2018). Big data analytics (BDA), IoT, and blockchain have all been identified as significant future technologies for assisting decision-makers in optimising procurement processes by exchanging real-time data between customers and vendors (Ibem *et al.*, 2014; Rejeb *et al.*, 2018; Bag *et al.*, 2020). Sensors in products can be used to monitor them while they are in use by customers, and frequent performance monitoring and maintenance can extend their life cycle (Kalsoom *et al.*, 2020). As a result, it will open up new chances for corporations to invest in product upgrades before transferring ownership. IoT and cloud manufacturing (CM) can help with operations and logistical choices (Tu *et al.*, 2018).

2.4.1 Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS)

Vaidya *et al.*, (2018) define cyber-physical systems (CPS) as systems that integrate digital and physical space with computing, communication, and control systems (cyber space). CPSs, as described by Kruger, (2019), are revolutionary technologies for connecting and managing interconnected systems of a company's physical and digital assets. CPSs work to automate

information sharing through the use of a globally accessible information and communications network that matches production and processes (Frazzon *et al.*, 2013; Rad *et al.*, 2015; Coreynen *et al.*, 2020). CPSs are networks of IoT devices that comprise small sensors and actuators that govern, multiple, and spread artificial intelligence in industries, according to (Rauch *et al.*, 2019). These sensors and actuators are embedded in various materials and machine parts as embedded systems, which are subsequently connected via the internet (Alcácer *et al.*, 2019; Kruger, 2019). Using these sensors in CPSs-enabled machines aids in the detection of machine failure and the automatic preparation of CPS fault repair operations (Lass *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, with the use of the cycle time required for the action conducted on that station, each workstation is exploited to its maximum potential (Yen *et al.*, 2014; Bassi, 2017). A smart car, for example, is a typical CPS integrated production that combines CPS data mining for route prediction and achieves an accuracy of 80%. As a result, CPSs bring the physical and digital worlds together by collecting and exchanging data via the internet (Mourtzis *et al.*, 2016; Lu, 2018). Another example is a smart manufacturing line, which allows machines, workers, materials, and work in progress to communicate and monitor production data. This information can be passed to another networked node in which computation analysis and decision making will take place and feedback will be provided (Cisneros-Cabrera *et al.*, 2018; DeMilia *et al.*, 2018).

Decentralization, interconnection, information transparency and autonomous behaviour of the production process are the main features of CPS (Figure 2.4) (Petrasch *et al.*, 2016; Vaidya *et al.*, 2018).

- Decentralization enables the CPS to make independent decisions and complete autonomous tasks (Lehmann *et al.*, 2018; Vaidya *et al.*, 2018; Tuttokmaği *et al.*, 2019). Companies gain from decentralisation of CPSs since it simplifies planning and coordination of various operations (Shrouf *et al.*, 2014).
- Machines, devices, sensors, and people may connect and communicate with each other via IoT thanks to interconnections between diverse devices and equipment (Weking *et al.*, 2019; Lass *et al.*, 2020).

- Information transparency refers to the ability to access massive amounts of data generated by digital plant models and sensors and kept in the physical world as a virtual duplicate (Lu, 2018). As a result, transparency enables potential consumers to make advantage of open and readily available data in their decision-making processes (Mostafa *et al.*, 2019; Ivanov *et al.*, 2020).
- By intensely accumulating and visualising information gathered from sensor data, digital systems can support humans in making educated decisions and solving pressing problems on short notice (Bassi, 2017). It also permits humans to receive physical assistance in the form of unpleasant, arduous, or dangerous chores (Lass *et al.*, 2020).

Figure 2.4: Design principles of CPSs

2.4.2 Cloud Computing

Another pillar of Industry 4.0 is cloud computing, which has advanced the digitalization of manufacturing processes by enhancing data management and storage capabilities (Wan *et al.*, 2020; Yacchirema *et al.*, 2018; Tortonesi *et al.*, 2019). As a result, in terms of virtualized storage technologies that function as data centres, cloud computing has given more reliable services (Telukdarie *et al.*, 2018). These storage systems work in the background, receiving data from a variety of devices and sensors, which is then analysed and interpreted to make web-based virtualization simple for consumers to grasp (Matthyssens, 2019; Tuttokmađi *et al.*, 2019).

When corporate computing became commercially viable in the 1960s, the manufacturing

industry was one of the first to completely adopt it (Ancarani *et al.*, 2019). When used in production, cloud computing results in a high-performance, transparent synchronisation of all necessary data (Rao *et al.*, 2019), which can then be displayed based on user roles. After logging in, customer-specific needs can be readily specified from a prior order. The entire production process may thus be tracked in a single system, from planning and ordering to production and delivery (Yacchirema *et al.*, 2018; Castelo-Branco *et al.*, 2019). Cloud computing data centres are positioned all over the world in order to provide the finest service to its users (Tsiatsis *et al.*, 2019). Figure 2.5 depicts the use of cloud computing in manufacturing. Flexibility is one of the key features of cloud computing that allows users to add or remove any hardware or software in data centre according to their dynamic needs.

Figure 2.5: Data of entire supply chain in manufacturing is accessible in the cloud (Vaidya *et al.*, 2018)

2.4.3 Big Data Analytics (BDA)

Another significant enabling technology in Industry 4.0 is big data, which allows manufacturers to use data generated throughout their processes (Nino *et al.*, 2017; Kazancoglu *et al.*, 2021). Manufacturers have been using data mining techniques for a long time. Nonetheless, with the rise of IoT, cloud computing, and CPSs as global technical trends

spurring increased adoption in the manufacturing industry, the use of data generated by these technologies has received a lot of attention (Gokalp *et al.*, 2017; Nino *et al.*, 2017). Manufacturing businesses all around the world have realised the importance of maximising the potential of big data analytics (Gokalp *et al.*, 2017; DeMilia *et al.*, 2018). These companies operate many manufacturing plants that generate massive volumes of data that can be analysed to increase process efficiency, product quality, cost reduction, value addition, and production optimization services (Nino *et al.*, 2017; Zhang *et al.*, 2018).

The big data era is fuelled by an explosion of data in all fields of new data generation, such as social media, as well as new measurement capabilities (for example, IoT, smart digital devices), better data storage (cloud computing), and improved analytics computing technology (for example, machine learning, artificial intelligence) (Akter *et al.*, 2016; Wamba *et al.*, 2017; Jeon *et al.*, 2020). The journey to turn data into information that businesses can utilise to make better strategic and operational decisions (Figure 2.6) is known as Big Data (Yen *et al.*, 2014; Wamba *et al.*, 2017). According to a McKinsey analysis, data generated in bytes by the manufacturing sector is the most of any other industry during the production process (Stojanovic *et al.*, 2015; Zhang *et al.*, 2018). Manufacturers can profit from big data by reducing product development time and eliminating flaws in goods through simulation and testing before to the real manufacturing process (Wamba *et al.*, 2017; Côte-Real *et al.*, 2019; Mikalef *et al.*, 2021). Companies that have integrated sensor data into their operations analytics have seen a 5-15 percent reduction in their operating costs, according to (Chan *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, producers who employ data-driven insights to collect and analyse data from production machinery for optimum operations and factory-wide performance have shown increases in operational performance and improved manufacturing production line performance (Stojanovic *et al.*, 2015; Chiang *et al.*, 2017; Cisneros-Cabrera *et al.*, 2018; Fan *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 2.6: A simple presentation of BDA use in manufacturing

BDA is projected to have a huge influence across a wide range of businesses. Large retailing organisations, for example, are using big data capabilities to improve customer experience, reduce fraud, and provide just-in-time advice (Al-Fuqaha *et al.*, 2015; Akter *et al.*, 2016). The purpose of BDA is to reduce operational expenses and improve quality of life in the healthcare industry (Seddon *et al.*, 2017). Asset and business process monitoring (Wamba *et al.*, 2017), supply chain visibility, higher manufacturing and industrial automation (Akter *et al.*, 2016), and improved business transformation in manufacturing and operations management are all seen as benefits of BDA (Côte-Real *et al.*, 2020).

2.4.4 Robotics

The emergence of low-cost digital computers and communications networks has enabled large-scale automation and integration of manufacturing systems (Ghobakhloo, 2020), allowing for greater efficiency and flexibility in meeting production schedules while also allowing for the manufacture of high-quality products (Bi *et al.*, 2010). The desire to improve product quality, improve the safety of the manufacturing environment, and respond quickly to changing consumer needs are some of the drivers that are propelling the advancement of advanced industrial automation, which has long been connected to increased manufacturing productivity (Krueger *et al.*, 2016; Gattullo *et al.*, 2019). The requirement for additional flexibility in the production plant necessitates the development of breakthrough robotic technologies that enable producers to easily handle high volumes of product variety (Krueger *et al.*, 2016).

Robotics is an Industry 4.0 foundational technology that acts as high-level building blocks for composing tasks or executing robot programmes (Dalenogare *et al.*, 2018; Rao *et al.*, 2019).

Robotics utilise their sensory sensors to detect low-level factors using object identification and posture estimation procedures, allowing them to accomplish activities that are difficult or dangerous for human workers (Stanescu *et al.*, 2008; Wan *et al.*, 2020; Chiarini, 2021). As a result, the employment of robotics allows industrial companies to achieve improved performance in both operational and production operations (Krueger *et al.*, 2016; Nino *et al.*, 2017).

Cloud computing and big data analytics, according to Petrasch *et al.*, (2016), Gokalp *et al.*, (2017;) and Guha *et al.*, (2018), would enable real-time analysis in the industrial business. Emerging cloud databases can be made available on demand to provide real-time analytics and access to big data technology (Akter *et al.*, 2016; Feng *et al.*, 2018; Fisher *et al.*, 2018). Real-time data analytics refers to the instantaneous analysis and transmission of data from operational data stores to humans, allowing them to act on information that is only seconds old (Linthicum, 2016). A plant manager, for example, can achieve a high level of precision in monitoring equipment maintenance requirements and predicting downtime and lost production hours. This convergence of IoT, cloud, big data, and robotics has raised the standard in the manufacturing sector, lowering costs and enhancing company performance around the world (Jeon *et al.*, 2020).

2.5 Automation

Automation is the use of technologies to produce goods and services with minimal human intervention, with the main aim to reduce labour in the most tedious or repetitive tasks (Lass *et al.*, 2020). In the manufacturing context, automation is the use of machines and equipment to automate systems and production processes with enhanced efficiency as the ultimate goal (Mboli *et al.*, 2020). For instance, robotic assembly lines are the most common forms of automation used by manufacturing plants, where human input is only needed when defining the processes while assembling of various parts is left to the machines. This leads manufacturers to experience benefits such as reduced downtime, provide predictive maintenance and improve decision making.

Large volumes of production are characterised by fixed automation, in which machines are set with a particular task and the sequence and speed of these tasks are fixed by the production line or equipment (Agostini *et al.*, 2021). A very common example of fixed automation is the automotive panels. Automotive suppliers produce huge amounts of parts before changing designs and processes such as stamping or casting are done by fixed automation. A hobbing machine dedicated to produce only one gear is another example of fixed automation. Programmable automation is used for producing low volumes of products that have short life cycles and is often associated with batch production (Alcácer *et al.*, 2019). However, downtime is needed to conduct changes in the production line. Flexible automation allows manufacturers to perform changeovers automatically. This type of automation is characterised by real-time or on-demand production. A hobbing machine that automatically produces various gears without the need to shut down or manual changeovers is an example of flexible automation.

Lead times, estimates and timelines can be easily handled and understood by having real-time data available to the manufacturers (Brozzi *et al.*, 2020). In addition, automated equipment can help to improve repeatability with the ultimate improvement in quality and reduction in variability of the products (Mastos *et al.*, 2020). Nevertheless, automation offers a predictable business model that can help in intelligent decision making as well as provide transparency to all stakeholders. The future of automation is associated with robotics, IoT and other digital technologies, which are implemented in a smart factory.

2.6 Smart Factories

Although automation has always been an important aspect of a factory, enterprising manufacturers have taken it to a whole new level by incorporating IoT and artificial intelligence into manufacturing operations (Wu *et al.*, 2013; Alcácer *et al.*, 2019; Mastos *et al.*, 2020). Physical machinery and business processes have coupled with automation to give rise to complex optimization decisions that people used to make due to the increasing complexity of cyber physical systems (Ning *et al.*, 2011; Brozzi *et al.*, 2020; Lass *et al.*, 2020). As a result, manufacturers have been able to link floor decisions and perceptions with the supply chain

(Mboli *et al.*, 2020), resulting in the creation of what we now refer to as a smart factory. As a result of adopting a smart manufacturing system, a number of business prospects in the form of efficiency, productivity, individualism on demand, and novel business models are produced (Sanders *et al.*, 2016; Oztemel *et al.*, 2020; Agostini *et al.*, 2021). The business opportunities created by smart factories are summarised in Figure 2.7.

The first industrial revolution began with the introduction of mechanical manufacturing equipment, which was followed by mass production of commodities (Shrouf *et al.*, 2014; Khanna *et al.*, 2019). The digital revolution was defined as the adoption of enhanced automation and control of production processes through the use of electronics and information technology (Wilkesmann *et al.*, 2018). The use of IoT in various operations has resulted in a shift from a centralised to a decentralised production structure (Oztemel *et al.*, 2020; Shi, Xie, *et al.*, 2020). Machines and industries may now self-optimize and reconfigure their behaviour in response to changes in orders and operational conditions thanks to this technology (Dalenogare *et al.*, 2018; Frank *et al.*, 2019). The technology that enables data collecting is at the heart of smart factories. This technology includes sophisticated sensors, motors, and robotics that are used on manufacturing production and assembly lines (Oztemel *et al.*, 2020).

Four intelligent features distinguish a smart factory (Kalsoom *et al.*, 2020):

- **Sensors:** These are devices that can self-organize, learn, and store environmental data in order to study actions and skills (Celestine *et al.*, 2020). As a result, sensors are able to make decisions that allow them to adapt to changes in the environment.
- **Interoperability:** By connecting different devices, coordination can be improved, allowing for more flexibility in the production system's setup protocols (Leng *et al.*, 2020).
- **Integration:** Smart factories can have a high level of process integration thanks to robots and artificial intelligence (AI). AI, in combination with the integration of human intellectual capacities, allows factories to conduct analysis and make decisions (Rojko, 2017).

- Virtual reality (VR) techniques: One of the high-level components of smart factories, VR virtualizes industrial processes employing computers, signal processing, animation technology, intelligent reasoning, prediction, simulation, and multimedia technologies to enhance human–machine interaction (Shi and Xie, 2020).

Figure 2.7: Business opportunities of smart factories (Alcácer *et al.*, 2019)

2.6.1 Smart Factory vs Traditional Factory

The smart factory represents a shift from traditional automation to a connected and flexible system that generates a continuous data stream via highly networked operations and production systems that can learn and adapt to changing demands (Farhangi, 2017; Gattullo *et al.*, 2019; Punithavathi *et al.*, 2019). Manufacturing, maintenance, inventory monitoring, digitization of operations, and other activities in manufacturing systems can all be driven by data from physical, operational, and human assets in these factories (Birkel *et al.*, 2020; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2021). Smart factories' major goal is to use intelligent production systems and appropriate engineering methodologies to achieve a successful and integrated implementation of production facilities (Kimani *et al.*, 2019). Smart factory endorsement can help to change the

intercommunication of designed systems in the same way that the internet has revolutionised the way humans connect with one another (Lass *et al.*, 2020). Wilkesmann *et al.*, (2018) separated smart factories into three components: using online information to execute with high efficiency, agility, and flexibility; and using multiple levels of understanding to deliver factory transparency. These components are explained below:

2.6.1.1 Components

Machines use real-time data and information from various components, such as sensors, to achieve self-awareness and self-comparison (Sattar *et al.*, 2019). This self-awareness enables the machines to assess their own performance and identify any malfunctioning components (Brozzi *et al.*, 2020; Lass *et al.*, 2020). As a result, the system can identify risks connected with the final product and prevent any faults (Haddud *et al.*, 2017).

2.6.1.2 Smart Machines

Smart machines can share information about their performance and efficiency with other devices over the internet (Morimoto, 2013; Herceg *et al.*, 2020). This machine self-assessment enables it to adjust its settings and efficiency in response to the knowledge gained through information exchange. The production system now has the capability of customising performance criteria for particular machines based on self-comparison (Shrouf *et al.*, 2014).

2.6.1.3 Production System

As a result, the production system's settings can be changed to alter the state of all the machines involved in the creation of each individual product (Alaslani *et al.*, 2019; Naeem *et al.*, 2021). This ensures high-quality output at the lowest possible cost.

Several themes emerge in any smart factory transformation: those linked to culture and change management, as well as the idea that transformation is only as successful as the people who embrace it (Alcácer *et al.*, 2019; Rao *et al.*, 2019; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2021) (Figure 2.8a). Others are significantly more specialised and unique to the smart factory and its technologies, and

these might be crucial concerns for executives to address (Oztemel *et al.*, 2020) (Figure 2.8b). But, informed by the wisdom of experience and the influence it may have, all of these lessons can be combined to create a vision for a successful smart factory future (Ivanov *et al.*, 2020; Ramirez-Peña *et al.*, 2020).

The manufacturer can meet client requirements in such an integrated smart factory environment by adjusting production parameters and other machine settings at the last minute. In traditional factories, this capability does not exist (Zhong *et al.*, 2015; Chen *et al.*, 2019). The essential hallmark of a smart factory is its ability to readjust and evolve in response to the organization's changing needs (Agrifoglio *et al.*, 2017; Ivanov *et al.*, 2020). Changing client demands, the creation of new markets, the development of new products and services, improved operational productivity, and the use of modern technologies in maintenance procedures are all examples of these requirements (Lightfoot *et al.*, 2014; Shrouf *et al.*, 2014; Tanyingyong *et al.*, 2016). Smart factories become more reactive and predictive as a result of their ability to adjust and learn from real-time data, avoiding operational downtime and other potential process problems (Alcácer *et al.*, 2019; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2021). In the production phase, sensors in the form of WSNs enable smart factories to monitor specific operations across the plant, increasing knowledge of what is going on various levels (Tortonesi *et al.*, 2019; Kazancoglu *et al.*, 2021). Vibration sensors, for example, can alert you when motors, bearings, or other equipment need to be serviced (Kalsoom *et al.*, 2020). These warnings serve as reminders for factory preventive maintenance. Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and WiMAX in smart factories can provide a mobile platform that provides high-speed and low-cost connectivity anywhere and at any time (Shrouf *et al.*, 2014; Farhangi, 2017; Khaleel *et al.*, 2017; Lass *et al.*, 2020).

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.8: Themes from smart factory initiatives (a) familiar themes; (b) smart factory specific themes

(Petrasch *et al.*, 2016)

Several RFID applications, in addition to sensors, have been successfully used in smart factories. This technology is critical for improving a variety of industrial automation activities, including inbound-outbound management and the automatic identification of goods,

instruments, and other manufacturing tools (Khanna *et al.*, 2019; Birkel *et al.*, 2020). The initial goal of developing this technology was to track and identify items in retail and logistics (Pero *et al.*, 2014; Hofmann *et al.*, 2017; Majeed *et al.*, 2017); however, it is now being used in manufacturing applications such as supply chain, logistics, and other commercially available systems (Kaur and Kaur, 2017; Mehami *et al.*, 2018; Choy *et al.*, 2020). Cloud computing, in addition to RFID, is another key technology used in smart factories. On-demand self-service capabilities in cloud computing have been demonstrated to be critical for businesses in terms of cost reduction, system flexibility, profit growth, and competitiveness (Gattullo *et al.*, 2019; Oztemel *et al.*, 2020). As a result, cloud computing provides a flexible option for data applications in terms of storage space and computational power that can be scaled up and down as needed (Delen *et al.*, 2009; Abdel-Basset *et al.*, 2018; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2020). The massive volume of data generated during operations can be carried to the cloud via cyberspace, where it can be transmitted to the processes (Yen *et al.*, 2014). As a result, big data analytics may help with system administration and optimization, as well as supervision and control (Akter *et al.*, 2016). For example, a leading electronics business that manufactures air conditioners built a smart factory with completely automated production, three-dimensional scanners, IoT technology, and integrated machine control. Not only did the company profit in terms of shorter lead times for customers and lower total costs as a result of this deployment, but it also saw a 25% increase in production capacity and a 50% reduction in faulty products (Sanders *et al.*, 2016, 2019; Boyes *et al.*, 2018; Tsiatsis *et al.*, 2018). Figure 2.9 highlights the differences between a traditional factory vs smart factory system.

2.6.2 Features of Smart Factory

A smart factory is built around a few essential aspects that contribute to a more productive system, less downtime, and the ability to predict and adapt to changes in a larger network (Rao *et al.*, 2019). These capabilities give producers more visibility into their assets and help them overcome the obstacles that manufacturing systems present (Brandon-Jones *et al.*, 2014). As a result, increased productivity, efficiency, and responsiveness to changes in supplier and customer demands are all simply achievable. The key features are explained below.

Figure 2.9: Smart factory vs Traditional factory

2.6.2.1 Connectivity

The most important source of value in a smart factory is its interconnectedness. Assets that are interconnected with WSNs regularly take data sets from sources in a linked smart factory, guaranteeing that the data reflects actual conditions (Kalsoom *et al.*, 2021). As a result of incorporating data from business systems, a comprehensive overall perspective of supply chain activities is gained, driving overall supply network efficiency (Lee *et al.*, 2020; Cañas *et al.*, 2021).

2.6.2.2 Optimization

An efficient smart factory achieves reduced manual intervention and increased reliability. The smart factory can improve production, uptime, and quality while lowering costs and wastage thanks to automated workflows, improved tracking, and efficient energy management (Dieter Tebje Kelly *et al.*, 2013; Wilkesmann *et al.*, 2018).

2.6.2.3 Proactive

Continuously running machines and tools until they fail is the best way to get the most out of them (Chong *et al.*, 2018; Massaro *et al.*, 2020). Overheating, vibration, and tool breakage, on the other hand, can cause catastrophic damage to machinery. This might result in unanticipated downtime, which can be costly and time-consuming to rectify (Haddud *et al.*, 2017). A

proactive system detects abnormalities, assists in inventory replenishment, detects and addresses quality issues, and monitors safety and maintenance concerns (Tse *et al.*, 2016; Jeon *et al.*, 2020). As a result, people and systems can anticipate and respond to problems before they exist, rather of reacting to them after they occur. Smart factories can boost uptime, output, and quality while avoiding security risks thanks to their proactive capabilities (Alcácer *et al.*, 2019; Oztemel *et al.*, 2020).

2.6.2.4 Transparency

A transparent network offers for better visibility across the entire facility and ensures that enterprises can make better and more accurate decisions. Role-based views, real-time alerts and notifications, and real-time tracking and monitoring are some of the technologies that can help with this (Shrouf *et al.*, 2014; Walid *et al.*, 2015).

2.6.2.5 Agility and Flexibility

A smart factory's agility and adaptability allow it to adjust to changes in schedule and product adjustments with as little human interaction as possible (Gunasekaran *et al.*, 2017). Advanced smart factories also have self-configure and self-awareness capabilities, where the system can recognise and modify equipment and work flow in real time and see the impact of those changes (Boyes *et al.*, 2018; Wilkesmann *et al.*, 2018; Brozzi *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, agility can improve uptime and yield by decreasing product changeovers and thereby enhancing accuracy (Yen *et al.*, 2014).

Historically, technologies were rapidly integrated with physical components; now, IoT and machine-to-machine (M2M), at an alarming rate and accuracy, are fast merging data and system flows which are the underpinnings of the global economy (Al-Fuqaha *et al.*, 2015; Giri *et al.*, 2017; Tuttokmađi *et al.*, 2019). Fixed broadband technologies are limited to household installations in the developed world, whereas a mobile broadband platform connects billions of new devices around the world, bringing electronic devices to nearly 4 billion end users (Tsiatsis *et al.*, 2018). Cloud computing, fog computing, and other similar concepts can enable

low-cost access to processing capacity for these billions of end-users via the global economy (Lass *et al.*, 2020; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2021). As a result of the combination of IoT and cloud computing technologies, a new sort of value chain is forming, one that is driven by the creation of information rather than physical objects (Ghobakhloo, 2020).

These types of value chains are described by their flexible, agile and responsive connectivity functionalities; which make the use of IoT devices easy for the end-users, thus improving firm performance of the companies (Andreev, 2014; Galinina *et al.*, 2017; A. Pradhan *et al.*, 2018; Mekki *et al.*, 2019). There are a variety of smart factory key technologies used these days, these are explained following.

2.6.2.6 Smart Sensors

Among other recent advances in technology, smart sensors have been in the spotlight in terms of their potential significance and wide range of application areas (Kalsoom *et al.*, 2021). With the integration of computing and IoT in industrial processes, ordinary sensors have been transformed into smart sensors providing them with abilities to carry out complex calculations with collected data (Landaluce *et al.*, 2020). Apart from increased capabilities, smart sensors have also become remarkably small and exceedingly flexible, turning bulky machines into high-tech intel. Equipped with signal conditioning, embedded algorithms, and digital interfaces, smart sensors have become devices with detection and self-awareness capabilities (Dahlin, 2012; Choy *et al.*, 2020). These sensors are built as IoT components that convert real-time information into digital data that can be transmitted to a gateway (Herrojo *et al.*, 2019; Sattar *et al.*, 2019). These abilities allow smart sensors to predict and monitor real time scenarios and take corrective actions in an instant. Complex multi-layered operations such as collecting raw data, adjusting sensitivity, and filtering, motion detection, analysis, and communication are the main functions of intelligent sensors (Mulloni *et al.*, 2020). For instance, wireless sensor networks (WSNs) are one of the applications of smart sensors, whose nodes are connected with one or more other sensors and sensor hubs, making a communication technology of some kind. In addition, information from multiple sensors can be combined to deduce conclusions about an existing problem; for instance, temperature and pressure sensor

data can be used to infer the onset of a mechanical failure. Figure 2.10 shows the building blocks of a typical smart sensor (Le *et al.*, 2019), while Figure 2.11 summarizes the key features of smart sensors (Dahlin, 2012; Kadechkar *et al.*, 2020).

Figure 2.10 Smart sensor building blocks

Figure 2.11 Features of a smart sensor

Calibration Capability

The ability of a sensor to determine its normal function is termed calibration capability (Jeon *et al.*, 2020). Self-calibration is simple in many cases, and different calibration techniques are available for different types of sensors:

- Sensors with an electric output carry out calibration by using a known reference of voltage level.
- Sensors such as load cells used for weighing systems can adjust their output to zero when no force is being applied (Gattullo *et al.*, 2019).
- Other sensors can use look-up tables for calibration. However, to carry out calibration using look-up tables, a huge amount of memory capacity must be available to store correction points due to the large volume of data gathered during the process. On the contrary, an interpolation method is preferable in which a small matrix of correction points is required (Tanyingyong *et al.*, 2016).

Self-Diagnosis of Faults

Smart sensors carry out self-diagnosis by observing internal signals for evidence of faults. Differentiating between normal measurement deviations and sensor faults can be a challenge for some sensors (Dahlin, 2012; Chae *et al.*, 2021). This challenge is overcome by storing multiple measured values around a set-up point and calculating minimum and maximum values for the measured quantity (Kadechkar *et al.*, 2020). In order to measure the impact of sensor fault on the measured quantity, uncertainty techniques are used. This enables the continuation of using a sensor after the fault has arisen.

2.6.2.7 WSNs

The true hallmark of an Industry 4.0 smart factory is its ability to readjust and evolve in response to the organization's changing needs (Tortonesi *et al.*, 2019; Landaluce *et al.*, 2020). Changing client demands, the creation of new markets, the development of new products and services, improved operational productivity, and the use of modern technologies in maintenance processes are all examples of these requirements (Landaluce *et al.*, 2020). The capacity to adjust and learn from real-time data makes smart factories more receptive and predictive, reducing downtime and other potential process issues (Lee *et al.*, 2020; Nagy *et al.*, 2018; Jagtap *et al.*, 2019). The sensors in the manufacturing phase, in the form of WSNs, allow smart factories to monitor specific operations throughout the factory, enhancing awareness at many levels (Wasson *et al.*, 2018). Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and WiMAX in smart factories can

provide a mobile platform that provides high-speed and low-cost connectivity anywhere and at any time (Bi *et al.*, 2016; Landaluce *et al.*, 2020).

2.6.2.8 RFID

Several RFID applications, in addition to sensors, have been successfully used in smart factories. It is capable of disclosing product information at a low level in an autonomous, immediate, and touchless manner (Pero *et al.*, 2014). RFID tags, unlike barcodes, do not require a direct line of sight to transfer data, making it possible to scan multiple tags in a batch at the same time (Tu, 2018). This technology is critical for improving a variety of industrial automation procedures, including inbound-outbound management and automatic identification of products, instruments, and other manufacturing tools (Reyes *et al.*, 2016). This technology was created with the intention of tracking and identifying things in retail and logistics (Reyes *et al.*, 2016), but it is now being used in manufacturing applications such as supply chain, logistics, and other commercially available systems (Frederico *et al.*, 2019; Nascimento *et al.*, 2019). RFID can improve information visibility at various phases of a corporate supply chain, including raw material acquisition, production, shipping, and retail (Delen *et al.*, 2009; Zhou, 2009). One of the most likely RFID benefits is reduced uncertainty as a result of information visibility and openness.

The RFID tags are categorised into two types:

- **Passive Tags:** Energy from the radio waves originating from the interrogator is used in this type of tags to convey the stored information back to the interrogator (Alwadi *et al.*, 2017).
- **Battery-Powered Tags:** The information in this type of tags is relayed by the power of a small battery (Ellis *et al.*, 2018; Mulloni *et al.*, 2020).

RFID technology has increasingly made its way into the manufacturing process, starting with the supply chain. As a result, many researchers are interested in the proper design and implementation of RFID-based systems (Ellis *et al.*, 2018; Mehami *et al.*, 2018; Herrojo *et al.*, 2019). However, only a few real-world applications, such as RFID-based production process

monitoring and analysis, can be investigated (Mehami *et al.*, 2018; Landaluce *et al.*, 2020; Mulloni *et al.*, 2020; Sen *et al.*, 2020). RFID technology is useful in the scoring model driven system for automatically tracking and tracing all things, including materials, WIP, the location of fixed and mobile resources, and so on (Abdel-Basset *et al.*, 2018; Birkel *et al.*, 2020). The tracking of production processes allows for considerably more efficient and automated resource management and performance measurement. RFID devices are used in the shops, on conveyors, in batches, on pallets, and so on, and the data is turned into meta-data. Meta-data can also be turned into performance metrics, which are used to monitor how well an operational process is working (Pero *et al.*, 2014; Pfahl *et al.*, 2014).

2.6.2.9 M2M

Historically, technologies were fast merged with physical components; now, IoT and machine-to-machine (M2M) are rapidly merging data and system flows that form the foundations of the global economy at an alarming rate and accuracy (Tuttokmaği *et al.*, 2019). Fixed broadband technologies are limited to household installations in the developed world, but a mobile broadband platform connects billions of new devices around the world, bringing electronic gadgets to over 4 billion end users (Al-Fuqaha *et al.*, 2015; Giri *et al.*, 2017). The primary technologies employed in a smart factory system and their impact on the manufacturing industry are summarised in Table 2.2.

2.7 Importance of IoT in Manufacturing Industry

New market demands and rising IoT technologies have shifted the manufacturing industries' surroundings toward smart factories (Shrouf *et al.*, 2014). The manufacturing industry has played a critical part in the development of modern society. With the rapid advancement of information and management technology in recent years, the social environment for manufacturing has changed dramatically (Ben-Daya *et al.*, 2019; Shi and Xie, 2020). For example, industries have been attempting to bring greater agility, network, service-oriented, and social manufacturing traits to the fore because of the diversity of customer expectations

and the expanding worldwide market competitiveness (Bag *et al.*, 2020; Lass *et al.*, 2020). Manufacturing is an important aspect of any economy, hence advancements in manufacturing technology are strongly linked to IoT (Telukdarie *et al.*, 2018). For a variety of reasons, this industry is at the forefront of IoT adoption. Industry 4.0, the first smart factory, has access to a wide range of modern technologies, including big data analytics, artificial intelligence, advanced robotics, 3D printing, and cloud computing (Burke *et al.*, 2014; Kerin *et al.*, 2020). Manufacturing systems have become more flexible thanks to the widespread use of CNC and industrial robots (Tao *et al.*, 2018; Wilkesmann *et al.*, 2018); whereas the CAD and CAPP has made computer integrated manufacturing practical (Shrouf *et al.*, 2014; Kaur *et al.*, 2017). Manufacturers have been able to adopt digital transformations for a variety of reasons, including increased productivity, automation, customer focus, competitive advantages, value chain enhancement, and quick returns (Holmström *et al.*, 2016; Shi *et al.*, 2020; Jain *et al.*, 2021). WSAWs (wireless sensor and actuator networks) are becoming increasingly common in industrial processes. Because of its ability to provide flexible monitoring and management of production operations, this is the case (Haddud *et al.*, 2017; Khaleel *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, by executing self-awareness and self-configuration, these networks can operate in contexts that allow them to conduct more sophisticated operations (Shrouf *et al.*, 2014; Khaleel *et al.*, 2017). With IoT, the factories have the ability to communicate information which involves production processes, maintenance schedules, surrounding environments and much more.

Table 2.2: Key technologies of a smart factory and their impact on industry (Kalsoom *et al.*, 2020)

Key IoT Technologies	IoT Impact on Manufacturing Industry	Sources
Cyber-physical systems	Evaluate real-time information sharing. Self-monitor and govern the processes. Foresee actions or need of users. Self-organizing production.	Nagorny <i>et al.</i> (2018); Manavalan <i>et al.</i> (2019); Wagire <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Big Data	Using historical data to provide proactive risk alerts. Reduce issues related to product quality and failure. Flexible in combining data from different sources for business intelligence.	Frank <i>et al.</i> (2019); Cimini <i>et al.</i> (2020); Kozjek <i>et al.</i> (2020)

Key IoT Technologies	IoT Impact on Manufacturing Industry	Sources
Augment Reality	Management of emergency situations. Enhancing maintenance activities by providing remote assistance and guidance. Providing new ways of design and manufacturing process integration.	Lu (2017); Frank <i>et al.</i> (2019); Wagire <i>et al.</i> (2020)
RFID	Inventory shrinkage. Saving processing, scanning and recording times. Accurate and timely delivery. Inventory accuracy and shelf replenishment.	Fatorachian <i>et al.</i> (2018); Galati <i>et al.</i> (2019)
M2M	Progressive benefits to shipper, receiver and customer. Real-time visibility. Quality controlled logistics.	Holmström <i>et al.</i> (2017); Zanella <i>et al.</i> (2017)
Sensor Technologies	Autonomous decision making. Visibility, theft reduction. Reduce repair cost and maintenance downtime through better monitoring. Safety and security.	Fatorachian <i>et al.</i> (2018); Frank <i>et al.</i> (2019); Galati <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Cloud Technologies	Quality control. Real-time visibility. Enhanced security measures. Adjusting to market volatility by making SCs wary of how resources should be used in the event of a collapse. Increased scalability abilities.	Manavalan <i>et al.</i> (2019); Lass <i>et al.</i> (2020); Wagire <i>et al.</i> (2020)

The ability to use low-power networked embedded devices for monitoring and control operations has risen with the rapid growth in micro embedded systems and the increasing importance of pervasive computing in next-generation industrial ecosystems (Esposito De Falco *et al.*, 2017; Guo *et al.*, 2019; Lass *et al.*, 2020). These systems benefit from modern electronics and wireless data connection networks (Esmacilian *et al.*, 2016; Boyes *et al.*, 2018). Manufacturing systems' complexity provides for a wide range of IoT applications in these processes. The following are the primary sectors with complicated IoT applications:

2.7.1 Manufacturing Operations

Several elements are included in manufacturing operations such as asset management, intelligent manufacturing, performance optimization and monitoring, planning, human-machine interaction and end-to-end transparency in operations (Brauer *et al.*, 2005; Lee *et al.*, 2020; Hofmann *et al.*, 2017).

2.7.2 Production Asset Management and Maintenance

Asset management, often known as asset monitoring, is the process of keeping track of a company's physical assets and data (Morimoto, 2013; Wan *et al.*, 2020). Production asset management and maintenance in manufacturing industries includes elements such as production asset monitoring and tracking, from asset location to monitoring of parameters such as quality, performance, and potential damage or breakdowns (Büyükoçkan *et al.*, 2018; Gottge *et al.*, 2019; Maisiri *et al.*, 2021). In addition, IoT provides a centralised command centre that enables detailed and comprehensive view of all floating products around the world. For instance, for a multinational firm with consumer goods and products spread across the world, tracking or tracing a single package or consignments can become enormously challenging. IoT simplifies this challenge by providing a single platform (Brozzi *et al.*, 2020; Maisiri *et al.*, 2021).

2.7.3 Supply Chain

Tracking numbers and bar codes are a standard way for maintaining goods across the supply chain in traditional supply chains. IoT, on the other hand, has enabled supply chains to replace conventional approaches by building RFID and GPS sensors that track things from floor to store (Ivanov *et al.*, 2020). Manufacturers can employ these sensors at any point in the supply chain to collect data that can help them improve quality control and product forecasting (Garcia-Muiña *et al.*, 2018; Sharma *et al.*, 2020). IoT enables manufacturers to utilise smart sensors on their production processes to manage planned and predictive maintenance as supply

chains continue to grow and prevent down-time that can cost too much (Ivanov *et al.*, 2020; Büyüközkan *et al.*, 2018).

2.8 IoT and Firm Performance

Organizations and industries have been able to quickly translate their strengths into a competitive advantage thanks to advancements in IoT (Tang *et al.*, 2019). Organizational borders have been more progressive in recent years as a result of rising technology, rapid increases in innovation, and worldwide rivalry (Oliveira *et al.*, 2018; Côte-Real *et al.*, 2019). Product innovations are viewed as major drivers of improved business performance (Holmström *et al.*, 2016; Ricci *et al.*, 2021). In recent years, the problem of improving business performance by incorporating IoT technology has gotten a lot of attention (Dalenogare *et al.*, 2018). Many businesses are adopting IoT measures to cope with the rapid changes in today's competitive market (Rao *et al.*, 2019).

As a result of recent academic interest in the implications of IoT, there has been an increase in the corpus of literature in this area. Since the 1980s, researchers and academics have been interested in the potential of IoT to offer businesses with a competitive advantage (Lee *et al.*, 2020; Wamba *et al.*, 2017; Rao *et al.*, 2019; Al-Surmi *et al.*, 2020). The technological value of IoT and its impact on business performance are the focus of primary study in this area. Researchers have focused on the effects of company performance, overlooking the important intermediate dynamic capacities of firms (Queiroz *et al.*, 2018) that operate as a mediator between IoT and firm performance (Castelo-Branco *et al.*, 2019). According to recent research, innovation plays a critical role in manufacturing industry performance (Dallasega *et al.*, 2018), and IoT has a favourable impact on a firm's competitive advantage (Mikalef *et al.*, 2017; Akhtar *et al.*, 2018; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2021). According to academics, manufacturing technological efficiency is greatly dependent on the capacity to generate innovative products (Wu *et al.*, 2014; Oliveira, 2017; Zhang *et al.*, 2018; Shi and Xie, 2020).

Performance measurement is the most basic activity for assessing a company's competitiveness (Rojko, 2017; Wamba *et al.*, 2017; Tortorella *et al.*, 2019). Organizations strive for exceptional

performance in order to compete in global markets and assessing suitable performance is critical to a business's success (Lin *et al.*, 2018; Müller, 2019; Alhawari *et al.*, 2021). As a result, performance measurement has got a lot of attention because it has a big impact on performance. Scholars feel that in order for manufacturers to fulfil the present configuration of changing and fluctuating market demand, IoT devices must be agile in order to respond quickly (Sanders *et al.*, 2016, 2019; Fadhilah *et al.*, 2019; Kumar *et al.*, 2021). Scholars define agility as the integration of technology, human resources, and organisation into a production model that creates a data and communication infrastructure, allowing firms to operate with greater speed, quality, and efficiency (Abdel-Basset *et al.*, 2018; Akhtar *et al.*, 2018; Nagy *et al.*, 2018; Fosso Wamba *et al.*, 2019; Dewangan *et al.*, 2020). As a result, it provides higher-quality products at lower prices, as well as improved service and delivery circumstances (Wilkesmann *et al.*, 2018; Lass *et al.*, 2020). Manufacturing enterprises that compete in highly uncertain and dynamic markets see IoT device adaptability as a crucial competitive weapon in addition to agility (Coreynen *et al.*, 2020). This means that manufacturing systems should not only be viewed as systems that generate high-quality products at low prices, but also as systems that can respond quickly to market and consumer demands (Sambamurthy *et al.*, 2003; Patel *et al.*, 2016; De Mendonca *et al.*, 2018; Mukherjee *et al.*, 2018). The agility, flexibility, and connection of IoT devices in manufacturing operations help enterprises gain a competitive advantage, resulting in operational efficiency and improved market and financial performance (Castelo-Branco *et al.*, 2019). The majority of research has focused on operational agility and its impact on company performance (Akhtar *et al.*, 2018; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2020; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2021; Mikalef *et al.*, 2021). In this regard, the agility, connection, and adaptability parameters of IoT devices have just recently been studied in the context of improving business performance (Sharma *et al.*, 2017; Fatorachian *et al.*, 2018; Lass *et al.*, 2020; Belhadi *et al.*, 2021). Several sorts of IoT capabilities have been highlighted by various scholars in terms of improving firm performance and establishing competitive advantage, including IoT infrastructure, making technology work, IoT business process integration, and IoT management (Wu *et al.*, 2014; Weking *et al.*, 2019; Ejsmont *et al.*, 2020; Kerin *et al.*, 2020; Ramirez-Peña *et al.*, 2020). These categories, however, are insufficient to describe IoT usage trends and their relationship to real-time information visibility, DDIPCs, and firm performance.

Some researchers have looked into the relationship between IoT capabilities and firm performance as a more in-depth topic (Wamba *et al.*, 2017; Dev *et al.*, 2020; Ejsmont *et al.*, 2020). Lyu *et al.*, (2009) conducted a quantitative empirical study on SMEs in Taiwan to investigate the relationship between IoT, innovation, and company performance in the manufacturing industry. The findings, which were based on 168 questionnaire responses and structural equation modelling, revealed that innovation is mediating the effect of IoT on corporate performance. The findings of IoT management practises conducted by collecting data from 129 organisations in the United States by Esmaeilian *et al.*, (2016) reveal that, aside from tangible assets such as IoT managerial skills and expertise, the quality of the technology foundation was crucial to boost firm performance. Tang *et al.*, (2018) did another study to empirically analyse the link between IoT capabilities and corporate performance. When comparing the results of questionnaires done on IoT leaders from 56 companies, it was discovered that companies that embraced strong IoT capabilities performed better in terms of profitability and cost-based performance than a control group of companies. Scholars identified a gap and began to argue that in order to measure the impact of high IoT investments on firm performance, it is necessary to develop theoretical multi-dimensional IoT capabilities within the firms (Sher *et al.*, 2004; Akter *et al.*, 2016; Torres *et al.*, 2018; Afzal *et al.*, 2019; Aydiner *et al.*, 2019), so some researchers began to investigate the influencing mechanism of IoT. Fan *et al.*, (2018) discovered that organisational learning played a significant role as a mediator to intervene the impact of IoT capabilities on firm performance using structural equation modelling (SEM) with data obtained from managers in 271 manufacturing enterprises. As a result, the influence of IoT on a firm's capabilities and strategic processes can be used to determine the potential of IoT investments and their worth in terms of improving firm performance. Torres *et al.*, (2018) proposed a model that included inter-relationships between IoT resources, IoT capabilities, and business performance. They tested the model using data from 129 companies in the United States. The research revealed that the level of support and enhancement in a firm's core capabilities offered by IoT can explain differences in performance.

Wang *et al.*, (2019) investigated the relationship between dynamic organisational capacities and company performance using 877 samples of high-tech new ventures in China. The findings revealed that dynamic capabilities were positively related to firm performance, with operational performance being the most closely linked. Tse *et al.*, (2016) did a study to see if high-tech manufacturing enterprises in China benefit from service innovation. They gathered data from 187 high-tech firms and discovered a positive relationship between service innovation and company performance using firm size, firm age, and product innovation as control variables.

Dynamic capacities, according to researchers, can influence company performance through a variety of techniques and procedures (Bharadwaj *et al.*, 2016; Torres *et al.*, 2018; Chaniias *et al.*, 2019). However, empirical research on the linkages between dynamic capacities and operational success is limited, according to Tse *et al.*, (2016) and Mu, (2017). To close this gap, Mu, (2017) created a model that highlighted the impact of dynamic capabilities, as well as marketing and operational capabilities, on new product development performance and firm success in general. The link between marketing competency, operability, and firm performance was discovered using survey data from high-tech Chinese enterprises.

It was discovered that there has been relatively little research on the influence of IoT implementation on corporate financial performance. To bridge this gap, Tang *et al.*, (2018) did a study in which they analysed the performance of enterprises after they adopted IoT by understanding the opinions of managers or shareholders. The study looked at financial performance metrics, productivity, and company market value to see if such methods had a favourable impact on financial performance. After gathering secondary data from Fortune 500 organisations, it was discovered that IoT adoption had an impact on the firms' financial performance and market value. Fadhilah *et al.*, (2019) investigated the effects of third-party logistics' IoT capabilities on their logistic performance and financial performance. IoT capabilities can influence corporate processes and have an impact on business performance, according to a survey of Fortune 500 organisations. As a result, it was discovered that if the efficiency and efficacy of logistics activities are increased using IoT, logistics costs can be minimised while enterprises' financial performance improves significantly. A recent study

carried out by Calış Duman *et al.*, (2021) to investigate the scope of Turkey to digitise their manufacturing industry broadly concluded that technology enhances organisational performance criteria such as sales, production speed, production amount, profitability and product quality. It was also revealed that technology inclusion in production ultimately leads to reduction in production costs.

The interdependence of financial and operational flows, on the other hand, is rarely acknowledged, and decisions are frequently made based on other criteria (Garcia-Muiña *et al.*, 2018; Nagy *et al.*, 2018; Negri *et al.*, 2021). Operations managers make operational decisions about inventories, service levels, and capacity requirements in order to generate financial performance in terms of profit, working capital, and return on investment (Galinina *et al.*, 2017; Mikalef *et al.*, 2017; Sharma *et al.*, 2020). At the same time, financial managers make partially arbitrary decisions about targeted financial performance ranges (Chang *et al.*, 2016; Prajogo *et al.*, 2016; Atif *et al.*, 2021), resulting in operational performance constraints. Current methods do not explicitly address the trade-off between operational and financial decisions, as organisations are not always able to forecast the effect of a decision from both an operational and financial standpoint (Sithole *et al.*, 2016; Farhangi, 2017; Dekkers *et al.*, 2019; Fadhilah *et al.*, 2019). Efforts to enhance working capital position, for example, may have unintended consequences: focusing a reduction in accounts payables may lead to increased supplier pricing and, as a result, excess working capital requirements (Bassi, 2017). Furthermore, while most businesses will be able to reduce their overall days of working capital requirements, only a few will be able to improve their receivables and inventory performance (Protopappa-Sieke *et al.*, 2010; Guo *et al.*, 2019).

In the literature, there is both qualitative and quantitative research that involves financial aspects in supply chain management. Xie *et al.*, (2020) looked at the link between operational success, financial performance, and supply chain management methods in 8 consultancy studies and 17 research papers. His survey's findings emphasise the significance of innovative manufacturing business models. Interrelationships between various operational indicators such as service level and inventory decisions have been a major emphasis (Atif *et al.*, 2021). From a qualitative standpoint, there are several frameworks that interrelate operational and financial

performance data. Birkel *et al.*, (2020) conduct a thorough analysis of the literature on balanced scorecard frameworks in supply chain management. The authors create a supply chain management balanced scorecard template that incorporates four major perspectives: financial, customer, internal business process, and learning and growth. However, deciding how to prioritise the many viewpoints remains an issue.

The examination of the relationship between IoT capabilities and firm performance is clearly a hot topic, as seen by the above conversation. All studies concur that IoT capabilities have a beneficial association with company performance from various angles. However, it was discovered that many studies look at IoT capability as a whole, ignoring the devices' agility, adaptability, and connectivity. Furthermore, most studies do not consider the impact of these characteristics on IoT adoption and company operational and financial success. The goal of this research is to see how each sort of IoT component (flexibility, agility, and connection) affects operational and financial performance of firms, mediated by visibility and moderated by DDIPCs. The purpose of this study is to propose a conceptual framework for a model that is designed to explain the relationship between flexibility, agility and connectivity of IoT devices and increase in firm performance, mediated by visibility and dynamic data information processing capabilities of the firms as moderator. Thereby, recognising the interdependency of financial and operational performance. Table 2.3 summarizes and critically analyses the literature on IoT capabilities and firm performance.

Table 2.3: Summary of literature on IoT capabilities and firm performance

Reference	Analytical Methodology	Topic	Critical Analysis
Calış Duman <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Quantitative approach. Survey Sample: 877 high tech new ventures.	Dynamic environments and relationship between dynamic capability and firm operational performance, an empirical study of Chinese new ventures.	Provisional and regional limitations restrict applied research in I4.0.
Jain <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Theoretical analysis	Investigating the impact of IT infrastructure and e-commerce capability on firm performance.	Similar study can be conducted in other countries regarding the existence of I4.0 applications in manufacturing.

Agostini <i>et al.</i> (2021)	SEM Survey Sample: 75 public companies in manufacturing industry.	Data mining in the relation between ownership structure and firm performance, a structural equation model analysis of Chinese public companies in manufacturing industry.	Data was limited to subjective measures, increasing the subjectivity of the findings.
Kumar <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Multivariable regression analysis Survey Sample: 178 manufacturing firms in China.	An empirical research to study the relationship between IoT capabilities and firm performance to by assembling resources that work together with organizational capabilities.	Size and turnover are essential aspects of a company that are missed in this research.
Ghobakhloo (2020)	SEM Survey Sample: 558 Taiwan financial companies.	IoT adoption of firms and service innovation contributing to the enhancement of firm performance.	Need to assess the business value of lean-digitized manufacturing system in a larger scale research context.
Derigent <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Regression analysis Survey Sample: 102 smart factories in Europe.	To verify the effect of high radicality of product innovation on high flexibility and high agility in manufacturing system; along with its impact on business performance.	Some key enablers of Industry 4.0 are still not addressed by holonic architectures.
Sony <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Theoretical analysis	To investigate the effects of IoT in manufacturing innovation processes by developing a conceptual framework.	Limited databases access, followed by limitations such as search criteria, screening method, inclusion/exclusion criteria and time constraints.
Teekasap (2017)	SEM Survey Sample: 67 SMEs in Brazil	To study whether IoT investments drive firm performance in the long term.	Data is limited to a single country; a need to replicate the survey in other countries confirms the findings.
Mu (2017)	Hierarchical regression analysis Survey Sample: 1000 Chinese high-tech firms	To investigate the link between dynamic capability, marketing capability and operations capability on firm performance by proposing a model that links all these factors with firm performance.	With IoT filled with security vulnerabilities, security and privacy of information from both legal and technical points of view should be considered.
Côrte-Real <i>et al.</i> (2020)	SEM Survey Sample: 614 European high-tech firms	Understanding the relationship between the emergence of IoT and firm performance to make rational decisions regarding business model configurations and investments in IoT.	Solutions come with many overhead costs and require specialized expertise to be implemented correctly, which are missed.

Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2012)	Hierarchical regression analysis Survey Sample: 187 high tech Chinese firms.	To examine how service innovation can be beneficial to manufacturing firms in terms of firm performance.	Normative models are needed more than before, as research merely describes the transformation.
Sung (2018)	SEM Survey Sample: 45 questionnaires to senior managers.	Research on the relationship between IoT capabilities and firm performance based on industry environment conditions.	Research does not provide empirical findings to support policy implications.
Aydiner <i>et al.</i> (2019)	SEM Survey Sample: 204 firms in Turkey	To analyse the impact of IoT capabilities on 3PL firms on logistics performance and financial performance	No mention of tools for model-driven development to simplify the process of building IoT applications.
Lyu <i>et al.</i> (2009)	SEM Survey Sample: 168 SMEs in Taiwan.	To understand the present innovative situation of business services and to analyse the relationship between IoT, innovation and firm performance in manufacturing industry.	This is a preliminary study and other variables may be taken into account as antecedents to Industry 4.0 implementation.
Akhtar <i>et al.</i> (2018)	SEM Survey Sample: 205 responses from European IT, telecommunication and energy companies.	To investigate the relationship between IoT, DDIPCs and operational agility of firms.	Study focuses only on the operational agility of the firms, whereas firm performance is a combination of both operational and financial performance.
Mikalef <i>et al.</i> (2017)	PLS-SEM Survey Sample: 274 international firms.	To examine the relationship between IT-enabled dynamic capabilities and competitive performance, as mediated by organizational agility.	Discussion of technical requirements on data processing capabilities remained out of scope of the paper.
Mital <i>et al.</i> (2018)	SEM Survey Sample: 314 responses.	To investigate the adoption of IoT in India.	The results of the survey are only valid at the industry level behavior (macro).
Birkel <i>et al.</i> (2020)	SLR Sample: 102 peer review papers.	To provide a comprehensive overview of the challenges and risks of IoT in supply chain management.	IoT solutions may use different reaction mechanisms, which are missed in this study.
Wagner <i>et al.</i> (2018)	PLS-SEM and Hierarchical regression analysis Survey Sample: 336 manufacturing firms from Europe and US.	To investigate the determinants of sourcing flexibility and its impact on firm performance.	Focus only on a simple industry 4.0 architecture, missing the interoperability and standardization issues.

Tang <i>et al.</i> (2019)	SLR Sample: 97 peer review papers.	To identify common emerging areas of application of IoT along with examination of current limitations and predictions of future research directions.	In industry 4.0, management care about the issues of real time, which need addressing.
Jain <i>et al.</i> (2021)	EFA on manufacturing managers and IT professionals	An experimental evaluation of improved IoT middleware for flexible performance and efficient connectivity	Study was based only on smart infrastructure sensor technology in UK, which is limited.
Al-Surmi <i>et al.</i> (2020)	SEM Survey Sample: 242 Yemen managers	The performance impact of triadic strategic alignment among business, IT, and marketing strategies while simultaneously implementing IoT in the firms.	Challenges involving complexity of enterprise systems mainly in the form of high dimensionality are lacking.
Beigne <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Theoretical analysis	To identify flexible IoT application solutions at both architectural and technological levels.	Several control agents including configuration agent and contract manager are missing.
Wamba <i>et al.</i> (2017)	SEM Survey Sample: 297 Chinese IT managers and business analytics.	To propose a big data analytics capability model by examining the direct effects of these capabilities on firm performance.	Validation of model used by SEM is needed.
Warner <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Qualitative study	To explore how incumbent firms in traditional industries build dynamic capabilities for digital transformations.	Data was limited to subjective measures, increasing the subjectivity of the findings.
Aydiner <i>et al.</i> (2019)	SEM Survey Sample: 204 firms in Turkey.	To investigate the interrelationship between information systems related capabilities and their effects on firm performance.	Limited sample size and sample specificity.
Wilden <i>et al.</i> (2013)	PLS-SEM Survey Sample: Major Australian firms with more than 150 employees.	To examine whether organic organizational structures facilitate the impact of dynamic capabilities on organizational performance.	To understand how the core characteristics of reconfigurability interact (whether they possess similar/different behavior or whether one impacts positively/negatively on another.

2.9 Resource-Based View (RBV)

What began as a generic view of the firm has evolved into "one of the most prominent and powerful models for defining, explaining, and forecasting organisational interactions" (p. 1300) (Fawcett *et al.*, 2011) across business disciplines. This was no easy task, and the resource-based strategy took more than three decades to evolve into the RBV. Several other theories of the firm have been proposed in the strategy and management literatures (e.g., transaction cost economics, agency theory, network view, and institutional theory), but only RBV considers an organisation as a collection of resources and provides a powerful framework for uniting multiple and dissimilar resources, which can then be combined to generate competitive advantage (Gligor *et al.*, 2014; Chou *et al.*, 2018; Aydiner *et al.*, 2019). Given the context of our study, knowing what IoT-specific resources a company has and determining the best approach to use them is important to gaining a competitive advantage (Weking *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, experts from a variety of business disciplines claim that RBV has the ability to combine several research streams and other theories of the firm to form a single overarching strategic theory of the firm (Seddon, 2014; Akter *et al.*, 2016; Chou *et al.*, 2018). Aside from RBV, IT strategy experts are interested in the knowledge-based perspective of the company, dynamic capacities, and contingency theory. While the knowledge-based perspective of the business and dynamic capacities are RBV spin-offs, Dekkers *et al.*, (2019) discovered that contingency theory has weaker explanatory power than RBV in describing firm performance in terms of revenue and profitability. This empirical data is in accordance with other current (and previous) studies that have identified RBV as one of the most persuasive theories in the information system (IS) and other business disciplines for explaining the relationship between organisational resources and company performance (Fawcett *et al.*, 2011; Gligor *et al.*, 2014; Chou *et al.*, 2018; Aydiner *et al.*, 2019). For example, Chae *et al.* (2018) argue that employing RBV can increase the value of IS resources in business performance. Akter *et al.*, (2016) note that RBV contains empirically testable hypotheses, whose evaluation will contribute to our understanding of the role of IS resources in organisational performance. RBV is a strong framework, according to Liang *et al.* (2010), that allows for the identification and categorization of IS resources, as well as the measurement of their impact on a firm's

competitive advantage and performance. RBV is a well-known theory in a variety of business areas, including marketing (Lightfoot *et al.*, 2013), operations management (Ali *et al.*, 2017), supply chain management (Holmström *et al.*, 2016; Aryal *et al.*, 2018; Birkel *et al.*, 2020), and strategic management (Al-Surmi *et al.*, 2020), in addition to the MIS sector.

This shows that RBV is a key paradigm for analysing the relationship between organisational resources and performance, both theoretically and experimentally. Given that the major goal of this study is to uncover the relationships that will enable organisations to leverage IoT capabilities, which could lead to improved company performance, RBV looks like an appropriate theoretical framework. This is in line with Aydiner *et al.*, (2019) argument that RBV not only provides a valuable tool for evaluating the strategic worth of organisational resources, but also establishes resources as an independent variable and company performance as a dependent variable that are linked. According to RBV, a company's tangible and intangible resources are diverse, but only those that are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (or simply VRIN) may give it a competitive advantage (Seddon, 2014). While RBV does not differentiate between resources and capabilities, Seddon *et al.*, (2017) define resources as a company's assets that it owns and manages. Capabilities, on the other hand, are characterised as a unique sort of resource (Akter *et al.*, 2016) that allows businesses to pool and deploy their resources (in concert) to achieve a certain goal (Queiroz *et al.*, 2018). In the existing literature, numerous different categories of resources have been suggested. Physical resources used by businesses include machines, industrial equipment, and buildings (Kerin *et al.*, 2020; Shi, Xie, *et al.*, 2020). Experience, skill, judgement, risk-taking proclivity, and wisdom are all attributes associated with a company's human resources (Masum *et al.*, 2016; Obeidat *et al.*, 2016). The formal reporting structure, clear management control mechanisms, and compensation regulations are all examples of organisational resources as well as the history, relationships, trust, and organisational culture that are features of groups of employees affiliated with a corporation (Jardim-goncalves *et al.*, 2017).

According to RBV, superior performance is dependent on the firm's resources and competencies. The value of resources, according to Fawcett *et al.*, (2011), is to deliver a service (enhance performance). Furthermore, organisations maximise the value of their resources by

deploying skills to allocate scarce resources to the most productive tasks. As a result, human (managerial and technical staff), physical (equipment), technological, and relational resources all play a role in a company's capabilities (Srivastava *et al.*, 2001; Shafeey *et al.*, 2014). Combining resources, according to Yew Wong *et al.*, (2010), can result in the production of skills and capabilities. Capabilities, for example, are deeply ingrained inside intricate combinations of stored knowledge and skills that originate from training and long-term experience, and they are exercised through organisational resource; formal procedures and established "routines" (Liang *et al.*, 2010). Furthermore, this embeddedness (capability ownership) is not transferable (Fawcett *et al.*, 2011). As a result, capacities are viewed as enablers rather than catalysts for other resources (Shafeey *et al.*, 2014).

Firms compete on the basis of "unique" organisational resources that are valued, scarce, difficult to replicate, non-substitutable, and produce long-term competitive advantage, according to Gligor *et al.*, (2014). Furthermore, valuable and uncommon resources gain a competitive advantage in the near term, and enterprises perform better, but in order for these advantages to be sustained over time, such resources must be inimitable and non-substitutable (Srivastava *et al.*, 2001). Competitors can easily purchase or reproduce some resources, such as physical and technological assets (Seddon, 2014). A corporation can survive competitive imitation and maintain competitive advantage by generating and continuously adapting physical and technological resources, or by combining these resources with additional resources and competencies (Liang *et al.*, 2010; Yew Wong *et al.*, 2010).

2.10 Summary

This chapter summarised the existing literature on the rise of new manufacturing philosophies such as smart factories and CPSs as a result of IoT technologies. The advantages of IoT-based manufacturing systems are well understood, particularly in terms of demand agility and flexibility in adopting and modifying solutions. As a result, this technology may assist manufacturers to increase their operational efficiency by enhancing interaction in business-to-business interactions such as manufacturer-to-wholesaler or wholesaler-to-retailer. Operational

performance and competitive advantage of the firms has been a focus of recent research; however, the above literature review identifies the need to look at the impact of IoT on overall firm performance with includes both operational and financial performance of the firms based on RBV.

Chapter 3 Conceptual Framework and Hypotheses Development

3.1 Introduction

The establishment of a suitable conceptual framework to help accomplish the key objectives of this research is explained in this chapter, which builds on the literature review completed in the preceding chapter. This chapter focuses on the notion of IoT factors, followed by an assessment of how they affect firm performance. It defines IoT variables and establishes measurement items for each of these factors, DDIPCs and visibility, in particular. Following that, it concentrates on hypotheses development by supporting the direct and indirect effects of IoT, DDIPCs, and visibility on firm performance.

Novel features of this chapter are the variables of IoT, dynamic capabilities of firms and information visibility, and the theoretical foundations for explaining relationships between these constructs and firm performance. This approach helps to gain a better understanding of what, which, how and why each IoT variable, DDIPCs and visibility enhance firm performance.

3.2 Conceptual Framework

A detailed examination of the elements that govern how easy it is to use IoT has revealed that these variables have been proven as major predictors of how easy it is to use technology. Furthermore, research has identified DDIPCs and information visibility as structures that may have a direct or indirect impact on company performance. As a result, we examine the creation of the proposed conceptual framework for this study in this chapter by providing more information about the various components. The goal of this model is to get a thorough understanding of the phenomenon being studied by demonstrating the impact of independent

variables on the value of dependent variables. It will also allow the researcher to hypothesise and evaluate the links between identified variables in order to ensure that the theorised model is valid.

In particular, this research adopts connectivity, flexibility and agility of IoT devices (independent variables) as determinants that indicate the ease of using IoT technology. Visibility is expected to mediate the relationship between the use of IoT and firm performance (dependent variable), whereas DDIPCs are expected to moderate the relationships between use of IoT and firm performance, and visibility and firm performance. Figure 3.1 illustrates the proposed model, followed by detailed explanation of each category in next sections of this chapter.

Figure 3.1: Proposed conceptual model

3.3 Direct Effects

This section will provide a full explanation of the direct correlations between IoT use and firm performance, as well as a justification for including each of the model's elements.

3.3.1 Connectivity of IoT

Sensors, actuators and network platforms are linked together to establish an IoT infrastructure (Jeon *et al.*, 2020; Sharma *et al.*, 2020). The degree to which things are networked together is defined as IoT connectivity (Galinina *et al.*, 2017). Connectivity creates a new environment and mechanism for IoT product systems to communicate with one another via monitoring, control, and optimization. This environment enables IoT devices to communicate with the cloud and other IoT devices. This connection allows enhanced sensing chances by maintaining and increasing data flow in real-time within the IoT product system. Connectivity aids in the maintenance of sensing, configuration, and change capabilities. As a result, a reliable connection removes the chances of distorted data, making functions easier. Therefore, a stable connection enables firms to make better decisions, increasing interactions with different partners within the production network (Mekki *et al.*, 2019).

Suppliers would be able to acquire more data if there was a reliable connectivity between IoT items. With various IoT devices linked together, they can be utilised to collect various types of data to meet the needs of the suppliers. More data from customers' products and processes enables suppliers to better understand and learn about their customers' preferences, increasing their chances of coming up with new ideas or possibilities to improve their present operations utilising digital technology to meet customer demands (Sharma *et al.*, 2020). Connectivity allows for real-time monitoring of IoT products and processes, as well as enhanced sensing capabilities for continual regular improvements using digital technologies to eliminate delays and provide more responsive customer support.

The connected network of IoT system products enables them to increase their functionality in order to control/adjust the system according to the needs of a new circumstance without having to visit the products' locations (Boyes *et al.*, 2018). Customers will have more alternatives to add more sophisticated features in a shorter amount of time when they need them, thanks to this capability. As a result, the system has become more adaptable, allowing providers to quickly adjust to changing consumer needs by switching to a new configuration. This resource is also utilised to enable the monitoring and control capabilities of other IoT products.

When the connection is seamless and stable, IoT products and systems are able to coordinate easily. While the link is active, IoT items can receive real-time updates on the state and operations of other IoT products, allowing them to take appropriate action (Belhadi *et al.*, 2021). Joy Global's Longwall shearer, for example, can communicate with other equipment independently to improve mining efficiency.

Hypothesis 1a:

H1a: Connectivity of IoT devices is positively related to the use of IoT.

3.3.2 Flexibility of IoT

IoT promises a technological revolution that can boost efficiency and productivity in existing equipment infrastructure. It also aids in the utilisation of cloud-based IT technologies and capabilities, which are growing more powerful. Implementing real-time data analysis can allow for autonomous decision-making, as well as the creation of new services and revenue streams for businesses. In a world where no two organisations are the same, getting the most out of any IoT application requires IoT solutions that are tailored to specific company needs.

For many, especially those in industrial sectors, it can be a complicated, fragmented, and even an apprehensive shift. For example, the manufacturing industry has decades of legacy equipment and infrastructure that is difficult to replace rapidly or at a reasonable cost. Connecting smart sensor technologies to the cloud and enterprise software with new embedded hardware and software, often via an internet gateway, raises concerns of connectivity, interoperability, security, and scalability (Szydlo *et al.*, 2017). All of this can make connecting previously unconnected systems and devices a difficult task, especially when working with solutions from various suppliers.

Every use case necessitates IoT solutions that are uniquely adapted to the demands of the business, which is why flexibility is so important (Mboli *et al.*, 2020). The success of a particular IoT application depends on selecting a connectivity service provider that not only understands the business objectives, but also provides completely modular IoT solutions—connectivity, management, billing, and security. Experts may offer highly tailored solutions

thanks to the option to deploy modules separately or in combination, ensuring delivery of the best-fit technology for the business and giving the tools to launch and grow your IoT deployment globally. Therefore flexibility is an important factor to be considered when implementing IoT solutions. For instance, the element of convenience is effectively provided to more individuals by installing connected, smart, or sensor-driven gadgets. A more personalised experience can be provided to the customer with the convergence of these historically distinct areas of energy management, security, and convenience. To put it another way, flexibility is offered to the customers.

Flexible platforms not only promote cross-device communication, but they also collect, validate, and enrich data using analytics before combining it with other resources (Szydlo *et al.*, 2017; Secchi *et al.*, 2019). They then allow IoT devices to expose the generated intelligence to apps that produce commercial outcomes such as optimising energy production for a utility or decreasing manufacturing process mistakes. As a result, the architecture of IoT systems must be flexible in terms of handling alternative wireless protocols, minimising power consumption, and adding additional sensor inputs.

Hypothesis 1b:

H1_b: Flexibility of IoT devices is positively related to the use of IoT.

3.3.3 Agility of IoT

Agility is a tool that helps companies respond more quickly to client needs (Akhtar *et al.*, 2018; Farahani *et al.*, 2018). In other terms, agility is described as an organization's capacity to respond quickly to changes and uncertainty (Hasegan *et al.*, 2018). In addition to these features, agility aids in reacting to internal operational changes and gives more flexibility in day-to-day operations (Akhtar *et al.*, 2018), allowing the firm to take advantage of market opportunities in the external business environment (Burke *et al.*, 2014), as it is a customer-focused or environment-focused approach rather than organization-focused.

Demand for flexible and smart responses will continue to grow as additional computational capabilities in IoT clusters become available (Wan *et al.*, 2020). To accomplish speed and

accuracy, it is necessary to recognise critical data and events, as well as respond quickly when anything significant occurs. The user experience is also improved by a responsive design (Szydło et al., 2017; Oteafy et al., 2018; Oztemel et al., 2020). Customers aren't the only ones who use IoT; technicians, engineers, families, and others use it as well. The capacity of the IoT to communicate with small devices is a major selling advantage.

The pervasive networking of IoT devices within enterprises has fostered the establishment of a data-rich business environment. Access to information at any time, from any location, and in any format is expected in today's digitally enhanced corporate landscapes. As customers become more connected to their suppliers via the internet, businesses have recognised the growing need to develop strategies that reflect their reliance on their digital ecosystems (Oztemel et al., 2020). Best practises in scenario-based planning that anticipated change include customer-facing decision support and dynamic analytic models (Szydło et al., 2017). The evolution of the digital interaction between management and customers can be used to identify the fundamental enablers of agility for digital business success.

Hypothesis 1c:

H1c: Agility of IoT devices is positively related to the use of IoT.

3.3.4 Use of IoT and Firm Performance

We can discover a number of studies that have explored how operations are restructured when adopting a new factory concept (smart factory) and how businesses are affected by this reorganisation, with the increased attention on how emerging technologies are enabling digital transformations of firms. Scholars appear to agree on the efficiency improvements associated with digital transformation of manufacturing processes in companies that have implemented advanced and distributed control over their processes (including production and supply chain) (De Mendonca et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2019; Rao et al., 2019; Alhawari et al., 2021). Certain IoT technologies, such as 3D printing, robotics and artificial intelligence (AI), have been proven to have a significant impact on the management of manufacturing processes, including scale and variety. Furthermore, by including customers in product design and development,

digital manufacturing and IoT solutions help enterprises to revolutionise their inventive processes (Aryal *et al.*, 2018; Al-Surmi *et al.*, 2020). Firms can reimagine their business strategies by altering the sources of value generation with the help of smart products (Radziwon *et al.*, 2014).

According to Nagy *et al.*, (2018), companies that leverage IoT solutions to turn technological developments into competitive advantages develop the ability to create new value streams and outperform their competitors. Tang *et al.*, (2018) suggested that a company's ability to adapt and supply smart products will provide it a competitive edge, reducing industry obstacles and reformulating value chain characteristics and structure. Smart products provide new capabilities such as monitoring, control, optimization, and autonomy, all of which have an impact on value chain connections (Farahani *et al.*, 2018; Oztemel *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, firms may find alternate strategies with rise of new strategic opportunities that will enable them to gain better vision and performance.

According to recent research on digital manufacturing, organisations who adopt new digital technical solutions can increase production and efficiency (Holmström *et al.*, 2016). Although the flexibility and agility of IoT technology is coupled with firms' ability to meet market demands and provide enhanced product variety with a high level of customization, operational processes are difficult to re-evaluate and restructure within a new factory concept (Mital *et al.*, 2018; Ghobakhloo, 2020). Firms may efficiently deploy lean manufacturing solutions by relying on new IoT solutions that help to improve control over material and information flow. 3D printing, for example, allows for supply chain reorganisation (Sharma *et al.*, 2020; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2020).

Digital technologies, on the other hand, are linked to new innovation methodologies that encourage client participation in product creation and production (Derigent *et al.*, 2020; Osterrieder *et al.*, 2020). Companies that use digital IoT technologies can withstand open and distributed innovation processes. IoT technologies have an impact on a variety of corporate operations and processes, delivering a wide range of benefits to businesses that can help them improve their performance (Maganha *et al.*, 2018). Big data and IoT, for example, are aimed

at making processes and product monitoring easier, whilst 3D printing and additive manufacturing are useful tools for increasing customisation and efficiency (Brozzi *et al.*, 2020). Automation can be applied to a variety of commercial activities, while robotics is associated with increased productivity in operations and manufacturing (Sung, 2018; Kozjek *et al.*, 2020). As a result, companies who invest in and embrace IoT technologies can expect to achieve a variety of objectives, including improved performance.

Within the context of this discussion, it is expected that the adoption of such technologies will provide enterprises with a competitive edge in terms of efficiency, distinctiveness, and support for innovation (Maisiri *et al.*, 2021; Yousefnezhad *et al.*, 2021). The introduction of new digital technologies that support a paradigm shift from traditional production to smart manufacturing necessitates a better understanding of the link between IoT usage and improved firm performance. This relationship is better understood by the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 2:

H2a: Use of IoT has a direct and positive impact on financial performance.

H2b: Use of IoT has a direct and positive impact on operational performance.

3.4 Indirect Effects

3.4.1 Visibility and Use of IoT

The manufacturing sector is critical to economic development. In order to remain in today's global market, businesses must network with a variety of other partners. As a result, manufacturers must rethink their collaboration strategies and find new ways to share up-to-date information within their organisations (Jagtap *et al.*, 2019). Although the phrases visibility and information sharing have been used interchangeably in the literature, they are not synonymous (Pero *et al.*, 2014; Maghsoudi *et al.*, 2016; da Silva *et al.*, 2019). Information sharing is an action, and visibility is the result, according to (Barratt *et al.*, 2007). Academics and practitioners have been discussing visibility across industrial processes. Kharlamov *et al.*,

(2018) define visibility in supply chains as the perception, type, and usefulness of information exchanged, as well as the ability of enterprises to act on such information. Adoption of IoT technologies within the sector can provide transparency and information visibility throughout the manufacturing process (Haddud *et al.*, 2017; Jagtap *et al.*, 2019). This aids in obtaining accurate real-time information about processes and transactions when physical items are transported forward and backward.

Firms must be able to supply goods and services to their clients as swiftly and affordably as feasible to compete in today's dynamic business environment (Mostafa *et al.*, 2019; Rao *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, businesses must be able to deliver exceptional results in product distribution and customer value. To achieve these objectives effectively, manufacturing members must have access to information about all parts of the production process (da Silva *et al.*, 2019). An ideal circumstance proposes a flawless end-to-end information flow that is available in real-time and visible to all members in order to achieve desired value. According to a study of U.S. manufacturers (Sithole *et al.*, 2016), eight out of ten had fragmented systems that made communication with their supply chain partners challenging. Furthermore, the majority of respondents claimed that the absence of compatibility prevented them from accessing important external data (Pradhan *et al.*, 2018; Jagtap *et al.*, 2019; Ahmed *et al.*, 2021). In other words, the absence of data access revealed a lack of understanding of the production process. This significantly hinders businesses' ability to achieve two important goals: improved customer service and increased company performance (Ahmed *et al.*, 2021).

Until date, research has suggested that visibility is important for increasing company performance. According to research undertaken by Ahmed *et al.*, (2021), firms that have access to information beyond their cooperation limits perform far better than organisations that do not. According to da Silva *et al.*, (2019), the more precise the data, the greater the visibility and, as a result, the better the firm's success. Due to a lack of visibility, many businesses rely on forecasts rather than demand to make decisions, forcing them to make decisions apart from their production partners (Mandal, 2017). The existence of functional silos also obstructs data flow and access (Ellis *et al.*, 2018). The ability of a company to respond to customer requests is a benefit of information sharing. Barratt *et al.*, (2007) suggest that visibility has two stages:

the first includes the recipient deciding how accurate, timely, and relevant the data is. When information is processed through these checks, it becomes visible. The second stage entails incorporating the knowledge into the decision-making processes of the recipients in order for them to make educated decisions. This logic demonstrates that better decision-making leads to better performance. According to Jagtap *et al.*, (2019) and Ahmed *et al.*, (2021), visibility has a significant impact on corporate performance. They claimed that because the ultimate purpose of businesses is to be market-driven, they can attract more customers, improve channel relations, gain a competitive edge, and be aware of trends if the information they have is current and logical. This capability is created via visibility. Because visibility reduces uncertainty, the amount of buffer inventory (used to mitigate risks and uncertainties) is lowered (Bartlett *et al.*, 2007). As a result, businesses are able to demonstrate improved performance. This leads us to devise the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 3:

H3a: Visibility mediates the relationship between use of IoT and financial performance.

H3b: Visibility mediates the relationship between Use of IoT and operational performance.

3.4.2 DDIPCs and Use of IoT

Advanced developments in the digital, material, and biological realms have constituted the driving matrix for businesses in recent years (De Mendonca *et al.*, 2018). After the fourth industrial revolution, for example, there is a focus on cloud, computers, IoT, AI, and Big Data, all of which are part of the so-called Digital Transformation. The use of information and communication technology (ICT) is a key component of the digital transformation, as it aids in the transformation and reconfiguration of organisational factors such as strategy, procedures, culture, and structures (Mu, 2017). Organizations must also be able to reconfigure themselves in the face of a competitive market using capabilities, in addition to this digital revolution. These capabilities are termed as the Dynamic Capabilities of organizations (De Mendonca *et al.*, 2018; Teece, 2018; Coreynen *et al.*, 2020).

As quoted by De Mendonca *et al.*, (2018), dynamic capabilities are:

'Dynamic capabilities are related to the processes that can act by analysing the external environment in which the firm is inserted, sensing through processes which aim to direct internal P&D outside the firms, recognise target segments, changing customer needs, take advantages of the opportunities detected in processes such as customer solutions, selection of organizational boundaries; and managing threats and transformations arisen from organizational changes with processes of co-specialization and knowledge management.'

To put it another way, a dynamic capacity is a collection of organisational abilities and competencies, as well as the processes that enable a company to stand out in a crowded market. Dynamic capabilities, according to Herceg *et al.*, (2020) and Kozjek *et al.*, (2020), entail implementing strategically linked planning for quick delivery and cost-effective operations and support. Dynamic capabilities, according to Warner *et al.*, (2019), are innovation bases that enable the ability to generate, extend, and adapt a firm's resource base. Firms' dynamic data and information processing capabilities (DDIPCs), according to Akhtar *et al.*, (2018), are their capacity to recognise opportunities, grasp them, and act on them. Firms must use the links between DDIPCs and IoT to quickly build, deploy, and modify business models to stay relevant in the emerging digital economy, according to reports (Jiang *et al.*, 2015; Akhtar *et al.*, 2018; Warner *et al.*, 2018).

Although the firm's regular skills allow it to carry out operational responsibilities, Sher *et al.*, (2004), Wilden *et al.*, (2013), Wamba *et al.*, (2017), Teece, (2018), Warner *et al.*, (2019) and Al-Surmi *et al.*, (2020) explain that ordinary capabilities in functions such as accounting, HR management, and sales are now easily replicable because they can be easily outsourced to the cloud and are no longer helpful in improving firm performance (Chae *et al.*, 2018; Côte-Real *et al.*, 2019). Several authors, including Akter *et al.*, (2016), Chae *et al.*, (2018), Torres *et al.*, (2018) and Aydiner *et al.*, (2019) have argued that IT capabilities no longer have a direct positive impact on firm performance, as more standardised and homogeneous information systems have been implemented through enterprise resource planning (ERP) and web technologies since 2000s. However, the findings of Brusset *et al.*, (2017), De Mendonca *et al.*,

(2018) and Alora *et al.*, (2019) suggest that the lack of a positive impact of information systems on firm performance could be explained by factors such as the lack of appropriate data, the existence of time lags between information systems and the business value generated by these systems, and the absence of an assessment of the indirect benefits of IoT (Gupta *et al.*, 2016; Al-Surmi *et al.*, 2019). Distinguished experts claim that the influence of IoT on business performance may be moderated by DDIPCs in this line of research (Chae *et al.*, 2018; Torres *et al.*, 2018; Braojos *et al.*, 2019; Côte-Real *et al.*, 2019).

The association between the adoption of IoT and business performance is significantly positive when dynamic data and information processing skills are used as a moderator (Akter *et al.*, 2016; Garcia-Murillo *et al.*, 2018). Companies who use the links between IoTs and DDIPCs, according to Akhtar *et al.*, (2018), get a competitive advantage as their daily operations become more adaptable and adaptive as their IT infrastructures evolve. DDIPC is one of the most important capacities for processing and generating knowledge from the massive volumes of data generated by the deployment of IoTs in businesses (Akter *et al.*, 2016; Lee *et al.*, 2020; Chae *et al.*, 2018; Queiroz *et al.*, 2018). These skills have the ability to transform raw data into explicit and actionable information that network partners may utilise to improve their company's performance (Gupta *et al.*, 2016). According to Akhtar *et al.*, (2018) and Kalsoom *et al.*, (2021), having DDIPCs allows businesses to acquire useful data while also storing crucial datasets that can provide actionable insights to improve their performance. DDIPCs are vital for exploring and managing a range of data in order to comprehend, build, and deploy analytics models in businesses, according to (Barton *et al.*, 2012).

When linked to the use of IoTs, DDIPCs improve firm performance in a variety of ways: they match the resource base with changing environments by gathering useful data (Teece, 2018), they improve the effectiveness, speed, and efficiency of organisational responses by utilising valuable data, and they ultimately improve performance (Rao *et al.*, 2019). According to Wamba *et al.*, (2017), when a company's ability to process information matches its information processing requirements, it can obtain better results. The connection between IoT and DDIPCs is critical for companies that operate in a fast-changing environment where they must respond and adapt to changes and environmental uncertainty (Sher *et al.*, 2004). Firms require

flexibility and innovation when making operational and financial decisions, such as the timing of market entry, and technological advances necessitate extremely responsive decisions (Mandal, 2017; Warner *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, a company with strong capabilities in utilising the links between IoT and DDIPCs will be able to successfully construct and renew the resources, assets, and common capabilities needed to update and adapt to market changes (Akhtar *et al.*, 2018; Teece, 2018). It is critical to understand the moderating influence of DDIPCs on IoT use and business performance in this environment. Therefore, the following hypothesis is generated:

Hypothesis 4:

H4a: DDIPCs moderate the relationship between Use of IoT and financial performance.

H4b: DDIPCs moderate the relationship between Use of IoT and operational performance.

3.4.3 DDIPCs and Visibility

As previously mentioned, research subjects connected to organisations' dynamic capacities and adoption of digital technologies by firms have exploded in popularity over the last decade. According to these research, companies who employ IoT solutions gain from increased flexibility and time-to-market compared to companies that use traditional inter-organizational systems, resulting in improved performance (Alora *et al.*, 2019). The potential to improve information visibility across enterprises is the rationale for the superior IoT-enabled integration (De Mendonca *et al.*, 2018). Firms tend to employ dynamic capabilities to reveal the nature of information visibility in today's extremely chaotic market environment, which may help them to control external turbulences (Brusset *et al.*, 2017).

The DDIPCs' perspective focuses on a company's internal and external competences, as well as how to develop them to match the changing external environment. Renewal of competencies and reorganisation of organisational resources are important factors of gaining new kinds of competitive advantage (Wei *et al.*, 2010; Akhtar *et al.*, 2018). DDIPCs are one-of-a-kind processes that enable businesses to integrate, reconfigure, acquire, and release resources. Product development routines, strategic decision-making routines, knowledge generation

routines, and alliance routines are all examples of DDIPCs (Alora *et al.*, 2019). Manufacturing procedures that bring in new resources from outside sources might be viewed as a critical dynamic capacity since they can change operating routes for both buying and supplying companies (Jagtap *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, DDIPCs must rely on real-time data to comprehend market conditions and act accordingly (Mikalef *et al.*, 2017). As a result, the usage of DDIPCs in manufacturing processes improves visibility (Kharlamov *et al.*, 2018; Pradhan *et al.*, 2018).

From the perspective of DDIPCs, sensing for visibility is crucial since it reflects a company's ability to sense and acquire real-time information about external, volatile surroundings and act on it (Yang *et al.*, 2013). Firms must have visibility in several areas, such as knowledge about external events and supply chain changes, in order to react to changes. Market intelligence on client wants is the most important data in manufacturing (Jagtap *et al.*, 2019). Market trends and client demand information are critical for responding to market shifts and developing new opportunities, according to research (Yang *et al.*, 2013; Kharlamov *et al.*, 2018; da Silva *et al.*, 2019; Jagtap *et al.*, 2019). When such data is shared, a company acquires the ability to perceive its partners' requirements and communicate its own needs to the partners as well (Maganha *et al.*, 2018; Kozjek *et al.*, 2020). Hence, this knowledge can help the firm to improve its performance.

According to studies, companies that devote time to developing and honing their detecting, seizing, and transforming capabilities are better equipped to innovate and create new business models (Holcomb *et al.*, 2011; Maghsoudi *et al.*, 2016; Kharlamov *et al.*, 2018; Jagtap *et al.*, 2019). Learning aids in the creation of procedures that lead to a competitive advantage for a company (Oztemel *et al.*, 2020). Huge amounts of heterogeneous data are generated throughout the product lifetime as a result of the rise of IoT technology. With a variety of cost-effective and adaptable data gathering and storage solutions available, IoT allows businesses to collect, store, and process data (Gope *et al.*, 2016; Rao *et al.*, 2019; Jeon *et al.*, 2020). As a result, businesses may reap the benefits of data analysis, which allows them to gain a better understanding of their consumers, competitors, goods, equipment, processes, and services. Firms may be able to make more logical, responsive, and informed decisions and improve their

performance in the global market if they use their dynamic skills to comprehend the value of information acquired from this data (Liboni *et al.*, 2019; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2020).

Different research disciplines, such as organisation studies, strategic management, information systems, and decision sciences, recognise the importance of a firm's dynamic power to process information. According to the majority of these studies, a firm's ability to process information has an impact on its ability to plan procedures, outsource, and make operational decisions. Kozjek *et al.*, (2020) and Oztemel *et al.*, (2020) have claimed that if a company's information processing capability matches its information processing requirements, it can improve visibility of data received during processes and thereby improve performance. In other words, a good match between information processing capabilities and needs aids organisations in establishing effective intermediate partnerships and integrating industrial processes (Sutapa *et al.*, 2017; Sarstedt *et al.*, 2018). Hence, this leads us to test the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 5:

H5a: DDIPCs moderate the relationship between Visibility and financial performance.

H5b: DDIPCs moderate the relationship between visibility and operational performance.

3.5 Use of IoT, Visibility and Firm Performance

Companies spend millions of dollars on IT to improve their data processing skills and overall performance (Benitez *et al.*, 2020). As a result of the continuing economic digitization, businesses are growing their IT investments, and management is responsible for not just cutting costs but also shaping the business. The operational and financial performance of a company determines its success. The ability of a company to use its range of operational skills is referred to as its operational performance (Dalenogare *et al.*, 2018; Braojos *et al.*, 2019). This ability is at the heart of any firm's business model, which includes features like gross margin, workforce productivity, and operations (Makhdoom *et al.*, 2019). In other words, a company's operational performance is defined as its capacity to create and implement operational routines that allow it to manufacture/supply products to the market in an excellent manner (De Mendonca *et al.*,

2018; Tang *et al.*, 2018). A company can use IoT and DDIPCs to get accurate and timely market data in order to develop and apply excellent operational talent in order to meet its goals (Herceg *et al.*, 2020). Firms aspire to boost their financial performance by maximising profitability and increasing sales revenue by enhancing their business processes (Lee *et al.*, 2020; De Mendonca *et al.*, 2018). By strengthening IoT structures and mediating their information processing capabilities through DDIPCs, firms can better communicate with and provide responsive services to their customers, ultimately positively influencing their business (Akter *et al.*, 2016; Ghasemaghaei *et al.*, 2018; Queiroz *et al.*, 2018; Torres *et al.*, 2018).

For the purpose of determining the implications of supply chain performance, Brusset (2017) looked at both upstream and downstream links. The results showed that by streamlining supply chain processes, it was able to achieve as much visibility as possible, particularly in downstream activities. IoT has a significant impact on the character and structure of supply chains by increasing communication and collecting and sharing data, thanks to its potential to ease internal integration with suppliers (Ben-Daya *et al.*, 2019). This aids in better decision-making and improves the performance of the company. It also aids in the administration of remote supply chain activities, greater integration with partners for product information, and the provision of more exact data for effective financial decision-making (Haddud *et al.*, 2017; Wamba *et al.*, 2017; Büyüközkan *et al.*, 2018; Dekkers *et al.*, 2019; Fosso Wamba *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, the use of internal links to increase downstream visibility should be recognised. Another key conclusion is that companies who used IoT to integrate suppliers benefited from increased levels of flexibility and responsiveness (Fatorachian *et al.*, 2018). IoT enables for a shorter period between data collection and decision making, allowing supply chains to respond more quickly to changing conditions in real-time, enabling high levels of agility and responsiveness never experience before (Ellis *et al.*, 2018).

3.6 Pilot Study to Validate Hypotheses

Prior to initiating a full scale questionnaire based on the above mentioned constructs, a pilot study was conducted to assess the feasibility of the processes that are key to the success of the

main study. The viability of the hypotheses was tested and confirmed by three academics (including the supervisory team), who read and provided feedback on the readability, clarity and quality of the chosen hypotheses. It was found that the academics were able to comprehend the statements and captured the general context that had practical relevance to the main aims of the study. After getting approval from the academics, the research was found to be feasible for further study.

3.7 Summary

In this chapter, a theoretical framework was proposed that will enable the researcher to understand the relationships between various factors which are expected to impact firm performance. This research model is based on the prominent indicators as discussed in the comprehensive literature review in Chapter 2 including connectivity, flexibility and agility of IoT devices, which are used as key determinants of use of IoT, followed by DDIPCs and information visibility, which are relevant to the context of this study.

Therefore, this study proposes and tests three types of hypotheses. The first category studies the direct effects of connectivity, flexibility and agility on use of IoT. In addition, the relationship between use of IoT and firm performance is hypothesised to have a direct relationship. The second category focuses on investigating the moderating impact of DDIPCs on use of IoT as well as the impact of DDIPCs on information visibility. The third category studies the mediating role of visibility between use of IoT and firm performance. Table 3.1 summarizes the hypotheses created for this study.

To fulfil the research's goal, the conceptual model will be empirically evaluated in the United Kingdom. The following chapter delves into the methodology adopted for the study, providing a thorough discussion of the data gathering methods, questionnaire preparation, and data analysis techniques employed.

Table 3.1: Summary of hypotheses

H1a	Connectivity of IoT devices is positively related to the use of IoT.
H1b	Flexibility of IoT devices is positively related to the use of IoT.
H1c	Agility of IoT devices is positively related to the use of IoT.
H2a	Use of IoT has a direct and positive impact on financial performance.
H2b	Use of IoT has a direct and positive impact on operational performance.
H3a	Visibility mediates the relationship between use of IoT and financial performance.
H3b	Visibility mediates the relationship between use of IoT and operational performance.
H4a	DDIPCs moderate the relationship between Use of IoT and financial performance.
H4b	DDIPCs moderate the relationship between Use of IoT and operational performance.
H5a	DDIPCs moderate the relationship between visibility and financial performance.
H5b	DDIPCs moderate the relationship between visibility and operational performance.

Chapter 4 Methodology

4.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the different research approaches and philosophies available for the inquiry of an impact and describes the research strategy chosen for this research. The research approach employed for this study is presented in this chapter, which addresses the research questions: 1) research methods and major research steps; 2) an overview of research philosophy and the overall research design, including sampling method and sample size; and 3) instrument development. Following a brief justification of the overall quantitative research design, an outline of the research methodologies and research paradigm is offered. Following an explanation of the data collection methods, sample procedures, and data processing tools employed, ethical considerations are clarified.

4.2 Empirical and Theoretical Research

According to Remenyi *et al.*, (1995), empirical and theoretical research are the two main categories of academic research available. Theoretical research revolves around finding a result predicted by a theory, while empirical research involves data collection and analysis. As this research is aimed at finding the impact of IoT and visibility using DDIPCs on operational and financial performance of the firms by collecting a set of data from firms in manufacturing industry, it will apply an empirical research method.

4.3 Research Philosophies

In order to comprehend the choice of methods and viewpoints (worldviews or paradigms) available to the researcher while constructing a research strategy, it is necessary to understand the many methodological philosophies available to the researcher (Spector *et al.*, 2011). A

system of beliefs and assumptions concerning the generation of knowledge is referred to as "research philosophy" (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). According to Sekaran, (2003), researchers should be mindful of the philosophical commitment they make when choosing a research strategy, as this has a significant impact on what they do and how they perceive the rationale behind what they're looking at. Saunders *et al.*, (2015) coined the term "research onion" to describe the research philosophy (Figure 3.1). The onion is a method for visualising your data gathering options and aiding in the creation of a study plan.

Figure 4.1: Research onion (Saunders *et al.*, 2015)

4.3.1 Deductive vs Inductive

The degree to which the researcher is aware on the theory at the start of the study poses an essential question about methodological selection. This is sometimes depicted as two techniques to reasoning: deductive and inductive (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). Inductive research begins with the collection of data relevant to the study question. Following the collection of a

huge amount of data, the researcher searches for patterns in the data and strives to develop a hypothesis to explain these patterns (Sekaran, 2003). As a result, in an inductive approach, a researcher begins with a collection of observations, then moves from those observations to a more specific assertion about those experiences in order to produce or build a theory (often in the form of a conceptual framework) (Hussey *et al.*, 1997). In the deductive technique, the researcher begins with a persuasive idea and then tests its implications using evidence. As a result, individuals progress from a general to a specific level (Bryman *et al.*, 2007). Both deductive and inductive reasoning are used in this study. To fulfil research objective 1 and provide answers to research questions RQ2 and RQ3, it is appropriate to develop a theoretical framework and propose hypotheses. Using surveys and large samples, the quantitative technique is the most appropriate way to answer these research issues.

4.4 Adopting Positivist Approach

The positivist strategy was chosen for this study after evaluating the differences between the three techniques and the nature of the study under investigation. In addition, the following factors were taken into account before deciding on this strategy:

- The goal of this study is to look into the direct influence of IoT on company performance, as well as the moderating and mediating effects of DDIPCs and visibility. As a result, research related to social subjects is focused where the impact of IoT is measured, and the researcher is separated from the study's goal (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). As a result, the positivist method was justified from an ontological standpoint.
- This study proposes a number of hypothesised relationships that will be evaluated and quantified in the context of IoT. The positivist approach is frequently associated with quantitative methodology, which employs a deductive strategy (Bryman *et al.*, 2007). As a result, this study is also justifiable from a methodological standpoint.
- The research's goal necessitates a well-defined conceptual framework in which links between constructs are explicitly established and exact measurements are taken. As shown in Chapter 3, a variety of constructs about the use of IoT and business performance

are constructed in this study, based on validated theories and models. As a result, this research is defensible from an epistemological standpoint.

- Structural Equation Modelling will be used in this inquiry to evaluate hypotheses, moderators, and mediators, as well as perform a variety of tests such as normality tests and comparisons (see chapter 5 and 6). The positivist approach is described by the statistical packages utilised (Kotzab *et al.*, 2005).

With the reasons discussed above for choosing positivist paradigm, the following section describes the research method.

4.5 Research Strategy

4.5.1 Qualitative vs Quantitative

The next stage is to define the research approach after grounding the philosophical assumptions. The research design and data gathering methods and methodologies are the emphasis of this step. The mechanism used to collect data at subsequent stages determines two whether quantitative or qualitative data is collected. This section compares and contrasts the methodologies in order to defend the decision.

Figure 4.2: Methodology choice (Saunders et al., 2015)

According to Saunders *et al.*, (2015), because quantitative data is symbolised as numeric data, it encompasses any data collecting and analysis approach that creates numerical data (e.g. surveys, graphs, statistics, etc.) in order to quantify the cause-effect relationship between variables. Quantitative approaches also employ a deductive approach that is linked to hypothesis testing in order to change or reinforce an existing theory (Figure 4.2) (Bryman *et al.*, 2007). They're also tied to positivist epistemology, which use scientific procedures and statistical ways to display numerical data. Qualitative data, on the other hand, is represented by non-numeric data, hence it includes data collecting and analysis procedures that produce non-numerical data (e.g. interviews, categorising data etc.) (Miles *et al.*, 1984) and uses an inductive approach to derive hypotheses from data collection and analysis (Creswell, 1994).

This study employs the natural laws of discovery in a rational way via empirical testing, hence it employs a deductive technique to generate hypotheses from a theory that will be evaluated with big samples (Gummesson, 2000). The ontological stance of this research is objective reality since it undertakes that knowledge is expanded from evidence that can be directly observed and confirmed between independent observers. Because the major goal of this study is to analyse the link between defined variables, the epistemological position of this research is a positivist paradigm approach, in which the researcher is autonomous from those being researched (Creswell, 1994; Sekaran, 2003).

This study aims to fill a research gap by investigating how complexity, flexibility and agility of IoT devices affect the use of IoT in manufacturing firms through literature review. The intention is to understand how firms are adapting to IoT technologies in daily operations (RQ1). This is the deduction method that is used to provide fundamental reasoning in this research (Miles *et al.*, 1984; Olsen, 2004). In addition, the relationship between use of IoT, visibility and firm performance (operational and financial performance), moderated by DDIPCs and mediated by visibility is examined by using large samples. To fill this research gap, this research develops a theoretical framework and hypotheses, which are tested by the use of a survey questionnaire. This is the deduction process, which is used to drive relationship between variables under study (Creswell, 1994; Saunders *et al.*, 2015).

Following the research used by Mikalef *et al.*, (2017) and Akhtar *et al.*, (2018), this research examines the use of IoT in manufacturing industry and determines its impact on firm performance. Since this research is exploratory in nature, it is important to identify factors, besides agility, that make IoT adaptable by the firms and examine their impact on firm performance, moderated by DDIPCs and mediated by visibility. It means that this research will measure the relationships between variables by adopting research methods such as surveys (Hussey *et al.*, 1997). Therefore, this research belongs to quantitative study rather than qualitative.

4.5.2 Surveys

When it comes to gathering primary data, survey research is used extensively in a variety of fields (Denzin *et al.*, 1994). Choosing a survey technique makes it simple for researchers to collect large volumes of data. According to Bryman *et al.*, (2007), surveys aid in the examination of links between various variables, allowing for the testing of a theory by responding to research questions and hypotheses. Typically, this is accomplished through the use of questionnaires, in which the researcher gathers data that can be compared readily (Saunders *et al.*, 2015).

A survey design examines a sample of a population to produce a quantitative description of trends, attitudes, or opinions (Creswell, 1994). Collis *et al.*, (2003) found that surveys were mentioned in 60% of empirical studies published in German journals between 1990 and 2002. According to Bryman *et al.*, (2007), surveys were employed in 19 of 88 German doctoral dissertations on the topic of effects. The majority of the literature in the manufacturing business, specifically logistics, is based on quantitative research viewed through a positivist perspective (Denzin *et al.*, 1994; Gummesson, 2000). The utilisation of survey data is the most extensively utilised research strategy since this study employs hypotheses and tests them with big samples (Bryman *et al.*, 2007). Thus, the survey questionnaire has been the most popular research approach for studying the influence of IoT on corporate performance, followed by the case study.

The researcher used a survey approach for the current study for the following reasons:

- In business and information system journals, the survey approach is the most common (at least 50% of the total number of papers), for instance, Journal of Operations management, Computers in Industry, Production Planning and Control, Journal of Supply Chain Management etc.
- The survey method is the most commonly utilised method in technology adoption study, for example Fuller *et al.*, (2015) found that more than 78% of the articles in above mentioned journals that are related to IoT and its implementation use survey approach, while case studies were used by remaining 22% only (Hofmann *et al.*, 2017; Ben-Daya *et al.*, 2019; Manavalan *et al.*, 2019; Ahmed *et al.*, 2021; Zighan *et al.*, 2021).
- The goal of this study is to look at the impact of IoT on business performance, which necessitates gathering data from a big number of people, especially when employing the SEM technique for data analysis. As a result, any method other than surveys will be exceedingly costly and time-consuming (Hair *et al.*, 2010).
- A number of hypotheses within the given conceptual model (see Chapter 3) must be experimentally evaluated, and only the survey approach is adequate.
- The survey method is tied to positivist-quantitative methodologies in research (Saunders *et al.*, 2015).
- When adopting a survey approach, a huge amount of data is collected, allowing the conclusions to be generalised to the entire population.

Data using surveys is typically acquired using a variety of methods, including mail, telephone interviews, email, and self-administered questionnaires (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). For the following reasons, this study used an online survey as a data gathering method:

- When compared to other methods such as interviews, data may be obtained from a large number of participants concurrently in a rapid, easy, efficient, and cost-effective manner (Creswell, 1994; Bryman *et al.*, 2007).
- It is simple to create and administer. Interviews, for example, typically necessitate a high level of administrative expertise (Saunders *et al.*, 2015).

- Respondents have a high level of privacy because issues like anonymity and confidentiality were addressed in the cover letter.
- Collecting responses as soon as they are received promotes a higher response rate (Sekaran, 2003).
- A questionnaire has been commonly utilised as a data gathering strategy in studies similar to this one, for instance, Vickery *et al.*, (2003), Khan *et al.*, (2018), Kwak *et al.*, (2018), Mital *et al.*, (2018), Ben-Daya *et al.*, (2019) and Rao *et al.*, (2019).

This will lead to answering the research questions RQ1 to RQ3.

4.6 Research Design

A research design, according to Bryman *et al.*, (2007), provides broad guidance and outline for a study's data gathering and analysis. It is crucial in terms of connecting theory to empirical data to answer research issues (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). The usage and kind of data collection, sampling strategies, and budget are all determined by the research design chosen (Hair Jr. *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, when planning an investigation, the researcher should establish a list of sensible decisions about the study's goal, location, type of inquiry, researcher's position, time period, and level of data analysis (Sekaran, 2003). The goal of this study is to test hypotheses developed from the conceptual model using the research design guidelines offered by (Bryman *et al.*, 2007). Hypothesis testing enables researchers to quickly comprehend the interactions that exist between variables by elucidating the nature of such correlations. To characterise the factors that are linked to the research objectives and investigate significant links between IoT and business performance, a correlational analysis is chosen over a causal study. This study is conducted in a non-contrived context, which is identical to all correlation studies. The researcher did not intervene because the data for this study was gathered through a survey. Due to the reason that employing SEM requires large samples and it is beyond the timeframe of this research to gather longitudinal data at a different time to analyse the change in the dependent

variables, this investigation was chosen to follow a cross-sectional design.

Figure 4.3: Research design

Figure 4.3 depicts the study's research design, which is based on a series of phases proposed by Creswell, (1994). Chapter 2 of the literature review was crucial in gaining a thorough understanding of the research problem. The building of a conceptual model using constructs was shown in Chapter 3 in order to test the hypotheses. Chapter 4 discusses the research methods used to solve the research problem, such as employing a quantitative way to collect data, stages in survey development (validity, pilot test), sampling technique, and data collection process. A preliminary analysis of the acquired data was required to test the proposed model (Chapter 5). The results of the research model's testing are presented in Chapter 6, followed by a discussion and conclusion in Chapters 7.

4.7 Population and Sampling

In order to reflect the targeted population and avoid bias in data collecting methods, a sampling approach is an important aspect of the research before moving further with data gathering (Creswell, 1994; Bryman *et al.*, 2007). When designing a sample, four essential concerns must be considered, according to Saunders *et al.*, (2015): 1) sample approach (probability or non-probability); 2) sample frame; 3) sample size; and 4) response rate.

4.7.1 Sample

According to Saunders *et al.*, (2015), when designing a sample, the researcher should consider numerous factors, including the nature of the study problem, objectives, time, and budget. The two categories of sampling strategies are probability and non-probability (Creswell, 1994; Sekaran, 2003; Bryman *et al.*, 2007). Table 4.1 shows a description of each sample method along with the sampling approach and advantages/disadvantages of each technique.

Table 4.1: Sampling methods with sampling techniques

Technique	Advantages	Disadvantages
Probability Sampling		
Simple random sampling (SRS)	Easy to implement, analysis and interpretation, results projectable.	Require a complete list of population, expensive, time-consuming, produces high error rate.
Systematic	Simpler, faster, and less expensive than SRS. It is simple to determine the sampling distribution of the mean or proportion.	Costly and less representative than SRS; results and sample size may be skewed due to population periodicity.
Stratified random	The researcher determines the sample size in strata. All significant subgroups are included. Reduces the chance of sampling inaccuracy.	In comparison to SRS, it is more expensive and difficult, so researchers should put in more effort.
Cluster	Cost-effective, rapid, suitable for a huge population, and simple to implement inside a population list.	The fact that subgroups are homogeneous rather than heterogeneous will lead to reduced statistical efficiency because the findings are imprecise and difficult to quantify.

Non-probability Sampling		
Convenience	Among other approaches, it is the least expensive, time-consuming, and easiest to administer to ensure a sufficient number of participants in a study. It is also the most convenient and common.	Because the sample is not representative of the entire population, caution should be exercised when generalising conclusions.
Judgmental or Purposive	Low-cost and not time-consuming, it ensures that group sizes are balanced.	Subjectivity of the researcher can lead to bias, and the results' reliability can be questioned.
Quota	The researcher picks subgroups with controlled features and a large number of participants who are connected to the study at a low cost and in a short amount of time.	Because the results are dependent on the characteristics of the respondents in the sample, it is difficult to justify the findings as representative of the target population.
Snowball	When there are not a lot of people, it's more efficient. Even if there is no known list ahead of time, it is possible to include people.	It's time-consuming, and there's no way of knowing if the sample is representative of the total population.

4.7.2 Justifications for Using Convenience Sampling

Convenience sampling is the best method that is often utilised in business and social science studies, as previously stated (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). This strategy enables researchers to choose sample participants from the target population based on who is willing and easily accessible to participate in the study. Among all the procedures, this one is the least expensive and time-consuming. Due to the inability to get data for random sampling in the current study, as well as time and financial constraints, a non-random technique with the potential to collect sample sizes required for the analysis was chosen.

Manufacturing companies in the United Kingdom that provide integrated or comprehensive manufacturing services such as logistics, inventory management, processing operations, assembly operations, material handling and storage, and quality and control are the target audience. As a result, the FTSE 500 was used to locate and contact supply chain management experts in the companies, who were anticipated to be knowledgeable about the general operations and management of the supply chain, as well as firm-level performance.

4.7.3 Sample Size

The sample size within the targeted population must be specified for the study. According to Bryman *et al.*, (2007), adopting a large sample size in a study will not ensure precision, wasting time and money. On the other hand, when statistical data analysis, such as SEM, is necessary, using a tiny size would result in reduced accuracy of the results (J. F. Hair, Babin, *et al.*, 2017). In England, the study's target population was quite vast. As a result, the sample size was calculated using the AMOS rules of thumb for structural equation modelling. The following rules of thumb, according to Polit *et al.*, (2010), should be considered when determining sample size:

- For most studies, a size of > 30 and 500 is sufficient.
- When categorising the sample into sub-groups (e.g., older/younger, postgraduate/undergraduate), each category must have a minimum of 30 people.
- In multivariate research (e.g., SEM), the sample size need should be many times (ideally ten times) the number of variables in the proposed framework or study.

Similarly, Goodboy *et al.*, (2017) recommended a sample size of 200 or more for a sophisticated route model. While a sample size ranges from 50 to 1000, with 50 being very poor and 1000 being outstanding (Goodboy *et al.*, 2017; Hair Jr. *et al.*, 2017). As a result, Schreiber, (2017) suggested that a sample size should be calculated in terms of the number of respondents per estimated parameter, taking into account the model's complexity, which includes the number of constructs and variables. For a model with six or more constructs and three indicators in each, a sample size of 300 or more is necessary (Hair *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, Schreiber, (2017) stated that a commonly accepted value for every estimated parameter within the model is ten respondents.

Table 4.2: Research design

Particulars	Details
Target respondents	Manufacturing industries in UK
Sample frame source	UK national manufacturing database
Sampling technique	Non-probability convenience sampling
Sample size of pilot study	378
Sample size of the main study	378
Sample size of the main study considered for analysis	375
Methods of data collection	Email/online survey
Statistical techniques	EFA, CFA and SEM
Statistical tools	Excel, SPSS 26 and AMOS 26

According to the above SEM assumptions (Hair *et al.*, 2017; Schreiber, 2017), and in view of the suggested model's complexity in terms of variables and ratio of respondents (estimation of about 40 parameters), organisations should have at least 300 employees. The study's research design is summarised in Table 4.2.

4.7.4 Sample Execution

The industrial sector in the United Kingdom was chosen as an appropriate sector for this study to demonstrate the phenomena of interest (Chapter 2). The population was drawn from a national UK manufacturing database, which comprised enterprises that provide integrated or full manufacturing services, such as logistics, inventory management, processing operations, assembly operations, material handling and storage, and quality and control. Because the database contained over 10,000 companies, a lot of filters were implemented.

- Businesses with less than 100 employees and sales of less than £5 million were eliminated. A total of 3193 companies were found as a result of this filter.
- A total of 1100 people were chosen to participate in the study.

- These companies were used as a source to find and contact supply chain management experts in the companies, who were believed to be knowledgeable about the supply chain's overall operations and management, as well as the firm's overall performance.

4.8 Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire is constructed to obtain timely replies from respondents regarding their thoughts on the adoption of IoT and its impact on firm performance. The questionnaire constructs and measurements were based on previous conceptual studies because empirical studies in this setting using manufacturing businesses are sorely lacking. These studies offered data on the use of IoT and DDIPCs in manufacturing organisations, as well as information gleaned from current relevant literature on the impact of IoT agility, flexibility, and connection. To check the constructs' validity and reliability, a draught questionnaire was distributed to specialist researchers and academics in the fields of logistics, supply chain, and operations management in the manufacturing business. The constructs were tested in a pilot study with a few industrialists to ensure that they were valid and trustworthy. This study used a closed response strategy, in which participants were asked to react on a 7-point Likert scale.

4.8.1 Measures and Constructs

To operationalize the important constructs for this research, a thorough literature analysis was undertaken, which aided in determining the scales utilised in previous investigations. This allowed for the extraction of measures from studies that have validated the scales, ensuring their accuracy (Worthington *et al.*, 2006). Pre-tests were conducted to evaluate the level of applicability of the constructs with three academics, who provided feedback on how to improve the survey's content and wording (see Section 4.8.3).

Based on the literature analysis in Chapter 2, this study constructed constructs to quantify the influence of IoT on company performance. Respondents are asked to respond on a 7-point Likert scale, with 1 being strongly disagree and 7 being strongly agree (Table 4.6). This scale was chosen to reduce the attenuation issues caused by range restrictions (Schreiber, 2017). In

addition, it helps the respondent more choices to choose for the answers, which allows researcher to get accurate responses to the questions (Kwak *et al.*, 2018). Non-financial metrics such as cost, innovation, quality, delivery, and flexibility are used to assess operational performance. Financial success is assessed using financial measures such as Return on Assets, EBITDA margin, Return on Investments, EVA, and Market Value Added. The next section delves into each of the survey's constructs.

Business size (number of employees), as well as revenue and assets, were chosen as control variables that could influence firm performance. Large firms were chosen for this study because they are more likely to influence firm performance (Bharadwaj *et al.*, 2016). According to research, the size of a company is strongly linked to its performance (Wu *et al.*, 2008; Bharadwaj *et al.*, 2016; Caputo *et al.*, 2016). The basic assumption is that operational and financial performance changes depending on the firm's size and sales. Furthermore, existing literature on financial performance suggests that firm size is a good indication of financial performance because it demonstrates the accounting systems and procedures employed by businesses to determine costs (Bharadwaj *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, firm size was added in the model as control variable.

IoT operating system connects uniquely identifiable, embedded computing devices and sensors that may receive and integrate data via a network with minimal/no human-to-human or human-to-computer contact (Kimani *et al.*, 2019; Mekki *et al.*, 2019). Any IoT device must meet specific essential system criteria in order to perform effectively, such as ensuring steady network connections and efficiently managing system resources (Jeon *et al.*, 2020). Information can be accessed and used by numerous parties inside the company network thanks to the smooth connection between IoT devices. On a 7-point Likert scale, five connectivity items are designed, requiring respondents to rate connectivity levels in these business units.

The adoption of things based on requirements that can improve company performance (Patel *et al.*, 2016; Afzal *et al.*, 2019; Pacchini *et al.*, 2019; Punithavathi *et al.*, 2019) and is judged as a general competency of a firm (Mukherjee *et al.*, 2018; Kalsoom *et al.*, 2021). The degree to which IoT goods are adopted, and, more crucially, how convenient they are for the user, is

primarily determined by their flexibility. Flexible platforms not only promote cross-device communication, but they also collect, validate, and enrich data using analytics before combining it with other resources (Szydlo *et al.*, 2017). They then allow IoT devices to expose the generated intelligence to apps that produce commercial outcomes such as optimising energy production for a utility or decreasing manufacturing process mistakes. As a result, the architecture of IoT systems must be flexible in terms of handling alternative wireless protocols, minimising power consumption, and adding additional sensor inputs. Five flexibility items are developed on a 7-point Likert scale which requires respondents to assess flexibility levels in this business units.

Agility aids in reacting to operational changes within the firm and gives more flexibility in day-to-day operations (Dewangan *et al.*, 2020), allowing the firm to take advantage of market opportunities in the external business environment (Burke *et al.*, 2014). As more computational capabilities in IoT clusters become accessible, demand in delivering flexible and smart response will continue to develop fast (Zhong *et al.*, 2015). Five agility items are developed on 7-point Likert scale, which the respondents need to assess in their business units.

The perception, type, and utility of information communicated, as well as the ability of enterprises to act on that information, are all factors in determining visibility in manufacturing firms. Adopting IoT technologies inside SCM can provide transparency and information visibility throughout the supply chain (Haddud *et al.*, 2017). Visibility allows for improved management of distant supply chain operations and greater interaction with partners for product information, as well as more exact information for effective financial decision making (Haddud *et al.*, 2017; Büyüközkan *et al.*, 2018; Dekkers *et al.*, 2019; Fosso Wamba *et al.*, 2019). Firms need a flawless end-to-end information flow that is available in real-time and visible to all parties in a manufacturing organisation in order to offer goods and services to their customers. Due to a lack of data access, businesses are unable to gain visibility into their production processes, causing significant delays in achieving their goals of improving customer service and raising firm performance. Five constructs related to visibility are developed on a 7-point Likert scale and the respondents are required to assess the visibility levels of their business units.

Firms' DDIPCs are their skills to detect opportunities, capitalise on them, and modify their business model and wider resource base. Firms must use the links between DDIPCs and IoT to quickly build, deploy, and modify business models to stay relevant in the emerging digital economy, according to reports (Gia *et al.*, 2015; Akhtar *et al.*, 2018; Warner *et al.*, 2019). It is one of a firm's essential competencies for processing and generating information from massive volumes of data generated by the use of IoT in businesses. Firms with DDIPCs can not only collect useful data, but they can also store vital datasets that can provide actionable insights to improve their performance. Five items are developed on a 7-point Likert scale, the levels of which the respondents are required to assess on their business units.

The ability of a company to use its range of operational skills is referred to as its operational performance (Braojos *et al.*, 2019; Benitez *et al.*, 2020). This capability is at the heart of any company's business model, which includes features like gross margin, employee productivity, operational talent management, and operational excellence (Makhdoom *et al.*, 2019). Firms aspire to boost their financial performance by maximising profitability and increasing sales revenue by enhancing their business processes (Lee *et al.*, 2020; De Mendonca *et al.*, 2018). Five items are developed on a 7-point Likert scale. The respondents are required to assess the extent of operational performance of their business units.

Firms hope to boost sales revenue and retain business sustainability by optimising their business processes, hence improving their financial performance. It is a measure of how well a company achieves its financial goals (Randall *et al.*, 2009). It determines how well a business earns money and manages its assets, obligations, and stakeholders' financial interests (Nagy *et al.*, 2018). Five items are developed on a 7-point Likert scale. Respondents are required to assess the extent of financial performance of their business units. Appendix A provides the detailed questionnaire, including the constructs and questions included in the survey on each construct.

The validation of these constructs is explained in detail in Section 4.8.3.

4.8.2 Questionnaire Design

A 7-point Likert scale (strongly agree, agree, slightly agree, neutral, somewhat disagree, disagree, and strongly disagree) was used to determine whether respondents agreed or disagreed with a statement by placing a tick next to it. This size was designed to help with attenuation concerns caused by range constraints (Schreiber, 2017; Kwak *et al.*, 2018). The statements in the questions were kept short and simple so that respondents would be encouraged to finish the survey items without becoming confused.

The questionnaire is divided into three sections (Table 4.3). First Section A is intended to obtain specific demographic details about the profile of the company. Section B is an attempt to have demographic profile of the respondent. Section C comprises questions related to connectivity, flexibility and agility of IoT devices, followed by visibility and information flow within the firm, Use of IoT and its adoption in the firm, DDIPCs within the firm and how data is handled by the company operational performance in terms of cost, flexibility, innovation, quality and delivery, and finally, financial performance in terms of sales, return on investment, market value added and return on assets.

Table 4.3: Questionnaire Design

IoT Constructs		No. of Items	Question Number
Section A	Company profile		
Section B	Respondent Profile		
Section C	Connectivity of IoT	5	CIoT1, CIoT2, CIoT3, CIoT4, CIoT5
	Flexibility of IoT	5	FIoT1, FIoT2, FIoT3, FIoT4, FIoT5
	Agility of IoT	5	AIoT1, AIoT2, AIoT3, AIoT4, AIoT5
	Visibility of IoT	5	VIoT1, VIoT2, VIoT3, VIoT4, VIoT5
	Use of IoT	5	UIoT1, UIoT2, UIoT3, UIoT4, UIoT5
	DDIPCs	5	DDIPC1, DDIPC2, DDIPC3, DDIPC4, DDIPC5
	Operational Performance	5	OPerf1, OPerf2, OPerf3, OPerf4, OPerf5
	Financial Performance	5	FPerf1, FPerf2, FPerf3, FPerf4, FPerf5

4.8.3 Pilot Study

A pilot survey of eight professional practitioners (in manufacturing industry) and three academics (including supervisory team) was done to ensure that the constructs are clear and simple to understand. The questionnaire was revised based on the comments from the pilot study, and a final questionnaire was created.

The goal of the pilot study is to identify any potential flaws in the questionnaire's design and administration (Rowley, 2014; Schreiber, 2017). The questionnaire was piloted on eight practitioners in the manufacturing industry to ensure the highest level of reliability and validity. As a result of the pilot study, some changes to the questionnaire's wording and layout were made. To avoid misunderstanding and promote understanding of the items requested, leading and ambiguous questions were rephrased. Second, it appeared that several respondents were uncomfortable filling out the background section, thus topics relating to respondents' and firm's backgrounds were written out in Sections A and B. Although some respondents refused to submit information about their company or personal past, these questions were kept since they help to construct a picture of company differences. Third, aside from the company and personal profile, all other questionnaire items were gathered together under one area to ensure that respondents were at ease when completing their surveys.

Common-method variance was dealt by using guidelines provided by Garson, (2016) were followed, which involved avoiding unacquainted words, double barrelled questions and technical terms. In addition, Q-sort method was used to weigh the appropriateness of construct validity. The three academics were asked to undertake item placement ratios, which showed values of use of IoT = 100 percent; flexibility = 100 percent; connectivity = 95 percent; agility = 95 percent; DDIPCs = 100 percent; visibility = 100 percent and financial performance = 95 percent; exceeding the suggested threshold of 70 percent (Kwak *et al.*, 2018). This verified the constructs' validity in capturing the constructs' pre-specified factor components (Kwak *et al.*, 2018). As the above mentioned multiple processes proved content validity, no further analysis was believed to be needed for item clarification.

The pilot survey taught this study some valuable things. First, when the research objectives were conveyed to respondents in the manufacturing business, they were more receptive. Second, prior to the survey request, a personal comment to the respondents would boost the response rate. Third, if the survey information was not revealed, respondents were more likely to answer.

4.8.4 Non-response Bias

Because the sample is meant to reflect the total population, a high response rate is required to attain a high level of confidence and reduce bias in the data collected (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). Non-response can be explained by two factors: 1) respondents' failure to answer individual questions by leaving some blank; and 2) respondents' refusal to answer any of the questions without providing an explanation (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). The survey's validity is harmed if there is a large non-response rate.

Non-response bias arises when individuals who respond differ from those who do not in the result variable. The nature of the bias is also affected by the data collection method; for example, when using a postal survey, telephone, or even an interview, the non-response rate is significant (Hair *et al.*, 2017). For this study, experts and educated persons (high-skilled employees) are assumed to return the questionnaire at a respectable rate (Kotzab *et al.*, 2005). As a result, in order to eliminate bias, this study used an online-based questionnaire to collect data.

Furthermore, a high response rate was obtained based on the pilot study, in addition to high satisfaction with the questionnaire's length, clarity of wording, and layout. Non-response bias will be reduced as a result of this.

4.8.5 Methods to Achieve High Response Rate

According to Oliver *et al.*, (2010), a variety of factors can influence response rates, including refusal to answer questions owing to the questionnaire's length and the use of uninteresting or

sensitive topics. As a result, the procedures below were taken to improve the response rate and eliminate non-response bias:

- To allow respondents to focus on the questions, the questionnaire items were measured using a nominal or 7-point Likert scale.
- The wording was basic and straightforward, and open-ended questions were avoided.
- A cover letter outlining the study's objective and impact was provided to respondents prior to their participation in order to stimulate their involvement and interest in the study. This also demonstrated that their personal data would be kept private. The consent form and cover letter for the respondents can be found in Appendices B and C.
- Due to the model's complexity (40 components), the researcher made sure to construct a short and succinct questionnaire to avoid using any dull or uninteresting questions.

4.9 Data Analysis Techniques

Before testing hypotheses, the survey data was prepared for analysis by completing three key processes. A factor analysis and a reliability analysis were used to evaluate the constructs' validity. After that, descriptive analysis was used to describe the phenomena of interest. Calculating correlations revealed some preliminary links between the latent variables. Finally, SEM was used to test the hypotheses. The use of SEM as the primary data analysis technique in this study is briefly described and justified in this section.

4.9.1 Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

SEM is a statistical technique in which measurement models (confirmatory factor analysis) and structural models (regression analysis) are combined into a single statistical test (Hair *et al.*, 2017). It is a collection of approaches that are similar and have some qualities in common. A researcher considers a model that includes some structural variables, and then uses co-variances of observed data to test hypotheses about these variables (Hair *et al.*, 2017). Spearman invented this technique in 1904, and it is currently widely employed in a variety of research fields. SEM

allows the researcher to employ many measurements to describe constructs and solves the issue of measure-specific error, which is not addressed in other linear models where variables may only be represented by one measure and measurement error is not handled (Hox, 1999; Weston, 2006). SEM's importance stems from its capacity to examine hypotheses that are difficult to evaluate using other approaches (Schreiber *et al.*, 2017). This is because SEM uses a framework that includes numerous conventional statistical approaches, such as combining factor analysis and structural equation modelling to examine complicated connected variable dependence (Weston, 2006; Schreiber *et al.*, 2017). Another advantage of using SEM is that many statistical softwares are available making SEM very easy to specify and estimate (Pallant, 2007).

As defined by Goodboy *et al.*, (2017), SEM entails typical statistical procedures such as regression analysis, simultaneous equations, factor analysis, or ANOVA. Before employing SEM, a researcher should have a fundamental model in mind, according to Myers, (1990). The model might be as simple as indicating which factors may have an impact on others and in what direction. The model can then be tested using SEM, which may or may not be supported by the data. In this scenario, this technique can help the researcher increase the initial model's suitability without affecting its theoretical foundations (Hox, 1999; Schreiber *et al.*, 2017). As a result, this technique aims to comprehend the relationships between a group of variables. As a result of these benefits, a growing number of academics have recently begun to use SEM in their research (Hox, 1999; Vickery *et al.*, 2003; Weston, 2006; Tabachnik *et al.*, 2007; Hair *et al.*, 2010; Hair *et al.*, 2017; Akhtar *et al.*, 2018; Kwak *et al.*, 2018; Mital *et al.*, 2018). SEM is utilised as an analysis technique in this study because it allows for the assessment of casual associations between one or more independent variables and one or more dependent variables at the same time (Hair *et al.*, 2010; Schreiber *et al.*, 2017; Mikalef *et al.*, 2017). As this research aims to study the impact of the use of IoT devices and visibility (mediator) on firm performance using complexity, flexibility and agility of these devices, SEM technique is most suited to find the relationships between them, as moderated by DDIPCs.

As mentioned earlier, SEM allows for the testing of both measurement model as well as the structural model; hence providing in-depth knowledge on the relationships between variables

and indicators. A measurement model gives insight into the relationship between latent variables and their measures (or indicators). In this study, the latent variables are connectivity, flexibility, agility, use of IoT, visibility, DDIPCs, financial performance and operational performance; and their indicators are the question items designed to measure these variables (denoted by CIoT1, FIoT1, VIoT1 etc.). A structural model gives insight into the relationship between latent variables; for instance the relationship between connectivity and use of IoT is measured by structural model. Hence, SEM enables us to get insight into the depths of these relationships.

According to Hair *et al.*, (2010, p. 654), there are six steps in SEM:

1. Defining the constructs;
2. Creating the measurement model;
3. Designing a study to create empirical data;
4. Evaluating validity of the measurement model;
5. Specifying the structural model; and
6. Measuring validity of the structural model.

The first four steps are often covered by the measurement model, whereas the final two stages are typically covered by the structural model. In Chapters 5, 6, and 7, the application of the 6-stages in SEM techniques is extensively covered.

Figure 4.4 : SEM approaches used in this research (Hair *et al.*, 2006)

SEM is separated into two types: 1) covariance-based modelling, which is done with LISREL, Mplus, AMOS, and EQS software, and 2) variance-based modelling, which is done with partial least squares (PLS) software (Gefen *et al.*, 2000). Covariance-based SEM is useful when the

main purpose of the study is theory testing and confirmation, but PLS-SEM is more appropriate when the main goal of the research is prediction and theory building. In the current study, Analysis of Moment Structures, a covariance-based SEM approach is used to assess and analyse the data inside the proposed model (AMOS version 26.0). Hair *et al.*, (2017) recommendations for evaluating the structural model are followed in this study. The following two chapters provide a full explanation of how SEM was used in this study.

4.10 Ethical Considerations

Any research, but especially those aimed at studying participants' social behaviour, must take ethical considerations into account (Mittelstadt, 2017). For the current study, all participants were sent a consent form that stated their right to withdraw from the study at any time if they so desired, that their participation was voluntary, and that confidentiality and anonymity would be guaranteed at all stages of the research, all based on UWS guidelines for ethical considerations when collecting data. This approach was crucial for the research validity since it allowed participants to answer the questionnaire honestly. Other ethical considerations addressed in this study include the researcher's role following the data gathering technique, particularly throughout the data analysis stage (Sekaran, 2003).

All of the participants were also given a participant information letter. This letter included the title, purpose, and impact of the study, as well as the length and time of the questionnaire, as well as the contact information for the researcher and supervisor in case there were any further questions, as well as the contact information for the UWS ethical committee regarding the research's ethical aspects. Appendix B contains a copy of the consent form for the participant and Appendix C contains the participant information sheet. Before beginning the data gathering step, ethical approval from the Department of Computing, Engineering, and Physical Sciences at UWS was gained (see Appendix D).

4.11 Summary

The main goal of this chapter was to provide and justify the philosophical viewpoints, approaches, procedures, and statistical techniques that were used in this study to fulfil the main research goals. To explore and validate the conceptual framework, this study used a quantitative approach (Chapter 3). For this study, a survey strategy based on positivism was found to be the most appropriate. To collect data, a questionnaire was utilised, and a full overview of the many stages of questionnaire design, such as design, development, scale, and pilot study, was provided. Before generating a final version of the questionnaire, a two-stage pilot study was done, one with academics (expert knowledge) and the other with industrialists. A full description of sample size and other sampling procedures was also provided, as well as a justification for using the non-probability sampling technique. Furthermore, the rationale for using SEM as the primary data analysis technique in this study was presented. The two-step procedures in SEM analysis that will be used in this study to test and investigate the links between independent and dependent variables are CFA and the structural model. Finally, ethical concerns about this study were highlighted.

Chapter 5 Preliminary Data Analysis

5.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the preliminary data analysis of the data collected from the respondents in great detail. For preliminary data analysis, including data screening, frequencies and percentages, reliability analysis, exploratory factor analysis, and t-tests, the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0 was used. In this chapter, the outcomes of the data analysis are presented in relation to the use of IoT, visibility, and DDIPCs.

5.2 Data Screening

Preparing the data for consequent analysis is the first step in data analysis. It entails data entering, editing, and coding, all of which are necessary for transforming raw data into an effective form of analysis. The construct validity is next tested to ensure that the scale has fully apprehended the underlying and unobservable component it was designed to measure. Furthermore, content validity is assessed to determine the thoroughness with which each construct's domain is constructed and the appropriateness of the scale items reflecting all parts of the domain. Before data entry, all of the questions included in this survey were reviewed for missing data. Additionally, descriptive statistics were reviewed to confirm that the data was accurate. In this case, the answers to questions that yielded out-of-range values were compared to the original questionnaires for more accuracy.

5.3 Missing Data

Missing data, according to Hair *et al.*, (2017), is a significant issue in analysing data that might have an impact on the research goals and objectives. Missing data includes (1) responses in which answers to the survey questions are not provided at all by the respondent (for instance, answering only demographic questions but not actual survey questions); (2) responses in which some of the data is missing (for instance, answers to one or more of the survey questions are not provided); and (3) responses in which same response has been given to all the questions, also known as unengaged responses (for example, choosing answer 3 from the Likert scale for all the questions). When employing SEM with AMOS, the impact of missing data is significantly more critical. Chi-Square and other fit measures such as Goodness-of-Fit-Index and modification indices (refer to Chapter 6) cannot be computed if there are any missing data in the sample.

Missing data of up to 5%, according to Schreiber, (2017), is acceptable. Following an initial screening in SPSS 26.0, it was discovered that all missing data was distributed randomly and was below the 5% criterion. The largest percentage of data that was missing was 1.1. This value is very low, therefore, it can be deemed acceptable. As a result, the researcher used the 'mean substitution' method to substitute missing data for categorical variables, as many experts have recommended, e.g., (Bryman *et al.*, 2007; Pallant, 2007). However, rows 288 and 303 had no responses at all and were therefore removed from the data set. In addition, row 294 showed unengaged responses (the respondent gave the exact same response for every single item), and were removed from the data set. The final responses chosen for the analysis after sorting out the missing data and unengaged responses was 375. The frequency and percentage of missing data for the sample is presented in Tables F-1 in Appendix F.

5.4 Outliers

An outlier is described as "observations with a unique mix of attributes identified as distinctly different from the other observation," according to Hair *et al.*, (2006), p.73). As a result,

recognising and controlling outliers is crucial, as they might impair the data's normality and cause statistical tests to be skewed (Tabachnik *et al.*, 2007). In this case, Tabachnik *et al.*, (2007) recommend that extreme outliers be removed while mild outliers are retained. Hair *et al.*, (2006) proposed two approaches for detecting outliers: univariate and multivariate.

SPSS was utilised in this work to find univariate outliers in the data file by calculating z-score frequency distributions, as advised by Goodboy *et al.*, (2017). While there are no particular standards for identifying extreme values in the literature, a value of up to 3.29 can be allowed for a large sample (more than 80). The data set had no univariate variables. The results of the univariate outliers for the sample are presented in Table F-2 in Appendix F.

Multivariate outliers are another type of outlier; it involves observing and analysing multiple statistical outcome variables at the same time. The Mahalanobis D2 metric was utilised in this work to identify multivariate outliers (Goodboy *et al.*, 2017; Hair *et al.*, 2017). Mahalanobis D2 calculates the distance between a case's centroid and the centroid of the remaining cases. AMOS version 26.0 was used to measure Mahalanobis D2 in this study. All records with a p1 value less than 0.05 (significant on one side) are considered influential outliers, and the correlation between the variables for these responses is significantly different or abnormal when compared to the rest of the data (Tabachnik *et al.*, 2007). In the sample, there were twelve multivariate outliers, with cases 367-372 having the highest Mahalanobis D. However, the outliers in the dataset were maintained by the researcher because they were not considered to be troublesome due to their small quantity in comparison to the entire dataset and hence were eligible for further investigation (Hair *et al.*, 2017). Figure F1 in Appendix F shows the results of multivariate outliers for the sample.

5.5 Testing Normality Assumptions

The presence of normality must be tested in multivariate analysis, according to Hair *et al.*, (2017). In other words, if the data is not regularly distributed, the validity and trustworthiness of the results may be compromised.

The Jarque-Bera (skewness-Kurtosis) test was used in this investigation to determine if the data was normally distributed or not. The pattern of responses is termed a normal distribution when both skewness and kurtosis are zero (a circumstance that researchers are very unlikely to ever observe). A typical rule of thumb for skewness is that if the number is greater than +1 or lower than -1, the distribution is significantly skewed. The usual rule for kurtosis is that if it is larger than +2, the distribution is too peaked. Similarly, a kurtosis of less than -2 implies an excessively flat distribution (Hair *et al.*, 2010). Non-normal distributions have skewness and/or kurtosis that are greater than these limits.

Following this rule, all of the items in the sample dataset were discovered to be normally distributed. This meant that the values of skewness kurtosis were between +1 and -1, therefore were normally distributed. Same goes for kurtosis, as each value is between +2 and -2, it is considered to be significantly normally distributed. In addition, it can be seen in the graphs for each construct (see Appendix F) that the tail for skewness is neither distributed to the right nor to the left, showing a normal distribution. As for kurtosis, heavy tails have been identified for CIoT, FIoT, UIoT, DDIPC and FPerf, whereas light tails have been seen for AIoT, VIoT and OPerf. However, as the kurtosis values are between the cut-off values of +2 -2, they are considered to be acceptable. The skewness and kurtosis values for each variable are shown in Table F-3 in Appendix F.

5.6 Multi-collinearity

To find interrelated sets of variables, it's crucial to look for a required multi co-linearity. It is difficult to discern the distinct contribution to a factor of highly correlated variables.

1. The correlation matrix searches for low ($r < 0.3$) and high ($r > 0.9$) correlations. Extremely correlated variables (severe multi co-linearity) and perfectly correlated variables should be avoided.
2. There is no severe multi co-linearity in the data if the correlation coefficient values are less than 0.9 (Aguinis *et al.*, 2017) or less than 0.8.

3. If all of the questions in this study are reasonably well connected, and none of the correlation coefficients are excessively large, the researcher should not rule out any of them at this time.
4. The first evidence of significant co-linearity is a high correlation coefficient. Despite the lack of substantial correlation, the idea of co-linearity was not ruled out. Co-linearity can result from the interaction of two or more independent factors. As a result, tolerance and its inverse, the variance inflation factor (VIF), are the two most commonly used measures for evaluating data co-linearity in pairs and multiple variables.
5. The VIF determines whether one predictor has a strong linear regression association with another. There is no multi co-linearity if the VIF value matches the suggested value of VIF less than 10, and the average (sum of VIP divided by number of predictors) is less than 1 (Hair *et al.*, 2010). The tolerance (1/VIP) of each predictor should not be less than 0.1.

As the tolerance and variance inflation factor (VIF) data fulfilled the criteria, multi co-linearity appears to be non-existent. The VIF values ranged from 1.01 to 5.56 (10) and were backed up by tolerance values ranging from 0.18 to 0.94 (>0.10), showing that multi-co-linearity among independent variables was not a possibility. The results of multi-collinearity are shown in Table F.4 in Appendix F.

5.7 Reliability

The consistency with which a measurement equipment measures the idea is determined by its reliability analysis. Because it only requires one administration of a single measurement equipment, the internal consistency technique, which is the most basic kind of reliability estimation, is seen to be the most practical. Internal consistency, which is the degree of inter-correlation across items that assess the same idea, is used to define reliability in this study (Hair *et al.*, 2017).

Cronbach's alpha is widely regarded as a sufficient indicator of internal consistency and, consequently, reliability. The Cronbach's coefficient alpha is a recommended indicator of a set

of items' internal consistency (Sekaran, 2003). Cronbach's alpha threshold levels vary depending on the type of study; fresh, exploratory studies may have a lower level of 0.60 (Hair *et al.*, 2010), despite the usually accepted lower limit of 0.70.

The reliability tests of the main study were analysed using SPSS, as shown in Table 5.1. With a score range of 0.72 to 0.92, the results suggest that the constructs were reliable. This suggests that the items associated with each of the constructs in the proposed model were positively connected (Hair *et al.*, 2010).

Table 5.1: Cronbach's alpha for each item

Items	Cronbach's Alpha
CIoT	0.885
FIoT	0.728
AIoT	0.857
VIoT	0.838
UIoT	0.801
DDIPCs	0.921
FPerf	0.843
OPerf	0.899

5.8 Sample Profile

After cleaning the data, the researcher began to explore the nature of the variables. Here, the profile of the firms and respondents will be presented. Details of responses from the survey are presented in Appendix E.

5.8.1 Firm Profile

The responses of 375 manufacturing firms were analysed, as presented in Table 5.2 and Figure 5.1 which describe the sample characteristics (firm background). All participants are from manufacturing firms which provide full and integrated manufacturing services including logistics, inventory management, processing operations, assembly operations, material

handling and storage, and quality and control. The firms are almost equally represented in terms of organization size, 11.5 percent of firms have less than 50 employees, 13.3 percent of firms have 50 to 100 employees, 21.9 percent of firms have 101 to 200 employees, 32 percent of firms have 201 to 500 employees, and 21.3 percent of firms have more than 500 employees. In addition, majority of the companies have sales of around 50m-250m (26.13 and 26.67 percent respectively), whereas 10.4 percent companies have sales less than 50m, 24.27 percent have sales between 250m-500m and 12.53 percent have sales of more than 1b.

Table 5.2: Company profile

Company Profile			
		No.	Percent
Number of Employees	>50	43	11.5
	50-100	50	13.3
	101-200	82	21.9
	201-500	120	32.0
	More than 500	80	21.3
	Total	375	
Sales	< £50m	39	10.40
	£50m - £100m	98	26.13
	£100m - £250m	100	26.67
	£250m - £500m	91	24.27
	More than £1b	47	12.53

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.1: Company profile; (a) number of employees; and (b) sales of the companies

5.8.2 Respondent Profile

Table 5.3 and Figure 5.2 describes the respondent profile. Out of the 375 respondents (two respondents not indicated), 44.62 percent of respondents are from a top management positions and 31.45 percent represent middle management, since they were called before the visits, while 23.7 percent are representative of either managers or supervisors. The number of years stayed

in the company varies too. 1.61 percent respondents have worked less than a year in the company, 15.7 percent have worked 1-5 years, 42.13 percent have worked for 5-8 years, 32.53 percent have worked for 8-10 years and 8 percent have worked in the company for more than 10 years. It can be seen here that generally the respondents are managers with good skills and training.

Table 5.3: Respondent profile

Respondent Profile			
		No.	Percent
Title	Supervisor	89	23.73
	IT manager	120	32.00
	Director	109	29.07
	Owner	45	12.00
	Vice President	12	3.20
	Total	375	
Years in Company	<1	6	1.60
	1-5	59	15.73
	5-8	158	42.13
	8-10	122	32.53
	More than 10	30	8.00
	Total	375	

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.2: Respondent profile; (a) respondent title; and (b) employment years

5.8.3 Exploratory Factor Analysis

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is used since this research is regarded ground-breaking in the area of IoT research. EFA aids in the understanding of the structure of a group of variables (latent variables) and the reduction of data while maintaining as much original information as

feasible (Memon *et al.*, 2017). EFA employs all reflective latent (multi-indicator) variables rather than formative, categorical, or demographic measures such as gender, age, and so on.

All of the constructs in this study are factored to get the underlying information regarding their content and construct validity. This comprises the 40 items used to assess the impact of IoT on firm performance. Factor analysis is a statistical technique for determining natural groupings of items (variables that measure comparable things) from a huge correlation matrix expressed as dimensions or factors (Memon *et al.*, 2017).

After screening, EFA is used to determine the data's reliability and validity. SPSS 26 is used to carry out this procedure. To carry out the EFA, the following measures were taken.

5.8.3.1 Factor Extraction

Because it is less forgiving, EFA with promax rotation is used to simplify factor interpretation (Field, 2009). The original solution is extracted using the maximum likelihood approach (ML) to extract sequential factors, which are then rotated and factor loaded to improve interpretability by reducing the vast number of variables to a manageable number of scales. The reason for using ML is because it maximises the differences between two factors and offers a model fit estimate, which is useful for running confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) (Gaskin *et al.*, 2014). To obtain a clear pattern of loading, a rotational method is used. The EFA with promax rotation is used to identify the variables that will be measured.

5.8.3.2 Appropriateness of Data

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) method is used to determine whether the sample size is sufficient for factor analysis (Gaskin *et al.*, 2014). The KMO index runs from 0 to 1, with 0.6 being mediocre and 0.9 being excellent for EFA execution. Table 5.4 depicts the KMO data that ranges from low to excellent, as recommended by Hair *et al.*, (2010) and Lowry *et al.*, (2014).

Table 5.4: KMO statistics

Data range	KMO values
Excellent	0.9
Meritorious	0.8
Moderate	0.7
Average	0.6
Miserable	0.5
Unacceptable	<0.3

Both the KMO and Barlett's tests of sphericity were used to assess the data's suitability for this study. The KMO results for both the initial and amended EFA are shown in Table 5.5. (after deleting the cross-loaded items). The KMO value of 0.9 is obvious, however the Barlett's test yields a significant result (sig. 0.05), showing that the matrix is not an identity matrix and that the variables are sufficiently related to conduct a meaningful EFA.

5.8.3.3 Number of Factors

The number of components to keep could be determined by data screen plots or eigenvalues greater than one. The point of inflexion of this curve (where the slope of the line increases considerably) should be the cut-off point for picking factors (Latan *et al.*, 2017). The eigenvalues indicate how much variation is explained by a factor (variances extracted by the factor). A large degree of variation is represented by an eigenvalue of one (Martínez-López *et al.*, 2013). All factors with eigenvalues equal to or greater than 1 were retained in this study using Kaiser's criterion.

Table 5.5: KMO results for initial EFA

		Initial	Revised
KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.915	0.900
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	10869.647	8297.037
	df	780	528
	Sig.	0.000	0.000

5.8.3.4 Communalities

The amount to which a thing connects with all other items is referred to as communality. The higher the communality, the better (Gaskin *et al.*, 2014). If a variable's communalities are low (between 0.0 and 0.3), that variable may fail to load significantly on any component. After evaluating the pattern matrix, low values indicate candidates for elimination. The initial EFA revealed that some of the components, such as UIoT5, had lower extraction values (0.26). Cross-loadings in significant factors arose as a result of this. Other factors had extraction values ranging from 0.39 to 0.88, which were considerably high. The initial and amended communalities of the items under consideration in Appendix F are shown in Table F-5.

5.8.3.5 Factor Loading

If the elements match these conditions, the factor solution is called stable. Significant item loading is greater than 0.3. (Hair *et al.*, 2010; Hair *et al.*, 2017). Items with a loading of less than 0.3 and items with a loading of greater than 0.3 on two or more criteria will be deleted by the researcher (cross loading). The significant factor loading will be determined by the sample size once again. For substantial factor loading, Hair *et al.* (2017) advised the following sample size (Table 5.6):

Table 5.6: Significant factor loading and sample size

Sample size	Significant factor loading
50	0.722
100	> 0.512
200	>0.364
300	>0.298
600	>0.21
1000	>0.162

Table 5.7: EFA results with factor loadings

Pattern Matrix								
	Factor							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
CIoT1		0.678						
CIoT2		0.943						
CIoT3		0.767						
CIoT4		0.677						
CIoT5		0.771						
FIoT3							0.744	
FIoT4							0.769	
FIoT5							0.673	
AIoT2				0.758				
AIoT3				0.865				
AIoT4				0.928				
AIoT5				0.868				
VIoT2			0.752					
VIoT3			0.803					
VIoT4			0.967					
VIoT5			0.966					
UIoT3								0.759
UIoT4								0.866
UIoT5								0.492
DDIPC1	0.714							
DDIPC2	0.771							
DDIPC3	0.847							
DDIPC4	0.884							
DDIPC5	0.955							
FPerf1						0.702		
FPerf2						0.789		
Fperf3						0.732		
FPerf4						0.685		
FPerf5						0.461		
OPerf2					0.848			

OPerf3					0.935			
OPerf4					0.710			
OPerf5					0.677			

The next step is to look at the constructs that load onto the same factor to see if there are any similar themes that are relevant to IoT and firm performance. The researcher can use highly loaded questions to figure out what the construct is. Table E-6 in Appendix F shows the initial results of the factor analysis. It can be seen that some of the items were cross-loaded on other factors, indicating high inter-correlations among variables being tested in EFA. Centred on the outcome of the factor loadings, there were no changes made in connectivity, DDIPCs and Fperf items because their corresponding items factor loadings and communalities are greater than 0.3. For flexibility, FIoT1 and FIoT2 were removed for revised EFA as they showed cross-loadings on connectivity although their communalities were greater than 0.4. Similarly, for agility, AIoT1 was dropped due to cross-loading on flexibility. For visibility, VIoT1 was removed as it loaded on agility. UIoT1 and UIoT2 were dropped for Use of IoT, although they had high communalities (0.7 and 0.5 respectively), however due to cross-loadings they were considered best to be removed from the EFA. UIoT5 had low communality (0.2) but its factor loading is 0.5 which is greater than cutoff value 0.3 (Akhtar *et al.*, 2018) and the contents are important to the construct. Therefore, it was retained for the CFA. Similarly, OPerf1 for OPerf was removed due to cross-loading on FPerf. Table 5.7 shows the revised factor loadings used for the EFA.

5.9 Summary

This chapter summarised the results of the preliminary analysis performed with SPSS 26. The many statistical procedures discussed in this chapter aided the researcher in examining the dataset's results. Missing data, unengaged replies, outliers, testing normal distribution of the data through skewness and kurtosis, and multi-collinearity were all discussed in this chapter. The results showed that the sample had a normal distribution and that the missing data was less

than 5%. The highest and lowest percentages of missing data were 1.1 and 0.8, respectively, which is low and considered acceptable. As a result, the mean substitution method was used to replace the missing data. There were no univariate outliers, but cases 362-372 had a lot of multivariate outliers, according to the Mahalanobis distance. Nonetheless, the researcher kept these cases because they didn't pose any issues and could be analysed further. The values of skewness and kurtosis in each case were in the range of 1, which is acceptable because there were no difficulties with data normality. Finally, the VIF and tolerance values indicated that the sample was free of multi-collinearity concerns.

The next part included information about the company's demographics and respondent profiles, such as the number of employees, sales, respondent title, and years spent at the company. The majority of responding companies had 201-500 people and sales of £50m-£250m, according to the findings. Furthermore, the bulk of the respondents were managers or high-ranking employees with 5-8 years of experience working for their respective firms.

The next section showed the results of EFA, including KMO statistics, communalities and factor loadings. This helped the researcher to ensure the convergent and discriminant validity of the dataset; and prepare the data for CFA. Some items showed heavy cross-loadings on other factors, which were removed from further analysis (FIoT1, FIoT2, AIoT1, VIoT1, UIOT1, UIoT2 and OPerf1). The chapter ended with a clear pattern matrix showing separate loadings of constructs on respective factors were presented.

The next chapter will provide further analysis using SEM to observe the construct and convergent validity and to test the relationships between independent and dependent variables. The results will be discussed against hypotheses.

Chapter 6 Model Testing

6.1 Introduction

The preliminary data analysis was reported in the previous chapter. This chapter will give an in-depth investigation of the links between the constructs in the proposed research model. During the analysis, two steps were taken to accomplish this. CFA was used in the first step to examine the constructs' validity and model fit. The SEM approach was used in the second step to investigate the hypothesised relations between variables. This allowed the researcher to ensure that only the survey constructs with good validity and reliability measurements would be employed in the structural measurement model (Hair *et al.*, 2010; Lowry *et al.*, 2014).

This chapter is organised as follows: the first section will assess the measures, including the constructs' validity and reliability. The next section will examine the direct links between the updated measurement model's constructs. The criteria and methods used to assess the impact of DDIPC moderation are described in the next section. The results of the mediating impact of visibility on firm performance will next be presented. Finally, there will be a summary of the findings.

6.2 Measurement Model

Validity and reliability measurement devices are critical because they determine whether or not significant scientific conclusions are legitimate. The ability of an instrument to measure the intended idea it claims to measure is referred to as its validity. The consistency of instruments of a latent construct is reflected in reliability (Hair *et al.*, 2010). To put it another way, valid constructs produce consistent measurement results throughout time. As a result, a construct cannot be valid if it is not reliable, but it might be reliable even if it is not valid. (Henseler, 2017).

Content validity, convergent validity, and discriminant validity are examples of validity measurements (Henseler *et al.*, 2017). The degree of agreement among scholars and practitioners on whether the measurement items cover the area of the construct is referred to as content validity (Hair *et al.*, 2010; Gaskin *et al.*, 2014). Three techniques for examining content validity are a comprehensive literature review, expert judge evaluation of measuring items, and a pilot study or Q-sort procedure (Seddon *et al.*, 2012). To ensure the content validity of the instruments, this study used a complete literature analysis and a pilot study.

The amount to which indicators of one construct come together to establish a single common dimension is known as convergent validity (Hair *et al.*, 2017). This metric indicates how well measurement items accurately represent the latent construct they are supposed to measure. When the measurement items' standardised factor loadings on their linked constructs are larger than twice their standard errors and statistically significant, convergent validity is regarded satisfactory (Heeler *et al.*, 1972; Henseler *et al.*, 2017).

The degree to which the indicators constitute a distinct construct that is independent of the others is known as discriminant validity (Henseler *et al.*, 2017). The typical measure for discriminant validity is average variance extracted (AVE). AVE explains the average extent of variance in indicators that a construct is able to explain (Hair *et al.*, 2017). Discriminant validity can be tested in two ways: first, if the AVE value of a construct is greater than the squared correlation between that construct and others in the model, discriminant validity can be assessed. Second, if the square root of one construct's AVE is greater than the correlations of that construct with all other constructs, discriminant validity is proven (Hair *et al.*, 2017).

The degree to which a construct can provide the same results in multiple efforts is known as reliability. For each first order construct, Cronbach's alpha is presented as a measure of reliability. Cronbach's alpha reliability criteria is > 0.70 in this study (see Chapter 5). Although Cronbach's alpha is widely recognised to be between 0.70 and 0.80 in confirmatory research (Gaskin *et al.*, 2014), others argue that values greater than 0.60 are acceptable for newly produced scales like the ones evaluated here (Leung, 2011).

The validity of the first order measurement models is investigated in this work using AMOS 26 confirmatory procedures. The fit of the sample data to the postulated model is estimated using model fit statistics. The validity of a measurement model is determined by its goodness of fit (Hair *et al.*, 2017). The goodness of fit (GFI), adjusted goodness of fit (AGFI), and root mean square residual (RMR) indices are commonly provided by first order measurement models (Liao *et al.*, 2002; Hair *et al.*, 2006). GFI scores greater than 0.80 (ideally > 0.90) and AGFI greater than 0.80 are generally considered appropriate (Hair *et al.*, 2010). The SRMR (standardised root mean square residual) is an error fit indicator, with lower values indicating model adequacy. SRMR values below 0.05 indicate a decent match, while values below 0.08 indicate acceptable approximation errors (Hair *et al.*, 2017). A result of 0.08 for the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) indicates a good fit (Schreiber, 2017). The comparative fit index (CFI) is a set of model fit indices whose values are more than 0.90, indicating good model fit (Hair *et al.*, 2010). The criteria for numerous fit indices utilised in this investigation are shown in Table 6.1, as adapted from (Schreiber *et al.*, 2017).

Table 6.1: Criteria for different fit indices used for the study

Indices	Abbreviation	Acceptance rule
Absolute/Predictive fit		
Chi-square	χ^2	Ratio of χ^2 to $df^* \leq 2$ or 3, useful for nested models or model trimming
Comparative fit		
Incremental fit index	IFI	≥ 0.95 for acceptance
Comparative fit index	CFI	≥ 0.95 for acceptance
Other		
Root mean square residual	RMR	Smaller the better, 0 indicates perfect fit
Standardised RMR	SRMR	≤ 0.08
Root mean square error of approximation	RMSEA	< 0.06 to 0.08 with confidence interval

* df – degrees of freedom, the number of independent pieces of information that went into calculating the estimate.

6.2.1 CFA Measurement Model Analysis and Results

The measurement model was examined with IBM SPSS AMOS 26 and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was used to test validity, reliability, and model fit. The software was loaded with all of the items that had survived the EFA. In this study, six first-order components, one mediator, and one moderator were discovered. To evaluate the measurement model in CFA, the goodness of fit was examined first, followed by the model's validity.

It is not necessary to discriminate between endogenous and exogenous constructs in the CFA, but it is required during the model testing step (Hair *et al.*, 2017). All of the variables are linked together in Figure 6.1, and the construct items (measured variables) are depicted as rectangular shapes. A causal relationship from a construct to an indicator is usually shown by a one-headed arrow, whereas covariance is usually represented by two-headed arrows. The researcher worked on each sample separately in order to create a model that best fit each sample in the current study. In total, 33 components generated from the EFA were employed in the CFA (as discussed in Chapter 5).

6.2.1.1 Goodness of Fit

The fit indices as mentioned in Section 6.2 were adopted in this study. A good model fit was revealed at $\chi^2 = 812.6$ at $df = 467$. The model fit indices were $\chi^2/df = 1.74$; CFI = 0.95; IFI = 0.95; RMSEA = 0.04; RMR = 0.02 and SRMR = 0.03. These figures indicated a good fit for the model. In AMOS, the modification indices show how much the model fit has improved. The following steps can be taken to improve the model's fit:

- The standardised residual covariance should be less than or equal to $|2.58|$ (Bryman *et al.*, 2007).
- Factor loading (Standardised regression weight) should be larger than 0.5 and ideally greater than 0.7 (Bryman *et al.*, 2007).

Modification indices (MI) with a very high covariance and likewise high regression weights should be removed (Hair *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 6.1: Hypothesized measurement model

However, as the model fit indices met the criteria, none of the above mentioned measures were applied. In addition, the criteria of convergent validity was met as the standardised factor loadings were above 0.6 except for UIoT5 (0.51). This suggested removing this item would improve the model fit. The consequential model had no subsequent impact on the model fit indices except that χ^2 and df showed a decrease in value ($\chi^2 = 781.4$ and $df = 436$). The model

fit indices statistics were as follows: $\chi^2/df = 1.79$; CFI = 0.95; IFI = 0.95; RMSEA = 0.04; RMR = 0.02 and SRMR = 0.03. Therefore, it was decided to retain UIoT5 following the argument of (Gaskin *et al.*, 2014). The criteria for discriminant validity were also met as the correlations were less than 0.8. Table 6.2 shows a summary of the model fit indices. Figure 6.2 shows the standardised estimates of the measurement model.

Table 6.2: Summary of fit indices for measurement model

Indices	Estimate	Interpretation
χ^2/df	1.74	Excellent
CFI	0.957	Excellent
IFI	0.957	Excellent
RMR	0.026	Excellent
RMSEA	0.044	Excellent
SRMR	0.038	Excellent

6.2.1.2 Construct Validity and Reliability

Examining the validity and reliability of the measurements is a necessary step before testing the hypotheses in the suggested conceptual model, as this may affect the results and hence the study goal (Hair *et al.*, 2017). Despite the fact that these two tests are distinct, they are closely related (Gummesson, 2000). As mentioned earlier, a measure can have high reliability (consistency) but not be valid (accurate), and a measure can have high validity (accuracy) but not be reliable, according to (Holmbeck, 1997).

Validity and reliability can be determined using the following methods:

- **Composite Reliability (CR):** Similar to Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability (also known as construct reliability) is a measure of internal consistency in scale components (Hair *et al.*, 2017). It is equivalent to the whole amount of real score variance divided by the total scale score variance. The cut-off value of CR, as agreed by different scholars, is accepted to be above 0.70 (Gummesson, 2000; Hair *et al.*, 2017).

-
- Average Variance Extracted (AVE): This shows the average extent of variance in indicators that a construct is able to explain (Hair *et al.*, 2017). Validity is established when AVE is greater than 0.5 and CR is greater than AVE.
 - Maximum Shared Squared Variance (MSV): It is the square of the highest correlation coefficient between latent constructs. For example, if the correlation between latent constructs A and B = 0.40, A and C = 0.50, A and D = 0.30 - the highest correlation coefficient here is 0.50, in that case, MSV for the latent construct A = $0.50^2 = 0.25$. Validity is established when MSV is less than AVE.
 - MaxR(H): Also called maximum reliability, has the aim to achieve reliability to a maximum value. A measure has high reliability if it produces similar results under consistent conditions. Value of MaxR(H) equal to or higher than 0.70 show good reliability statistics (Hair *et al.*, 2006), with values greater than 0.9 as excellent reliability.

AMOS, on the other hand, does not automatically compute the AVE and CR for each construct. Therefore, following two formulas were used by the researcher:

Figure 6.2: Full measurement model with path coefficients

1. The AVE can be calculated using the following formula, according to Fornell C & Larcker F D, (1981):

$AVE = \frac{\text{(summation of squared factor loadings)}}{\text{(summation of squared factor loadings) + \text{(summation of error variances)}}$

$$AVE = \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i^2)}{n} \tag{6.1}$$

λ represents factor loadings (standardised regression weights);

i represents the total number of items.

2. CR can be measured using the following formula (Leung, 2011):

CR = (square of summation of factor loadings) / (square of summation of factor loadings) + (summation of error variances).

$$CR = \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i)^2}{(\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i)^2 + (\sum_{i=1}^n \delta_i)} \quad (6.2)$$

λ represents factor loadings (standardised regression weights);

i represents the total number of items;

δ_i represents the error variance term for each latent construct.

Convergent validity was confirmed in the model, as shown by AVEs all above 0.5 (Table 6.3). Furthermore, the factors were reliable, as evidenced by CR values all above 0.7. In addition, discriminant validity was demonstrated by the fact that all values of MSV were less than AVE. Maximum reliability was evidenced by having all the values of MaxR(H) above 0.7, indicating good reliability statistics for the constructs. The factor correlation matrix with square root of the AVE on the diagonal can be seen in the table (highlighted in blue). Discriminate validity is evidenced as the square root of AVE values are greater than any co-factor correlation. For instance, square root of AVE for FIoT in Table 6.3 is 0.731, which is greater than any correlation values within the same column. As a result, the measurement model was finalised to test the hypothesis because there were no issues with validity or reliability. The validity and reliability statistics are shown in Table 6.3.

Table 6.3: Validity and reliability statistics for measurement model

	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	FIOT	DDIPC	CIOT	VIOT	AIOT	OPERF	FPERF	UIOT
FIOT	0.774	0.534	0.176	0.780	0.731							
DDIPC	0.926	0.715	0.276	0.931	0.289	0.845						
CIOT	0.884	0.606	0.276	0.897	0.384	0.525	0.778					
VIOT	0.938	0.792	0.328	0.949	0.282	0.470	0.365	0.890				
AIOT	0.920	0.742	0.176	0.925	0.420	0.222	0.405	0.250	0.862			
OPERF	0.896	0.685	0.526	0.908	0.127	0.370	0.284	0.552	0.248	0.827		
FPERF	0.849	0.532	0.526	0.857	0.248	0.524	0.425	0.573	0.247	0.725	0.729	
UIOT	0.759	0.521	0.014	0.806	0.014	0.117	0.108	0.117	0.002	0.046	0.085	0.722

6.2.1.3 Common Method Bias

Although surveys are the most widely used methodologies in the social sciences, they can be vulnerable to common method bias (CMB), which can compromise the validity and reliability of empirical findings (Kock *et al.*, 2021). First, when the systematic error variance is not adjusted for, it might be added to the trait variance in the measured construct, thus leading to incorrect conclusions about the scale's reliability. Second, common method bias may have an impact on parameter estimates for hypothesised relationships between constructs, such as correlation. As a result, it's critical to conduct a CMB before moving on to the structural model.

The CMB test was conducted out in this work using a common latent factor (CLF), where an unconstrained common method factor model was compared to a fully (zero) restricted common method factor model, and it was shown to be negligible in the Chi-square test (Table 6.4). The p-value is significantly greater than 0.05, indicating that there is no significant difference between the two models. This means that no common method bias was found in this study. As a result, there was no commonality among the circumstances that led us to depart CLF. Then, for additional analysis, factor imputation was used.

Table 6.4: Chi-square test result for measurement model

	<u>Chi-square</u>	<u>df</u>	<u>p-val</u>	<u>Invariant?</u>
Overall Model				
Unconstrained	795.4	436		
Fully constrained	812.6	467		
Difference	17.2	31	0.979	YES

6.3 Structural Model

The conceptual relationship of the constructs was evaluated by studying the paths in the structural model after analysing the measurement model in the previous section. The following sections will show the results of the structural model testing.

6.3.1 First Run

In order to test the hypotheses, the initial model was run for goodness of fit. The results of the fit indices for the first run were as follows: $\chi^2/df = 32.614$; RMR = 0.07; CFI = 0.641; IFI = 0.646; RMSEA = 0.291 and SRMR = 0.203. As evident from these figures, the model did not show a good fit and the indices were substantially worse than the measurement model. The covariance estimates in the modification indices in AMOS output showed if the analysis is repeated treating the co-variance between error terms e1 and e2 as a free parameter, its value will become larger by approximately 168.66 than it is in the present analysis. The regression weights showed that if the analysis is repeated treating the regression weight for using CIoT to predict DDIPC as a free parameter, the discrepancy will fall by at least 115.60. Similarly, it was revealed that analysis repeated if regression weights of FIoT and AIoT were treated as free parameter to predict DDIPC, the discrepancy will fall by 41.72 and 21.68 respectively. This meant that FIoT, CIoT and AIoT shared variances with DDIPC. Therefore, in order to get a good model for testing hypotheses, the researcher chose to draw variance lines from FIoT, CIoT and AIoT towards DDIPC to get a good model fit. The results of the first run for model fit are shown in Tables G.1, G.2 and G.3; and Figure G.1 in Appendix G.

6.3.2 Second Run

The fit indices results of the second run were as follows: $\chi^2/df = 5.89$; RMR = 0.023; CFI = 0.962; IFI = 0.962; RMSEA = 0.114 and SRMR = 0.151. The indices showed good fit except for the low CMIN/df value and high SRMR index. The results of the first run for model fit are shown in Tables G.4 and G.5 and Figure G.2 in Appendix G.

6.3.3 Third Run

To get a good value of SRMR, the modification indices were checked, revealing that if regression weights of CIoT, AIoT and FIoT were treated as free parameters to predict VIoT, the discrepancy will fall by 5.78, 11.10 and 12.46 respectively. By drawing variance lines between these factors and re-run the model for goodness of fit, excellent indices were found ($\chi^2/df = 3.38$; RMR = 0.009; CFI = 0.99; IFI = 0.99; RMSEA = 0.08 and SRMR = 0.02). Therefore, the researcher chose to third model to test for hypotheses. The detailed results of the second run are included in Tables G.4 and G.5 in Appendix G. Table 6.5 shows the final results of the goodness of fit indices for the chosen structural model. Thus, we proceeded to examine the hypothesised relationships within the model. Table 6.6 depicts the path coefficients for the hypothesised relationships within the proposed research model.

Table 6.5: Final results of goodness of fit for structural model

Indices	Estimate	Interpretation
χ^2/df	3.388	Acceptable
CFI	0.99	Excellent
IFI	0.99	Excellent
RMR	0.009	Excellent
RMSEA	0.08	Excellent
SRMR	0.022	Excellent

Table 6.6: Path coefficients for hypothesized relationships

Hypothesis	Standardised co-efficient		Remark
	Direct effect	Indirect effect	
Independent effects:			
H1a: CIoT → UIoT	0.16**		Supported
H1b: FIoT → UIoT	-0.025*		Not Supported
H1c: AIoT → UIoT	-0.055**		Not Supported
H2a: UIoT → FPerf	-0.027**		Not Supported
H2b: UIoT → OPerf	-0.034**		Not Supported
Mediation effects:			
H3a: UIoT → VIoT → FPerf		0.064**	Supported
H3b: UIoT → VIoT → OPerf		0.081*	Supported
Moderation effects:			
H5a: UIoT x DDIPC → FPerf	0.005*		Supported
H5b: UIoT x DDIPC → OPerf	0.033***		Supported
H6a: VIoT x DDIPC → FPerf	0.033***		Supported
H6b: VIoT x DDIPC → OPerf	0.012**		Supported

Notes: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$

As seen from Table 6.6, CIoT ($\beta = 0.16^{**}$) was found to have a weak positive impact on UIoT, supporting H1a. Whereas, FIoT ($\beta = -0.025$) and AIoT ($\beta = -0.055$) showed a negative influence on UIoT, rejecting H1b and H1c. In addition, it was found that UIoT had no direct impact on FPerf and OPerf showing negative standardised co-efficient values of -0.027 and -0.034 respectively. This led to the rejection of H2a and H2b. Furthermore, the indirect effects revealed a positive impact of VIoT when mediating between UIoT and FPerf ($\beta = 0.064$), hence supporting H3a. Similarly, the indirect effect of VIoT showed a significant positive impact when mediating between UIoT and OPerf ($\beta = 0.081$), accepting H3b. The direct moderating effects of UIoT x DDIPC on FPerf indicated that DDIPC dampens the negative relationship between UIoT and FPerf at $\beta = 0.005$, accepting H5a. Similarly, the moderating effect of UIoT x DDIPC on OPerf showed that DDIPC dampens the negative relationship between UIoT and

OPerf by $\beta = 0.033$, supporting H5b. Furthermore, the moderating effect of VIoT x DDIPC on FPerf indicated that DDIPC strengthens the positive relationship between VIoT and FPerf by $\beta = 0.033$, accepting H6a. Similarly, the moderating effect of VIoT x DDIPC on Operf showed that DDIPC strengthens the positive relationship between VIoT and Operf by $\beta = 0.012$, supporting H6b.

6.4 Mediation Effect

This study used a mediation model to demonstrate the link between UIoT, VIoT, and firm performance. Mediation analysis reveals how and why an independent variable and a dependent variable are linked (Sarstedt *et al.*, 2021). In the study, as shown in Figure 6.3, the mediating variable, M, is hypothesised to interfere in the association between the independent variable, X, and the dependent variable, Y.

The influence of the independent variable, X, on the mediating variable, M, is indicated by the path a. The influence of the mediating variable, M, on the dependent variable, Y, is indicated by the path b. Without a mediator, the path c represents the whole effect of the independent variable, X, on the dependent variable, Y. The path c' denotes the direct effect of the independent variable, X, on the dependent variable, Y, in the presence of a mediator, M. The product of path coefficients a and b is the indirect effect. The difference between the total effect and the direct effect is the indirect effect. It is written as $a * b = c - c'$ in mathematics. (Figure 6.3).

Figure 6.3: Direct and indirect effects in mediation

Hayes *et al.*, (2013) bootstrapping approach is used to see if any variable, M, mediates the relationship between independent variable, X, and dependent variable, Y. It is a non-parametric test that does not break the normality assumptions. As a result, this test is also suggested for tiny sizes. Bootstrapping is a resampling method in which a sample is selected from the data set periodically in order to calculate the desired statistical conclusion. The bootstrapping technique was used to determine indirect, total, and direct effects using Hayes' SPSS process macros. The resulting data is tabulated and graphically represented for further examination in the following topics.

The model's mediation effects were investigated using AMOS 26's 'user-defined estimand' (Gaskin *et al.*, 2014). To assess the implications of these indirect effects, the variables were bootstrapped. For 2000 bootstrapped samples with a 90% confidence interval, the unstandardized indirect effects were calculated (Gaskin *et al.*, 2014; Hair *et al.*, 2017). The results showed that UIoT had a significant effect on the dependent variable FPerf, with a value of 0.02 at $p < 0.05$. Furthermore, VIoT was shown to have a significant effect on FPerf, with a

value of 0.62 and a p value of 0.05. This demonstrated that VIoT mediated the link between UIoT and FPerf in a considerable way (Figure 6.4). In addition, the results showed that UIoT ($\beta = -0.02$ at $p < 0.05$) had no direct effect on OPerf; however, VIoT ($\beta = 0.59$ at $p < 0.01$) significantly mediated this relationship. Table 6.7 shows the results of the mediation effects.

Figure 6.4: Mediation path coefficients

Table 6.7: Results of mediation effects

Indirect Effect	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P
UIoT \rightarrow VIoT \rightarrow Fperf	0.064	0.027	0.106	0.008
UIoT \rightarrow VIoT \rightarrow Operf	0.081	0.033	0.135	0.009

6.5 Moderation Effect

Unlike mediation, moderation analysis allows you to see if a third variable, Z , has an impact on the relationship between X and Y (González-Romá *et al.*, 2017). Rather than looking for a cause-and-effect relationship between these other variables, moderation examines when and under what circumstances an effect happens. Moderation, in other words, looks for interactions that influence the timing of correlations between variables. The relationship between two variables can be strengthened (increasing the moderator increases the effect of the predictor on the outcome), weakened (increasing the moderator decreases the effect of the predictor on the outcome), or reversed (increasing the moderator decreases the effect of the predictor on the outcome) using a moderator (Williams *et al.*, 2009).

To test the hypotheses H4 and H5, two-stage approach to interaction modelling was adopted. In step one, the values of the variables of interest, i.e., UIoT, VIoT, and DDIPC, were standardized using the IBM SPSS, which created three new standardized variables. In the second stage, standardized variables were multiplied as per the requirement of the study to obtain a single element indicator signifying the product of the two measured variables, i.e., UIoT x DDIPC and VIoT x DDIPC. These product terms were entered into the model and analysed alongside other variables. The results show that the product term UIoT x DDIPC and FPerf are linked positively at standardized coefficient (β) of 0.005 and p-value of <0.01. Similarly, UIoT x DDIPC and OPerf are associated positively at standardized coefficient (β) of 0.012, with a significant p-value (<0.05). In addition, the product term VIoT x DDIPC and FPerf are linked positively at standardized coefficient (β) of 0.033 and p-value of <0.01. Similarly, VIoT x DDIPC and OPerf are associated positively at standardized coefficient (β) of 0.012, with a significant p-value (<0.05). Figure 6.5 (a) and (b) present the moderating slopes graphically and Table 6.8 shows the summary of the moderating effects.

Table 6.8: Summary of moderating effect

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
OPERF <--- VIoT x DDIPC	0.012	0.021	0.563	0.574
OPERF <--- UIoT x DDIPC	0.033	0.028	1.178	0.239
FPerf <--- UIoT x DDIPC	0.005	0.019	0.261	0.794
FPerf <--- VIoT x DDIPC	0.033	0.014	2.258	0.024

Figure 6.5: Moderating effect of DDIPCs on (a) UIoT and firm performance; and (b) VIoT and firm performance

6.6 Final Model

As mentioned in section 6.2, the model was revised to get a good model fit, as the previous model saw high co-variances between variables showing poor fit indices. After running the model for goodness of fit three times, the third model was chosen as it showed excellent fitness indices (Section 6.3.3, Table 6.5). The revised model is shown in Figure 6.6.

Figure 6.6: Finalised revised model

As seen from the figure above, it can be deduced that a positive relationship of Connectivity with DDIPCs and Visibility is found showing beta values of 0.52 and 0.14 respectively. Although the beta value of 0.14 is weak, but a positive value shows a clear impact of Connectivity on Visibility. Similarly, Flexibility has shown a positive relationship with DDIPCs and Visibility with beta values of 0.07 and 0.10 respectively. Likewise, Agility saw a positive relationship with DDIPCs and Visibility with same beta values of 0.08. Both Flexibility and Agility have shown weak relationships, but as they are positive and show good fitness, they have been considered for the final model.

In addition, as use of IoT has no positive direct link with both financial and operational performance due to negative values of beta, it can be seen that when moderated and mediated

by DDIPCs and Visibility it shows a considerable positive relationship with financial and operational performance. Summary of moderation effects can be seen from the Figure 6.7.

Figure 6.7: Summary of moderation effects (1)

It is evident from the figure above that although beta values for moderation effects are weak (0.005 and 0.012), they are showing a positive relationship which proves that DDIPCs moderate relationships between use of IoT and financial and operational performance.

Figure 6.8: Summary of moderation effects (2)

Figure 6.8 shows moderation effect of DDIPCs on Visibility and financial and operational performance. Although the beta values are weak for both effects, i.e. 0.033 and 0.012, they are positive which shows a weak but positive moderation effect.

The mediation effects are summarised in Table 6.7 (Section 6.4). As evident from the results, high beta values of 0.064 and 0.081 show strong mediation effect of visibility between use of IoT and financial and operational performance. Overall, these results led to the formation of the finalised model as shown in Figure 6.6.

6.7 Summary

The results of SEM showed some interesting results. It was theorised that connectivity, flexibility and agility of IoT enhanced the use of IoT in manufacturing firms. However, it was revealed that flexibility and agility had no direct relationship with the use of IoT. Connectivity of these devices seemed to enhance the use of IoT within the firms. In addition, use of IoT had no direct impact on financial and operational performance. However, when mediated by visibility, use of IoT had a significant positive impact and played a crucial role in enhancing financial as well as operational performance. Furthermore, the results showed that DDIPCs seemed to dampen the negative relationship between use of IoT and financial and operational performance. However, DDIPCs strengthened the relationship between visibility and financial and operational performance when treated as a moderator. In addition to the hypotheses, it was revealed that connectivity, agility and flexibility of IoT devices had a positive relationship with DDIPCs. This meant that these parameters enhance the DDIPC skills of the firms, and therefore the financial and operational performance of the firms. Similarly, it was discovered that these parameters showed a positive relationship with visibility as well. The results are discussed in detail in the next chapter.

Chapter 7 Discussion, Conclusion and Limitations

7.1 Introduction

This chapter provides an in-depth discussion of the research findings. It addresses how well the analyses conducted in Chapters 5 and 6 were able to answer the research questions and achieve the study's objectives. To a significant extent, theory and literature support these discussions. The elements affecting the usage of IoT within organisations are identified in this chapter, followed by their relationships and impact on firm performance. The effect of IoT, visibility, and DDIPC on financial and operational performance will be discussed (RQ1-RQ3) and conclusions will be provided based on the statistical results. Finally, a summary of the findings, contributions to the literature, practical and academic implications and limitations and future research suggestions will be provided.

7.2 Discussion of Results

The fundamental goal of this research is to see how manufacturers might use IoT to improve their financial and operational performance. Within industry 4.0, the majority of the studies focus on the contributions and risks of IoT in terms of flexibility, transparency, information exchange, connectivity, traceability, and tracking. Despite extensive research in these domains, it has been discovered that research into the links and impacts of IoT, visibility, and DDIPCs is limited. Among all aspects of technology, the introduction of IoT has had a significant impact on enterprises' production approaches and has significantly transformed operational and financial structures. However, the significance of IoT in manufacturing has yet to be fully explored in terms of firm performance. The relevant literature on the subject is generally fragmented, with most of it focusing on in-depth analyses of specific examples, with an emphasis on engineering factors (Akhtar *et al.*, 2018; Gattullo *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, the majority of the research is conceptual, and case based. In addition, no large-scale survey-based

empirical study has yet been conducted to establish and evaluate a mechanism for how IoT might help firms improve their performance. The lack of a clear and established path to using IoT product systems inhibits adoption and stops manufacturers from fully exploiting the technology's promise. This study closes these gaps by answering the following research questions:

- What is the impact of connectivity, flexibility and agility of IoT devices on the use of IoT in firms in manufacturing industries?
- How is the use of IoT related to data processing of the firms and how does visibility affect this relationship?
- What is the impact of use of IoT and visibility gained through interlinked DDIPCs on operational and financial firm performance?

These research questions are addressed by examining hypotheses (H1 to H5). Structural equation modelling, a multivariate technique, using IBM AMOS 26, is employed to inspect these relationships. Data analysis results indicate that hypotheses H1a, H3a, H3b, H4a, H4b, H5a and H5b are statistically supported, whereas hypotheses H1b, H1c, H2a and H2b are proved to be non-significantly supported.

To answer the first question, literature related to IoT was thoroughly reviewed. Furthermore, the key determinants for use of IoT are developed through extensive literature review: connectivity, flexibility and agility. The first question is then addressed by testing hypotheses H1a, H1b and H1c. The findings suggest that connectivity indeed has a significant positive relation with use of IoT, however, flexibility and agility showed no direct relationship with use of IoT. Interestingly, it was revealed that when combined with visibility and DDIPCs, flexibility and agility showed an enhanced positive relation to firm performance. These findings thus recommend that firms should utilise connectivity, flexibility and agility along with visibility and DDIPCs to gain efficient performance.

To answer the second question, hypotheses H2a, H2b, H4a, H4b, H5a and H5b are examined. This question is the one that literature could not provide a consistent empirical evidence, although theoretical back was found. This study finds that use of IoT has statistically significant

impact on firm performance only if moderated by DDIPCs. This also explains why several manufacturing firms struggle to achieve desired performance after adopting IoT.

To further explain this situation found above, the third question is answered by hypothesis H3a and H3b. The results from data analysis reveal that the degree of use of IoT impacts the firm performance depends on the use of information visibility. Manufacturers operating in low-visibility environment will suffer in firm performance without having analytics to deal with huge amounts of data gathered as a result of using IoT technology. This result might suggest companies should focus on their adopting both DDIPCs and visibility rather than just focusing on implementing IoT.

The following sections provide detailed discussion of the results.

7.2.1 Connectivity, Flexibility and Agility of IoT (RQ1)

The initial goal of this study was to look into the impact of IoT device connection, flexibility, and agility on the use of IoT in manufacturing firms, as well as the amount to which IoT usage impacted company performance. A thorough literature review (Chapters 2 and 3) was used to conceptualise and assess these dimensions, and the goal was met through a survey of UK manufacturing enterprises.

The term "connectivity" is used in IoT sector to define the specific IoT network solutions that can support this type of connectivity (Siddiqi *et al.*, 2018; Celestine *et al.*, 2020). In terms of boosting connectivity, IoT technologies such as cellular, Wi-Fi, and M2M offer a variety of options. M2M, which is an important aspect of IoT connectivity in the manufacturing business, has demonstrated a new wireless technology that allows items to communicate with each other, humans, and massive computing systems all over the world. M2M enables two machines to communicate with one another or for one machine to deliver data in one direction to another. It's widely used in Industry 4.0, allowing machines and systems to communicate more effectively and even to create totally new processes and systems. A smooth connection is required for M2M to perform properly (Dalenogare *et al.*, 2018).

This study reveals that connectivity indeed has a positive impact on the use of IoT, due to a significant relationship found between these two constructs showing $\beta = 0.16$ ($p < 0.05$). This also supported H1a. This is in line with the findings of Jeon *et al.*, (2020), who claimed that each IoT device must meet specific critical system requirements in order to function effectively, such as ensuring steady network connections and efficiently managing system resources. In addition, for effective performance, IoT applications must meet additional special requirements such as low range, low data rate, low energy consumption, and cost effectiveness (T. C. Lin *et al.*, 2018; A. Pradhan *et al.*, 2018; Celestine *et al.*, 2020). This observation is also consistent with the findings of Mekki *et al.*, (2019), who claimed that data transmission delays caused by inadequate connectivity could have a negative influence on all IoT devices. With the evolution of IoT roles from simple sensing and transmitting equipment to sensing, gathering, processing, and service roles, periodic requests between IoT devices are on the rise. With the evolution of IoT from 4G and Wi-Fi 5 to 5G and Wi-Fi 6, enhanced connectivity in terms of capacity, efficiency, and flexibility has become critical (Maisiri *et al.*, 2021). As a result, IoT device connectivity is discovered to play a significant role in boosting the utilisation of IoT in Industry 4.0.

Connectivity has also shown to have a positive relation with DDIPCs ($\beta = 0.52$, $p < 0.01$). This backs up the conclusions of Ahmad *et al.*, (2018), who claimed that IoT adoption is contingent on the availability of specific technology, organisational skills, and policies. Ge *et al.*, (2009), Wamba *et al.*, (2017) and Queiroz *et al.*, (2018) demonstrated that analytical capabilities play a significant role in organisational capabilities, allowing companies to benefit from data provided by IoT sources. However, some businesses lack the ability to expand beyond their endpoint and connectivity products, implying a critical need for seamless end-to-end connectivity that can assist businesses in collecting real-time data that can be used to improve performance (Chaniyas *et al.*, 2019).

The growth slope is apparent, and the prospects are becoming much more obvious to even the least exposed observers as operating systems get broader and more open as IoT-oriented devices and tools undergo tremendous technology explosion. The degree of acceptance and, (Liao *et al.*, 2017) perhaps more crucially, satisfaction that they provide is mainly determined

by the user's flexibility. Operating systems are no longer bound to a particular piece of hardware or a typical operating tool, as they are ubiquitous and totally cloud-based, allowing for new prospects to be developed in Industry 4.0. The fundamental goal of firms is to satisfy clients during the product delivery process, which is dictated by the architectural flexibility of the firm. This increases a firm's competitiveness (Tang *et al.*, 2019).

However, it is observed that there is a negative significant relationship between flexibility and the use of IoT, with $\beta = -0.025$ at $p < 0.1$. This reveals that there is no direct relationship between these two constructs, rejecting H1b. This also contradicts (Wu *et al.*, 2013), who claimed that the degree of acceptance, and, more crucially, the convenience that IoT goods provide, is largely determined by the user's flexibility. It might also be argued that flexibility by itself cannot be considered a measure to make IoT use easier for users. The results of this study's analysis show that IoT device flexibility has a positive significant link with visibility and DDIPCs, with values of $\beta = 0.10$ ($p < 0.05$) and $\beta = 0.16$ ($p < 0.05$) correspondingly. This supports the findings of Williams *et al.*, (2013), Szydlo *et al.*, (2017), Kazancoglu *et al.*, (2021) and Jagtap *et al.*, (2019), who stated that adaptable platforms acquire, validate, and enrich data with analytics before mixing it with other resources. They then let IoT devices to expose the generated intelligence to apps that produce commercial outcomes, such as optimising energy production for a utility or decreasing manufacturing process faults. As a result, the architecture of IoT systems must be flexible in terms of its requirements to handle different wireless protocols, reduce power consumption, and add additional sensor inputs, which may be accomplished through improved visibility and DDIP capabilities of the companies (da Silva *et al.*, 2019). Today's businesses must supply goods and services to clients as rapidly and cheaply as feasible, while still delivering exceptional product distribution and customer value. This can be accomplished if the manufacturing network chains have access to information about all parts of the production processes, as well as the firms' DDIP ability to utilise this data to provide actionable insights can enhance firm performance (Mostafa *et al.*, 2019; Mikalef *et al.*, 2021). An ideal situation would have a flawless end-to-end information flow as well as a flexible IoT architecture to ensure that enterprises' productivity is increased to a higher degree.

One of the properties of IoT devices that has attracted enterprises all around the world is smart response (Yang *et al.*, 2013; Li *et al.*, 2016). The capacity of IoT to manage faults and modifications in a timely manner has been described as one of the drivers for organisations embracing IoT. In today's business world, agility is critical for firm innovation and competitive success (Akhtar *et al.*, 2018). Firms are progressively using IoT into their daily operations in order to improve their agility (Ly *et al.*, 2018). Lu, (2017) and Akhtar *et al.*, (2018) found that the usage of IoT improves response operations in terms of specialised actions, situational assessment, resource allocations, and multi-organizational coordination. In fact, IoT gives all company network operations the opportunity to be more agile, and the use of such advanced technology is vital for modern business operations to become more agile (Gu *et al.*, 2014; Nastic *et al.*, 2014).

However, no direct implication of agility has been observed on the use of IoT, as the relationship between agility and use of IoT had a negative significant connection ($\beta = 0.05$, $p < 0.01$). This contradicts the findings of Akhtar *et al.*, (2018), who argued that agility of IoT provides competitive advantage to the firms. However, as found in the results that agility has a positive impact on DDIPCs and visibility, it backs up the claim made by Akhtar *et al.*, (2018) that agility, when combined with DDIPCs, can significantly improve firm performance. It is critical to recognise critical data and events, as well as reply fast when something noteworthy occurs, in order to achieve speed and accuracy (Szydlo *et al.*, 2017; Oteafy *et al.*, 2018). This supports the findings of Um, (2017), Warner *et al.*, (2019) and Mak *et al.*, (2020), who discovered that businesses can be more agile as a result of real-time visible fine-grained knowledge obtained through internet-connected devices and companies' ability to effectively receive and transmit information in a timely manner.

7.2.2 Visibility and DDIPC (RQ2)

The second objective of this research was to analyse how the use of IoT is related to data processing of the firms and how does visibility affect this relationship. It helped to answer RQ2 with regards to the impact of DDIPCs and visibility on firm performance.

Previous research has found that IoT has a large and favourable impact on business performance. With the increased focus on how emerging technologies are enabling digital transformations of businesses, a number of studies have been published that look into how operations are rearranged when embracing Industry 4.0 and how this affects businesses. Scholars appear to agree on the efficiency improvements associated with digital transformation of manufacturing processes in companies that have implemented advanced and distributed control over their processes (including production and supply chain). Scholars have claimed that companies who leverage IoT solutions to turn technology developments into competitive advantages develop the ability to create new value streams and outperform their competitors (YIN *et al.*, 2016; Khan *et al.*, 2018; Oztemel *et al.*, 2020). Although IoT appears to improve firm performance, some contend that deploying IoT alone is insufficient to establish a competitive advantage within businesses (Tse *et al.*, 2016; Manavalan *et al.*, 2019; Matthyssens, 2019; Mastos *et al.*, 2020; Al-Rakhami *et al.*, 2021). Firms may efficiently deploy lean manufacturing solutions by relying on new IoT solutions that help to improve control over material and information flow.

This work provides empirical support to these arguments. The findings of this study show that direct relationship between use of IoT and financial and operational performance does not exist, due to a negative $\beta = -0.027$ and $\beta = -0.034$ at $p < 0.01$ respectively. This rejects H2a and H2b. This also supports the findings of (Aydiner *et al.*, 2019), who stated that IoT alone no longer has a direct impact on company performance, as more standardised and uniform DDIPCs solutions are being offered to businesses. With the emergence of a more dynamic and discontinuous business environment, a flexible and inventive structure is required, requiring businesses to make more responsive decisions (Sher *et al.*, 2004). This conclusion backs with the findings of Dalenogare *et al.*, (2018) and Benitez *et al.*, (2020), who claimed that it's unclear how IoT investments affect a broader range of performance over time. The outcomes of this study fill this void by indicating DDIPCs and visibility aid use of IoT to enhance firm performance.

Firms must use the links between DDIPCs and IoT to quickly build, deploy, and modify business models to stay relevant in the emerging digital economy (Jiang *et al.*, 2015; Akhtar *et al.*, 2018; Warner *et al.*, 2019). However, the current study lacked empirical evidence.

This research is evident that DDIPCs moderate the relationship between use of IoT and financial and operational performance by having a significant positive relationship of $\beta = 0.005$ and $\beta = 0.033$ respectively significant at $p < 0.01$. This shows that although use of IoT has no direct impact on firm performance, it has a considerable positive impact when moderated by DDIPCs. Therefore, DDIPCs strengthen the relationship between IoT and firm performance. This finding supports academic arguments that DDIPCs improve firm performance when linked to the use of IoTs in a variety of ways: they match the resource base with changing environments by gathering useful data (Teece, 2018), they improve the effectiveness, speed, and efficiency of organisational responses by utilising valuable data, and they ultimately improve performance. According to Wamba *et al.*, (2017), when a company's ability to process information matches its information processing requirements, it can obtain better results. For businesses that operate in a fast-changing environment, the relationship between IoT and DDIPCs is critical where it is vital for them to respond and adapt to changes and environmental uncertainties in a timely manner (Sher *et al.*, 2004). This conclusion backs with the findings of Wilden *et al.*, (2013), who claimed that the development of IoT does not always lead to greater performance; rather, the context in which dynamic capabilities are implemented has an impact on performance.

According to the findings of Sher *et al.*, (2004), Wilden *et al.*, (2013), Y. Fan *et al.*, (2016), Wamba *et al.*, (2017), De Mendonca *et al.*, (2018) and Aydiner *et al.*, (2019), the lack of a positive impact of information systems on firm performance could be explained by factors such as the lack of appropriate data, the existence of time lags between information systems and the business value generated by these systems (Gupta *et al.*, 2016; Al-Surmi *et al.*, 2019). Until date, research has suggested that information visibility is important for increasing company performance. According to research Jagtap *et al.*, (2019), Mostafa *et al.*, (2019) and Rao *et al.*, (2019), firms that have access to information beyond their cooperative limits perform

significantly better than firms that do not. According to Oztemel *et al.*, (2020), the more precise the data, the greater the visibility and, as a result, the better the firm's success.

This investigation has provided empirical support to these opinions. It has been found that DDIPCs moderate the relationship between visibility and financial and operational performance by having a positive significant relation of $\beta = 0.033$ ($p < 0.01$) and $\beta = 0.012$ ($p < 0.05$) respectively. This supports Brusset *et al.*, (2017) notion that manufacturing processes that incorporate new resources into the company from external sources can be viewed as a critical dynamic capacity because they can change operating routes for both buying and providing firms. Furthermore, DDIPCs must rely on real-time data to comprehend market conditions and act accordingly. As a result, the usage of DDIPCs in manufacturing processes improves visibility (Holmström *et al.*, 2016). This research also supports the conclusions of Sher *et al.*, (2004), who claimed that effective and efficient information transfers inside a corporation are crucial to the establishment and maintenance of DDIPCs. The accessibility of information enables for the transmission of endogenous skills, experience, and knowledge throughout a company, hence improving performance. This also accepts H4a and H4b, which suggested that visibility mediates the impact of IoT on firm performance.

7.2.3 Impact of Use of IoT, Visibility and DDIPCs on Firm Performance (RQ3)

Tang *et al.*, (2018) suggested that a company's ability to adapt and supply smart products will provide it a competitive edge, reducing industry obstacles and reformulating value chain characteristics and structure. This research supports the RBV hypothesis that organisations gain a competitive edge and improved performance by combining valuable, rare, and inimitable resources (Liang *et al.*, 2010; Aydiner *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, RBV emphasises that the resources that enable enterprises to improve performance are distributed differently across organisations (Luz Tortorella *et al.*, 2021). Firms also employ these resources to accomplish strategies by effectively and efficiently building capabilities that may be exploited to improve corporate performance, according to Rungtusanatham *et al.* (2003) and Yang *et al.* (2013).

The ability of IoT to gather, store, process, and transmit information has informational effects. Enhanced data capture is linked to operational improvements through automation. Firms using centralised data can have greater control over information processing, allowing information and analysis to be shared across the organisation. This gives you more visibility and control over your business processes. It also enhances decision quality, responsiveness, empowerment, and resource use effectiveness, as evidenced by enhanced decision quality, responsiveness, empowerment, and resource use effectiveness (Kharlamov *et al.*, 2018; Somapa *et al.*, 2018; da Silva *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, effective information utilisation enhances administrative work efficiency as well as the effectiveness of management, communication, and planning procedures (Manavalan *et al.*, 2019).

The relationship between technological and administrative advances was studied by Lin *et al.*, (2018) and Maisiri *et al.*, (2021). They emphasise that in order to maintain or improve performance, businesses must make changes to their structures and procedures. While IoT technology allows businesses to improve their financial and operational performance, it also allows them to gain more control over their resources, improve cross-company cooperation, and better plan for the future. As a result, IoT investments boost company performance.

Using such technologies, according to Liang *et al.*, (2010), Yan *et al.*, (2016) and Werning *et al.*, (2020), can simplify and rationalise operations that promote the exchange of financial resources, strategic planning, and just-in-time provision between supply chain networks. Similarly, by enabling item recognition, monitoring, and tracking, which are critical enablers in attaining improved firm performance, such technologies can aid to enhance visibility and transparency throughout the supply chain (Akter *et al.*, 2016). As a result, Industry 4.0 digital technologies have the prospect to enable not just the creation of information, but also the sharing and integration of that information (Ben-Daya *et al.*, 2019) which is essential for the use of IoT to enhance firm performance (Tuptuk *et al.*, 2018). As a result, superfluous complexities are eliminated, and lead times are reduced. As a result, they can assist in improving response speed to uncertainties, which is critical to IoT, particularly for organisations with higher integrative prospects or those who have already implemented system-wide IoT.

7.3 Contributions to Theory and Practice

7.3.1 Contribution to Theory

This study contributes to the theoretical knowledge in the following aspects:

1. This research provides knowledge about the features of IoT, which contribute as the main drivers behind increasing implementation of IoT technologies in manufacturing firms. The comprehensive literature review provides key determinants of IoT that make IoT adaptable in these firms – connectivity, flexibility and agility of IoT technologies.
2. This study establishes a research framework based on RBV theoretical viewpoints. The data support this viewpoint, which states that organisations attain greater performance by combining valuable, uncommon, and non-substitutable resources. The use of IoT, when combined with the moderating effect of DDIPCs and the mediating effect of visibility, has a favourable impact on business performance, as evidenced by this study.
3. This study is one of the first studies that combines key determinants of IoT (connectivity, flexibility and agility) with DDIPCs and visibility to find the impact on both financial and operational performance.
4. The mediation effects of visibility help us to understand the relationship of IoT with firm performance. This research suggested that information visibility is more likely to be the source of achieving better firm performance than use of IoT alone.
5. The major contribution of this study to theory is that with a strong empirical evidence, this research reveals that an additional impact on performance generated from flexibility and agility of IoT devices when combined with visibility and DDIPCs of firms.

7.3.2 Contribution to Practice

The outcomes of this study have several important implications for manufacturing industry practitioners who are attempting to improve their performance by integrating IoT.

1. Despite the many advantages of IoT technology, visibility has been proven to be a valuable resource that has a major impact on business performance. Supply chain

- visibility, in particular, has been shown to improve company performance, although customer visibility has a greater impact on innovation outcomes. As a result, businesses must make a strategic decision to prioritise either their operational processes or their innovative outcomes, or both.
2. The second important resource that has a significant impact on business performance is DDIPCs. The capacity to upgrade, scale up or down, and reuse software components is emphasised in IoT capabilities. These qualities are critical for businesses because they help them become more adaptable in order to respond to changing customer demands. DDIPCs also let businesses to use real-time data obtained from massive amounts of data created by IoT devices in a timely and cost-effective manner. As a result, when engaging with IoT vendors, manufacturers must ensure that their IoT systems have a high level of this capability.
 3. IoT is gaining traction in academics and industry. Many businesses attempt to digitalize their business operations, yet often struggle to obtain the desired results. This research advises which competencies these businesses should concentrate on in order to improve their financial and operational success. Firms can develop these skills by leveraging the benefits of IoT product systems. IoT, which is equipped with sensors, can allow businesses to detect any changes or abnormalities and take appropriate action. Furthermore, because IoT systems can communicate with one another, they can govern and regulate other IoT systems, making operational control simple. In addition, with enhanced visibility of information, firms can achieve better communications throughout the manufacturing processes and network chains.
 4. This research implies that before making investment decisions or shifting priorities, businesses should analyse the peculiarities of their business environment. As previously said, delivering new items regularly in a low-environmental-dynamism environment does not help, but rather hurts revenues. Firms should concentrate their resources on digitising their service processes, as well as utilising their dynamic capabilities and information visibility, as these have been shown to increase firm performance. Firms, on the other hand, can offer both new services and goods in an environment with high

environmental dynamism. Both are proven to be supportive of positive company performance.

7.4 Limitations and Future Research

This study contains limitations, despite the fact that it was properly conducted and followed guidelines and suggestions. Given these limitations, the study's conclusions should be interpreted with caution. Future research should focus on overcoming these constraints. First, in this study's questionnaire, each observation represents a separate company, and each respondent answers the questions in the questionnaire only once. Because he or she was asked about practises and performance, there could have been response bias. Because of the costs associated with the practise, having several respondents answer the questionnaire for one company is difficult. Future research might use multiple respondents from an organization to confirm the results of this study.

Second, while this study is cross-sectional, it asks about company and supply chain performance, both of which are longitudinal in character. Because performance varies over time, future research should validate the research model in this study using secondary longitudinal firm performance data. Using secondary data for longitudinal analysis might broaden the study's scope and eliminate respondent bias.

Third, in the final research model, the author discovered a full mediation impact of visibility on firm performance, implying that the direct association between IoT use and firm performance is not entirely explained by IoT alone. Overall, because the study recommends a resource-based approach to analysing the influence of IoT on company performance, generalisation may be a concern. The findings could be a reflection of high individualism and self-interest ideals (Belhadi *et al.*, 2021).

Fourth, the empirical evidence only applies to the manufacturing industry in the United Kingdom; more study is needed to confirm the concept of a resource-based approach in other contexts. It will be interesting to see how the results alter in other countries, cultures, or degrees

of development. Firms' IoT adoption and related performance would fluctuate depending on their starting point or business climate. Future comparative research could look into how IoT product systems are implemented in different countries and whether the results are different. It would also be interesting to watch how far firms in emerging nations like China, Japan, and South Africa have adopted IoT product systems and what benefits they have reaped from them. Those studies would contribute to the field's understanding.

Fifth, this research was limited to high level employees of the firms such as managers, supervisors, CEOs etc. It would be interesting to know how lower level employees respond to IoT and its usage within the firms. In addition, it would add to the current knowledge to conduct a study on any other sector besides manufacturing, to know how it behaves in the adoption of these technologies.

Finally, this study considered overall organization. Human resources can be included in future studies to know the behaviour of employees when using IoT technology. For instance, if technology fails during production processes and humans have to be added to carry out the function, it would add to the current knowledge to know how it will impact the use of IoT.

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Appendix A Questionnaire

A.1 Use of IoT, Visibility, DDIPC and Firm Performance Survey

Section A: Company Profile

This section relates to the background of your company. The questions are meant only for analysis purposes and it will NOT be used to identify your responses individually. Please select one from the alternatives provided.

1. Name of your company (optional): _____
2. Number of years the company has been operating: _____
3. Number of full-time employees in your company

1	Less than 50
2	50 to 100
3	101 to 200
4	201 to 500
5	More than 500
6	Other (please specify)

4. Sales of the company: _____
5. Assets of the company: _____
6. Are you aware of IoT?

1	Yes
2	No

7. Are you using IoT in your firm:

1	Yes
2	No

8. To what extent are the following IoT technologies used by your company?

(Please rate where 0= not at all and 4= large extent)

Email	0	1	2	3	4
Bar coding	0	1	2	3	4
EDI	0	1	2	3	4
Intranet	0	1	2	3	4
Internet	0	1	2	3	4
Electronic funds transfer/Transfer transaction (TT)	0	1	2	3	4
Enterprise resource planning	0	1	2	3	4
Activity based costing	0	1	2	3	4
If others, please specify: _____					

Section B: Respondent Profile

1. Your Position in the company: _____

2. Years stayed at the company: _____

3. Gender

1	Male
2	Female

Section C: Please CIRCLE the number that corresponds to how much you agree or disagree with the following statements.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Agree	Agree	Somewhat Agree	Neutral	Somewhat Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree

Connectivity of IoT (Wamba <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Abdel-Basset <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Kimani <i>et al.</i> , 2019)								
1	There is a stable network connection between IoT devices.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2	Interconnectivity of IoT helps to efficiently manage system resources.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
3	Interconnectivity between IoT devices helps to provide more effective coordination among different functional activities.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
4	It easily helps to access data and other valuable resources in real time for business partners.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
5	It helps in effective assimilation of new information and knowledge to assist in decision-making process.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Flexibility of IoT (Jeon <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Afzal <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Garrido-Hidalgo <i>et al.</i> , 2019)								
6	Different wireless protocols can be handled easily	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
7	IoT infrastructure has the ability to scale down during off-peak times	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	It is easy to add new devices, services and functions into the IoT system without affecting the quality of service	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
9	IoT system enables the firm to add or remove context information according to the needs of the operation	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

10	IoT provides better service delivery	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Agility of IoT (Sambamurthy <i>et al.</i> , 2003; Akhtar <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Fosso Wamba <i>et al.</i> , 2019)								
11	Reliability of our offerings (i.e. services and products) has increased	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
12	Our offerings are most cost efficient than competitors	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
13	We accomplish greater speed in delivering our offerings	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
14	Our response to market changes is very flexible	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
15	We are very quick to adopt market opportunities	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Visibility of IoT (Ellis <i>et al.</i> , 2018)								
16	We exchange performance evaluation with the supplier.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
17	We frequently discuss strategic issues with the supplier.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
18	The firm operates transparently with other involved organizations to ensure that all the transactions are visible quickly.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
19	Inventory levels are visible throughout the supply chain.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
20	Demand levels are visible throughout the supply chain.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Use of IoT (Mikalef <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Akhtar <i>et al.</i> , 2018)								
21	We are highly dependent on IoT in order to track and trace our objects	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
22	We use IoT to monitor our operational environments	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
23	UIoT continuously assists to innovate our business operations	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
24	We often collect unstructured data via IoT	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
25	It has increased your firm's productivity and efficiency	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
DDIPCs (Kuang, 2009; Brandon-Jones <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Hasegan <i>et al.</i> , 2018)								
26	We have excellent expertise to process structural data	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
27	Our analytics personnel (team etc.) actively get insights from unstructured data	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
28	The programming skills of our personnel greatly helps us to get analytical insights from the large database	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
29	We effectively process complicated data and information	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

30	We effectively use real time information for day to day operations	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Financial Performance (Cho <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Wuttke <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Ma <i>et al.</i> , 2020)								
31	Average return on investment (ROI) has increased over the past 5 years.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
32	Average profit over the past 5 years has shown an increase.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
33	There has been an increase in the pre-tax return on assets (ROA) over the past 5 years.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
34	There has been an increase in the market value of the firm over the past 5 years.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
35	Earnings per share have shown an increase in the past 5 years.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Operational Performance (Parkan <i>et al.</i> , 1999; Protopappa-Sieke <i>et al.</i> , 2010; Paksoy <i>et al.</i> , 2011)								
36	The delivery speed of the firm has shown an increase after the adoption of IoT.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
37	There has been a stable energy and resource consumption by the firm.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
38	An effective scheduling technique is used by the firm.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
39	The maintenance and repair costs have decreased after the implementation of IoT.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
40	The operations have shown flexibility in configuring the product lines to deal and adjust with different requirements.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Appendix B Consent Form

B.1 Consent Form

Title of Study	Impact of the use of IoT, visibility and DDIPCs on firm performance.
Participant Details	Name: Email: Age:

Please initial box

- 1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated
(version) for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
- 2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time.
- 3. I agree to provide evidence of my identity which will be used for the sole purpose for my
participation in this study.
- 4. I consent to the anonymous use of the test scores obtained by the research team in scientific
reports and journals.
- 5. I agree to take part in the above study.

Participant:

Date:

Researcher:

Date:

N.B. You should keep a copy of this consent form and the participant information sheet for your records.

Appendix C Participant Information Sheet

C.1 Participant Information Sheet

RESEARCH PROJECT ON THE IMPACT OF USE OF IoT AND DDIPCS ON FIRM PERFORMANCE

To Executive Manager,

Dear Sir/Madam,

At the outset I would like to thank you for taking time to participate in this academic research survey. This research aims to understand the operational and financial performance of firms in manufacturing industries when it comes to new technologies, particularly the IoT. This study will help in increasing our understanding of the impact of the use of IoT with interlinked DDIPCs on firm performance, by building a relationship between the use of IoT, visibility, DDIPCs and operational and financial performance of a firm. I am looking to study the impact of visibility, connectivity, flexibility and agility of connected devices on IoT usage, and what is the impact of using these devices on firm performance. The intention of this study is to develop a framework for practitioners to improve firm performance by implementing the IoT into their daily operations. The information you provide will make an insightful contribution to my research. Hence, I am inviting you to participate in this academic survey.

The questionnaire will require approximately 10-12 minutes. Your participation in this survey is voluntary and you can withdraw if you wish not to participate in it. There is no right or wrong answers. There are no risks associated with participating in this survey and it collects no identifying information of any respondents. All of the responses in the survey will be recorded anonymously and all the information will be held in strictest confidence, as has always been the policy of the University. When the results from my PhD thesis are published, it will be impossible to identify an individual person or company.

I am aware that your esteemed organization has been very busy and undoubtedly, this has taken much of your time. However, your company's participation is very much important to meet the objectives of this study. Thank you for your time and assistance in my research and educational endeavours. Your participation is highly appreciated.

Yours faithfully,

Tahera Kalsoom

PhD Candidate

Email: [REDACTED]

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Appendix D Ethical Approval Form

Project Information

Title of Study

Impact of the use of IoT and DDIPCs on firm performance

Primary purpose of the study

Original Research

Where will the proposed research take place?

This is a quantitative research, and the questionnaires are to be distributed online to the manufacturing firms based in UK.

How will the costs of the study be met?

This is an online survey, to be sent to the targeted respondents via email. Therefore, there are no costs to this study.

Previous Approvals

Has the proposed study been considered by any other ethics committee?

- Yes
 No

Supporting Documents

Please upload any additional supporting documents you are submitting with this application

Signatures

Principal Investigator

The information supplied above is, to the best of my knowledge and belief, accurate. I have read the university ethics guidelines and clearly understand my obligations and the rights of study participants, particularly in relation to obtaining valid consent.

Signed: This form was signed by Tahera Kalsoom [REDACTED] on 12/02/2020 12:47 PM

Supervisor/Director of Studies

I support the above application and I agree to supervise the work.

Signed: This form was signed by Naeem Ramzan [REDACTED] on 12/02/2020 2:41 PM

Appendix E Visual Representation of Responses

E.1 Graphical Representation of Responses

Appendix F Preliminary Analysis

F.1 Missing Data

Table F.1: Missing Data

	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Missing Data	
				Frequency	Percentage
CIoT1	376	2.73	0.830	2	0.5
CIoT2	376	2.86	0.893	2	0.5
CIoT3	376	2.72	0.884	2	0.5
CIoT4	376	3.09	0.912	2	0.5
CIoT5	376	2.99	0.943	2	0.5
FIoT1	376	3.03	0.951	2	0.5
FIoT2	376	2.88	0.896	2	0.5
FIoT3	376	2.65	0.969	2	0.5
FIoT4	376	3.24	0.962	2	0.5
FIoT5	376	2.53	0.991	2	0.5
AIoT1	376	2.67	1.029	2	0.5
AIoT2	376	2.40	0.937	2	0.5
AIoT3	376	2.36	0.976	2	0.5
AIoT4	376	2.20	0.825	2	0.5
AIoT5	376	2.25	0.912	2	0.5
VIoT1	376	2.25	0.854	2	0.5
VIoT2	376	4.03	0.708	2	0.5
VIoT3	375	3.98	0.700	3	0.8
VIoT4	375	3.98	0.710	3	0.8

VloT5	376	3.98	0.690	2	0.5
UloT1	375	4.04	0.703	3	0.8
UloT2	376	4.07	0.698	2	0.5
UloT3	376	4.09	0.688	2	0.5
UloT4	376	3.46	0.925	2	0.5
UloT5	376	3.49	0.929	2	0.5
DDIPC1	376	3.54	0.908	2	0.5
DDIPC2	376	3.72	0.830	2	0.5
DDIPC3	376	3.37	0.951	2	0.5
DDIPC4	375	3.64	0.854	3	0.8
DDIPC5	376	3.72	0.858	2	0.5
FPerf1	376	3.99	0.643	2	0.5
FPerf2	376	3.85	0.686	2	0.5
Fperf3	374	4.10	0.596	4	1.1
FPerf4	376	3.92	0.706	2	0.5
FPerf5	376	3.70	0.793	2	0.5
OPerf1	375	3.75	0.761	3	0.8
OPerf2	376	3.88	0.724	2	0.5
OPerf3	376	3.88	0.739	2	0.5
OPerf4	376	3.75	0.761	2	0.5
OPerf5	376	3.75	0.715	2	0.5

F.2 Univariate and Multivariate Outliers

Table F.2: Univariate Outliers

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Outlier Cases
CIoT1	375	-2.07548	2.75001	None
CIoT2	375	-2.05672	2.38508	None
CIoT3	375	-1.93833	2.57534	None
CIoT4	375	-2.27013	2.07730	None
CIoT5	375	-2.10338	2.13185	None
FIoT1	375	-2.12473	2.07952	None
FIoT2	375	-2.10248	2.36042	None

FloT3	375	-1.69723	2.43612	None
FloT4	375	-2.33224	1.83888	None
FloT5	375	-1.53995	2.49428	None
AloT1	375	-1.61922	2.26065	None
AloT2	375	-1.48174	2.76649	None
AloT3	375	-1.39004	2.73845	None
AloT4	375	-1.45833	3.39624	None
AloT5	375	-1.37700	3.07729	None
VloT1	375	-1.45697	3.22546	None
VloT2	375	-2.84936	1.36799	None
VloT3	375	-4.24626	1.45116	None
VloT4	375	-4.14217	1.42060	None
VloT5	375	-4.30213	1.47546	None
UloT1	371	-4.30003	1.35209	None
UloT2	375	-4.36340	1.32699	None
UloT3	375	-3.07485	1.32455	None
UloT4	375	-2.66348	1.66795	None
UloT5	375	-2.67909	1.63529	None
DDIPC1	375	-2.79788	1.61702	None
DDIPC2	375	-3.29480	1.54973	None
DDIPC3	375	-2.50332	1.71997	None
DDIPC4	375	-3.09118	1.59758	None
DDIPC5	375	-3.18347	1.49736	None
FPerf1	375	-3.07034	1.54137	None
FPerf2	375	-2.72015	1.66035	None
Fperf3	375	-3.38304	1.45731	None
FPerf4	375	-4.14514	1.51874	None
FPerf5	375	-3.40263	1.63529	None
OPerf1	375	-3.58077	1.62254	None
OPerf2	375	-3.92555	1.52844	None
OPerf3	375	-3.84915	1.49869	None
OPerf4	375	-3.59722	1.62999	None
OPerf5	375	-3.80539	1.72972	None

Figure F.1: Multivariate outliers

F.3 Skewness and Kurtosis

Table F.3: Skewness and Kurtosis values (normality)

	Skewness	Kurtosis
CIoT1	0.276	-0.454
CIoT2	0.117	-0.825
CIoT3	0.304	-0.450
CIoT4	-0.281	-0.705
CIoT5	-0.089	-0.900
FIoT1	-0.119	-0.931
FIoT2	0.071	-0.631
FIoT3	0.301	-0.768
FIoT4	-0.415	-0.724
FIoT5	0.442	-0.404
AIoT1	0.311	-0.866
AIoT2	0.851	0.208
AIoT3	0.707	-0.079

AIoT4	0.831	0.652
AIoT5	0.706	0.024
VIoT1	0.812	0.492
VIoT2	-0.716	1.013
VIoT3	-0.726	1.391
VIoT4	-0.624	0.952
VIoT5	-0.609	1.162
UIoT1	-0.567	0.838
UIoT2	-0.890	2.167
UIoT3	-0.328	-0.121
UIoT4	-0.377	-0.273
UIoT5	-0.412	-0.251
DDIPC1	-0.586	0.185
DDIPC2	-0.942	1.162
DDIPC3	-0.266	-0.458
DDIPC4	-0.617	0.214
DDIPC5	-0.732	0.582
FPerf1	-0.824	1.933
FPerf2	-0.679	0.974
Fperf3	-0.816	2.502
FPerf4	-0.866	1.914
FPerf5	-0.583	0.522
OPerf1	-0.726	0.958
OPerf2	-0.879	1.800
OPerf3	-0.615	0.903
OPerf4	-0.709	0.962
OPerf5	-0.660	0.983

Figure F.2: Skewness and Kurtosis for CIoT

Figure F.3: Skewness and Kurtosis for FIoT

Figure F.4: Skewness and Kurtosis for AIoT

Figure F.5: Skewness and Kurtosis for UIoT

Figure F.6: Skewness and Kurtosis for VIoT

Figure F.7: Skewness and Kurtosis for DDIPC

Figure F.8: Skewness and Kurtosis for FPERF

Figure F.9: Skewness and Kurtosis for OPERF

F.4 Multi-collinearity

Table F.4: Multi-collinearity

	Dependent Variable: Fperf		Dependent Variable: Operf	
	Collinearity Statistics		Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF	Tolerance	VIF
CIoT1	0.577	1.732	0.577	1.732
CIoT2	0.324	3.089	0.324	3.089
CIoT3	0.455	2.198	0.455	2.198
CIoT4	0.492	2.034	0.492	2.034
CIoT5	0.456	2.193	0.456	2.193
FIoT1	0.600	1.666	0.600	1.666
FIoT2	0.583	1.714	0.583	1.714
FIoT3	0.607	1.647	0.607	1.647
FIoT4	0.593	1.687	0.593	1.687
FIoT5	0.661	1.514	0.661	1.514
AIoT1	0.858	1.166	0.858	1.166
AIoT2	0.386	2.589	0.386	2.589
AIoT3	0.317	3.152	0.317	3.152
AIoT4	0.268	3.738	0.268	3.738
AIoT5	0.324	3.089	0.324	3.089
VIoT1	0.949	1.053	0.949	1.053
VIoT2	0.350	2.859	0.350	2.859
VIoT3	0.229	4.376	0.229	4.376
VIoT4	0.187	5.339	0.187	5.339
VIoT5	0.180	5.556	0.180	5.556
UIoT1	0.482	2.074	0.482	2.074
UIoT2	0.482	2.075	0.482	2.075
UIoT3	0.556	1.798	0.556	1.798
UIoT4	0.540	1.852	0.540	1.852
UIoT5	0.786	1.273	0.786	1.273
DDIPC1	0.379	2.641	0.379	2.641
DDIPC2	0.329	3.040	0.329	3.040

DDIPC3	0.348	2.870	0.348	2.870
DDIPC4	0.281	3.561	0.281	3.561
DDIPC5	0.253	3.946	0.253	3.946

F.5 Communalities

Table F.5: Communalities

	Extraction	
	Initial	Revised
CIoT1	0.394	0.473
CIoT2	0.690	0.802
CIoT3	0.569	0.619
CIoT4	0.580	0.590
CIoT5	0.758	0.602
FIoT1	0.802	Dropped
FIoT2	0.506	Dropped
FIoT3	0.535	0.560
FIoT4	0.591	0.613
FIoT5	0.498	0.458
AIoT1	0.528	Dropped
AIoT2	0.667	0.669
AIoT3	0.736	0.755
AIoT4	0.826	0.828
AIoT5	0.763	0.740
VIoT1	0.753	Dropped
VIoT2	0.679	0.652
VIoT3	0.797	0.795
VIoT4	0.864	0.880
VIoT5	0.885	0.888
UIoT1	0.701	Dropped
UIoT2	0.555	Dropped
UIoT3	0.566	0.580
UIoT4	0.762	0.744

UIoT5	0.260	0.263
DDIPC1	0.629	0.630
DDIPC2	0.673	0.677
DDIPC3	0.710	0.709
DDIPC4	0.784	0.784
DDIPC5	0.829	0.828
FPerf1	0.546	0.563
FPerf2	0.567	0.588
Fperf3	0.585	0.590
FPerf4	0.620	0.615
FPerf5	0.383	0.351
OPerf1	0.562	Dropped
OPerf2	0.738	0.734
OPerf3	0.841	0.831
OPerf4	0.554	0.572
OPerf5	0.625	0.630

F.6 Initial Factor Loadings

Table F.6: Initial factor loadings

Pattern Matrixa								
	Factor							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
CIoT1		0.569						
CIoT2		0.839						
CIoT3		0.721						
CIoT4		0.666						
CIoT5		0.931						
FIoT1		0.948						
FIoT2		0.631						
FIoT3						0.731		
FIoT4						0.757		
FIoT5						0.723		
AIoT1						0.682		

AIoT2			0.747					
AIoT3			0.850					
AIoT4			0.929					
AIoT5			0.877					
VIoT1			0.881					
VIoT2	0.775							
VIoT3	0.808							
VIoT4	0.957							
VIoT5	0.969							
UIoT1	0.842							
UIoT2	0.700							
UIoT3								0.751
UIoT4								0.875
UIoT5								0.488
DDIPC1					0.720			
DDIPC2					0.773			
DDIPC3					0.844			
DDIPC4					0.865			
DDIPC5					0.949			
FPerf1							0.663	
FPerf2							0.744	
Fperf3							0.703	
FPerf4							0.663	
FPerf5							0.490	
OPerf1				0.515			0.301	
OPerf2				0.873				
OPerf3				0.971				
OPerf4				0.718				
OPerf5				0.695				

Appendix G Model Testing

G.1 First Run

Table G.1: Structural model fit indices for the first run

Indices	Estimate	Interpretation
CMIN/DF	32.614	Acceptable
CFI	0.641	Poor
IFI	0.646	Poor
RMR	0.07	Poor
RMSEA	0.291	Poor
SRMR	0.203	Poor

Table G.2: Co-variances for first run

			M.I.	Par Change
e5	<-->	FIoT	4.031	.039
e5	<-->	CIoT	74.823	.141
e2	<-->	AIoT	9.753	.047
e2	<-->	FIoT	9.172	-.040
e1	<-->	CIoT	4.385	.016
e1	<-->	e2	168.669	.101

Table G.3: Regression Weights of first run

			M.I.	Par Change
DDIPC	<---	AIoT	21.698	.225
DDIPC	<---	FIoT	41.720	.356
DDIPC	<---	CIoT	115.608	.720
VIoT	<---	AIoT	11.108	.113
VIoT	<---	FIoT	12.462	.136
VIoT	<---	CIoT	5.780	.112
OPerf	<---	AIoT	5.190	.075
FPerf	<---	CIoT	6.740	.081

Figure G.1: Structural model first run

G.2 Second Run

Table G.4: Structural model fit indices for second run

Indices	Estimate	Interpretation
CMIN/DF	5.89	Acceptable
CFI	0.962	Good
IFI	0.962	Good
RMR	0.023	Good
RMSEA	0.114	Good
SRMR	0.151	Poor

Table G.5: Regression weights for second run

			M.I.	Par Change
VIoT	<---	AIoT	11.108	0.113
VIoT	<---	FIoT	12.462	0.136
VIoT	<---	CIoT	5.780	0.112
OPerf	<---	FIoT	7.857	-0.078
FPerf	<---	FIoT	6.247	0.047
FPerf	<---	CIoT	8.178	0.066

Figure G.2: Structural model second run